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Wien, im März 2021

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(Carlotta S. Tubeuf)

Acknowledgements

First of all, I would like to sincerely thank my thesis adviser Prof. René Hofmann for giving me the opportunity of working in the exciting field of industrial energy systems, for involving me in the HyStEPs project and for his valuable scientific supervision and advice.

I am very grateful to my second adviser Dr. Alexander Schirrer, who taught me a lot about the design of experiments and the modeling of dynamic optimization problems in MATLAB. I want to thank him for always finding time for my questions and for guiding me with his expertise.

Thank you to the members of the Industrial Energy Systems department for including me in their team and for letting me use their server to run numerous simulations. I want to especially thank my supervisor Lukas Kasper, who supported me in all aspects of this thesis and always had valuable advices and suggestions for me. I highly appreciate his kind efforts and help.

Additionally, I would like to express my gratitude to the voestalpine Stahl Donawitz GmbH, in particular the department of energy operations, for their financial support and for giving me the opportunity to write this thesis with them. I want to thank my supervisors Andreas Kiedl and Florian Javernik, who provided me guidance in the execution of this diploma thesis.

Abstract

With the ongoing transition from fossil to renewable energy sources and the progressing decarbonisation of the economy, the development of energy storages gains in importance. Thermal energy storage (TES) systems can increase the energy efficiency of industry processes through the possibility to store heat that would otherwise be released into the environment as waste heat. A common TES used in the industry is the Ruths steam storage (RSS). In the HyStEPs project, in which this thesis is embedded in, a novel approach of increasing the storage capacity of a RSS by surrounding it with a latent heat energy storage, which uses the phase change of a material to store large energy quantities, is researched.

As a preparation for the experimental investigation on this hybrid storage system, a detailed design of experiment was established in the course of this thesis. Through the implementation of an optimal experimental design (OED), the experimental conditions get optimized in order to increase the sensitivity of the experiments with regard to selected parameters. In this thesis, an OED for two sub-models of the hybrid storage was performed using statistical criteria which rely on scalar functions of the Fisher information matrix. It was proven, that the optimized storage loading scenarios led to higher parameter sensitivities than if charged and discharged with a trivial load case. Based on the conducted OED, a fully developed experimental plan for the upcoming experiments on the HyStEPs prototype storage was established. In addition to the experimental design, an upscaling model for the hybrid storage was developed, which allows to presume the necessary dimensions and expected costs of the storage depending on the desired maximum storage capacity.

Kurzfassung

Im Zuge der globalen Energiewende erhöht sich der Bedarf an Energiespeichern zur effektiven Nutzung des Potentials fortschrittlicher Energieanlagen, sowie zur Steigerung der Energieeffizienz in Industrieprozessen. Thermische Energiespeicher werden dabei häufig verwendet, um Dampferzeugungs- und Verbrauchsraten auszugleichen. Im Rahmen des HyStEPs Projekts, in dem auch diese Arbeit angesiedelt ist, wurde ein neuartiges Hybridspeicherkonzept entwickelt, bei dem gewöhnliche Ruthsspeicher mit Latentwärmespeicherpaketen umschlossen werden, und somit die Menge an speicherbarer Energie ohne signifikante Vergrößerung des erforderlichen Speichervolumens erhöht wird.

Um die geplanten Experimente an einem Prototyp des Hybridspeichers mit geringem zeitlichen Aufwand und möglichst aussagekräftigen Ergebnissen durchführen zu können, wurde in der vorliegenden Arbeit ein detailliertes, optimiertes Versuchsdesign erstellt. Dabei wurde mittels numerischer und statistischer Methoden der Einfluss bestimmter Parameter auf das Speicherverhalten analysiert und optimale Be- und Entladeszenarien ermittelt, so dass die zukünftigen Messergebnisse einen hohen Grad an Empfindlichkeit gegenüber einer Änderung in den jeweiligen Parameterwerten zeigen. Basierend auf den Ergebnissen wurde anschließend ein detaillierter Versuchsplan erstellt. Darüber hinaus wurde ein Modell zur Skalierung des Hybridspeichers entwickelt, mit Hilfe dessen die erforderlichen Dimensionen und voraussichtlichen Kosten des Speichers in Abhängigkeit von der gewünschten maximalen Speicherkapazität ermittelt werden können.

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Nomenclature

Abbreviations

DoE	design of experiment
FIM	Fisher information matrix
HTF	heat transfer fluid
HyStEPs	hybrid storage for efficient processes
LHTES	latent heat thermal energy storage
LoU	level of uncertainty
OED	optimal experimental design
PCM	phase change material
RSS	Ruths steam storage
TES	thermal energy storage

Greek Symbols

β	thermal expansion [1/K]
\mathcal{I}	Fisher information matrix
ψ	sensitivity matrix
θ	parameter vector
Δh	specific enthalpy [J/kg]
Δ	difference
ϵ	relative approximation error

γ	optimization variable
λ	eigenvalue
μ	dynamic viscosity [N s/m ²]
ρ	density [kg/m ³]
σ_{noise}^2	standard deviation of measurement
φ	angle [°]

Roman Symbols

e	vector of eigenvalues
M	mass matrix
T	step sequence matrix
u	input vector
x	state variable vector
y	output vector
\dot{m}	mass flow [kg/s]
\dot{Q}	thermal energy flow [J/s]
A	surface area [m ²]
a_m	mass fraction of molten PCM
b	width [m]
C	costs [€]
c	specific heat capacity [J/(kg K)] / cost coefficient [€/kg],[€/m ²]
c_p	specific heat capacity at constant pressure [J/(kg K)]
$c_{m,in}$	inlet mass flow geometric coefficient
d	diameter [m]
dT_m	area of melting [°C]
fl	filling level
h	heat transfer coefficient [W/(m ² K)]
k	thermal conductivity [W/(m K)]

l, L	length [m]
L/D	length to diameter ratio
lb	lower bound
m	mass [kg]
N_M	number of PCM modules
n_t	number of time steps
n_x	number of state variables
n_y	number of output variables
n_θ	number of parameters
N_{cell}	number of PCM cells
p	pressure [bar]
Q	heat storage capacity [J]
s	wall thickness [m]
T	temperature [°C]
t	time [s]
T_m	melting temperature [°C]
ub	upper bound
V	volume [m ³]
x	mean distance [m]

Subscripts

0	initial
a	outer / stationary air
alu	aluminium
bw	boiling water
cs	condensing steam
ds	dry steam
i	control variable / inner

<i>in</i>	input value
<i>iso</i>	isolation
<i>K</i>	torispherical
<i>l, liquid</i>	material parameter of liquid phase
<i>lw</i>	liquid water
<i>M</i>	PCM module
<i>o</i>	outer plate
<i>out</i>	output value
<i>PCM</i>	phase change material
<i>RSS</i>	RSS value
<i>s, solid</i>	material parameter of solid phase
<i>st</i>	steel
<i>sup</i>	supporting steel structure
<i>triv</i>	trivial case
<i>v</i>	vapour
<i>Z</i>	cylindrical

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Along with the increasing awareness of the urgency to take action to halt the climate crisis, the members of the UN have declared to decrease the rate of global warming through “[h]olding the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels [...]” (UNFCCC [1], Article 2) by signing the Paris Agreement in 2016. In order to achieve this aim, amongst others, a transition from fossil to renewable energy sources is inevitable. While fossil fuels are not as dependent on external environmental factors, renewable energy concepts are characterized by the significant temporal imbalance between energy production and energy consumption: energy from renewable sources is not always available the same moment it is required. Therefore, the further development of energy storages is essential with regards to the increased share of renewable energy sources in the grid and the progressing decarbonisation.

There are plenty of concepts for energy storages, some more sophisticated than others, some perhaps as old as civilization itself, some are just at the beginning of research. Different storages are suitable for various applications, depending on the physical form of the stored energy (electrical, chemical, mechanical or thermal), the storage period (hourly, diurnal, hebdomadal, seasonal, etc.), the economic viability and other individual factors that need to be taken into account [2].

In this thesis, the focus lies with thermal energy storage (TES) systems in general, and one new hybrid form of a TES in particular. TESs are of great potential for industry processes, where heat, that would otherwise be released into the environment as waste heat, can be stored and used at a later stage. In the iron and steel industry, which is one of the biggest industrial CO₂ emitters in the EU [3], but also in other industries such as the pulp and paper or the food sector, steam accumulators (Ruths steam storages) are commonly used to balance out steam production and consumption rates. By being able to react dynamically to power changes, steam storages increase the energy efficiency of steam supply in industry processes [4].

This thesis is embedded in the HyStEPs (Hybrid Storage for Efficient Processes) project which is funded by the national funding agency FFG with the grant number 868842, as part of the Climate and Energy Fund KLI.EN. within the NEFI - New Energy for Industry framework. The basic approach of this project is to increase the storage capacity and therefore the efficiency of existing Ruths steam storage (RSS) systems by developing a new hybrid storage concept, which surrounds a RSS with a latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) in the form of modules filled with phase change material (PCM). The project is coordinated by the Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT), which has a patent application (A 50571/2016) for the hybrid storage concept together the the TU Wien, and involves the project partners TU Wien, voest alpine Stahl Donawitz GmbH and Edtmayer Systemtechnik GmbH.

1.2 Aim and Scope

In order to guarantee an efficient and fast execution of the planned experimental investigations on the lab-scale device of the HyStEPs hybrid energy storage, it was decided to develop an optimal design of experiment (DoE) in the course of the present thesis. A detailed DoE facilitates the subsequent conduction of experiments by designing a comprehensive experimental plan. In this thesis, an optimal experimental design (OED) for the two sub-components of the HyStEPs storage, the RSS and the LHTES, is established, which

aims to determine a set of optimal loading scenarios for the experimental plan. Thereby, uncertain parameters, e.g. heat transfer or material properties, that are crucial for the characterisation of the storage behaviour, can be estimated with high statistical confidence from the postliminary recorded experimental data.

In addition to the establishment of the DoE, a contribution to the techno-economic analysis of the HyStEPs storage concept based on the experimental results was made with this thesis by developing an upscaling model for the hybrid storage. With this model, the required dimensions and material costs for the storage can be estimated for a range of maximum loading capacities of the RSS. These variables are subsequently integrated into a further scientific work, which aims to optimize the storage operations with regard to economic feasibility.

The present thesis is structured as follows. In Chapter 2, the theoretical backgrounds that are important for this thesis are given. First, sensible and latent TES systems and their fundamental principles are described, followed by the presentation of the HyStEPs hybrid storage concept. Further, the basics of parameter identification and the optimal experimental design are explained. In Chapter 3, the governing research questions are established, the parameters to be examined with the help of the OED are selected and the computation models of the HyStEPs sub-components are outlined. Thereupon, the structure of the optimization model for the DoE is described. The results of the OED are presented and discussed in Chapter 4, along with the description of the final design of the experimental plan. Chapter 5 covers the development of the upscaling model for the hybrid storage. Finally, the thesis is concluded in Chapter 6 by summarizing and reviewing it, and giving an outlook to future research.

1.3 Methodological Approach

In order to give an insight into thermal energy storage systems and the operating methods of the sub-components of the presented hybrid storage, a thorough literature study was conducted.

For the establishing of the DoE, a formulation of an optimal design of experiment, which is a method from system identification model theory, was chosen. The dynamic optimization model that utilizes statistical criteria related to the so called Fisher information matrix (FIM), a common concept in statistical theory [5], in order to estimate the optimal experimental plan, was implemented in MATLAB [6]. The nonlinear programming solvers `fmincon` and `ga`, available within the MATLAB optimization and global optimization toolbox, were utilized to maximize the statistical criteria.

The DoE and the development of a comprehensive plan for the experiments on the hybrid storage are based on existing models of the HyStEPs storage system: the pure steam storage model, developed by S. Dusek and R. Hofmann [7], the PCM cell model, developed by L. Kasper [8] and the co-simulation of both models, developed by D. Pernsteiner et al. [9].

The upscaling function for the RSS was established based on calculation norms for steam vessels and compliance of energy conversation laws. The necessary storage dimensions were iterated in MATLAB for variable maximum pressures and capacities. The estimated costs were derived with fixed cost coefficients.

Chapter 2

Theoretical Background

In order to fully grasp the initial idea and the functioning of the HyStEPs concept, it is crucial to understand the fundamental principles of the different thermal energy storage systems associated with it. As elaborated previously, the development of energy storage systems seeks to level out imbalances in energy supply and demand. Thermal energy storages thereby persuade through their high degree of flexibility, deriving from their compatibility with numerous energy technologies [10]. Thermal energy storage concepts can be divided into sensible, latent and thermochemical energy storages, as shown in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Overview of storage technologies for TES systems, after [11]

Although thermochemical energy storages can reach very high energy storage densities through chemical reactions, the current state of research of this type of storage is still in the early stages and, accordingly, is rarely applied at present [11]. Thermochemical energy storages are not discussed in the scope of this thesis, therefore they will not be further discussed. In the following chapters, the thermodynamic characteristics and functionalities of sensible heat energy storages and latent heat energy storages will be explained, and thereupon, the novel hybrid steam storage concept developed within the HyStEPs project will be discussed in detail.

2.1 Sensible Energy Storages

Sensible heat thermal energy storages are the most common, sophisticated and cost-efficient forms of TESs. By storing or releasing energy, the temperature of the heat storage medium increases or decreases proportionally, respectively [11]. The amount of stored heat Q depends on the specific heat capacity at constant pressure c_p , the mass m and the temperature difference between T_1 and T_2 of the storage medium and can be calculated with Equation (2.1) [11].

$$Q = \int_{T_1}^{T_2} m c_p dT \quad (2.1)$$

Often, water is used as the storage medium, because of its high availability, relatively high heat capacity and inexpensiveness, but also air, oil, rock beds, bricks or sand and other liquid or solid materials are suitable for sensible energy storages. Besides the specific heat capacity of a fluid, other properties like the density, operational temperatures, thermal conductivity or the costs have to be considered when choosing a suitable material for the desired storage application [12, 13]. Usually, the components of a sensible TES are a storage medium, a container tank, a thermal insulation and inlet-outlet devices [14]. Sensible heat storage systems can either be realised as single medium systems, where the heat transfer fluid (HTF) is also the storage medium, or as dual medium systems, where the HTF exchanges heat with the storage fluid through direct or indirect contact. Single medium systems have the advantages that temperature losses through internal heat exchange are avoided and less tank volume is required if the fluid has low thermal conductivity (e.g.

water) and thus the hot and cold media can be stored in a single tank. Dual medium systems are often less expensive, because of a cheaper solid storage medium, that is charged or discharged through the contact with the transfer medium [15].

2.1.1 Ruths Steam Storages

One particular type of a single medium, sensible TES system is the sliding pressure steam accumulator, also known as Ruths steam storage (RSS), named after its inventor Dr. Ruths [16]. RSSs can balance fluctuations in steam consumptions by storing excess steam when it arises and providing additional steam, if more than the average amount is needed [17]. They are commonly utilized for thermal storage in the process industry, with steam temperature ranging between 100 and 200°C [18] or, since more recently, as buffer storages for solarthermal power plants [19]. In RSS systems, the storage medium is pressurized saturated liquid water, to which surplus steam is added through a distribution pipe with nozzles during charging, and removed during discharging [18]. The horizontal, cylindrical pressure vessel is filled with a certain amount of liquid water and saturated steam (around 50-90% and 10-50%, respectively). Vertical designs of RSSs are uncommon because of their poor water circulation, although they are sometimes applied in power plants due to limited space [16]. Figure 2.2 shows the schematic structure of a RSS in a cross-sectional view.

The accumulating water volume inside the vessel is largely preserved, while energy is stored through the increased pressure and temperature of the liquid water initiated by the added condensing steam. During discharging, saturated steam is removed by means of reducing the pressure of the saturated liquid water and maintaining thermodynamic equilibrium through flash evaporation, whereby the mass of the liquid volume consequently decreases typically in the range of 10-20% [18]. The higher the pressure difference between maximum and minimum pressure inside the storage, the more flash steam will be produced [20]. The maximum pressure inside the storage vessel when the storage is fully charged depends on the maximum pressure of the charging steam mass flow, and the minimum pressure, i.e.

Figure 2.2: Schematic structure of a Ruths steam storage [17]

the lowest pressure at the end of the discharging process, when no further steam can be removed from the storage vessel, is determined by the process requirements [17].

Due to the high specific heat capacity of liquid water and possibly high charging and discharging rates as well as fast reaction times, RSSs are an attractive storage type. Nevertheless, storage capacity is limited by the storage volume and storage vessel costs become unaffordable for systems operating over 200°C , because the required wall thickness of the storage vessel and hence the steel mass per kg steam increases with higher pressures [18, 20, 21].

2.2 Latent Heat Energy Storages

In addition to sensible heat, latent heat thermal energy storages (LHTESs) use the process of phase conversion to store energy. Thereby, the energy needed for the phase change is dispensed as heat, while the temperature of the storage medium remains constant and high energy densities are achieved [11]. Materials used in LHTESs are referred to as phase change materials (PCMs). Theoretically, all phase changes are suitable for storing latent heat, but the transition from solid to liquid and vice versa is proven to be economically

and technically the most attractive for latent heat storage, because of the small volumetric changes of approximately 10% [22, 23]. Even though solid to solid changes show small changes in volume, too, and are of interest for some LHTES systems, the storage capacity is significantly smaller compared to solid-liquid transitions. While the latent heat of phase change is high during the transition from solid to gas or liquid to gas, large volume changes occur, which are too complex to handle and impractical regarding containment [23]. In this thesis, only the solid-liquid phase change will be regarded.

Figure 2.3 illustrates the fundamental difference between sensible and latent heat thermal energy storages. The same difference in temperature, assuming equal storage medium masses and that a phase change takes place in the regarded temperature range, causes a bigger quantity of stored energy in latent heat storages compared to sensible storages [24]. In addition to the sensible energy stored through a temperature difference between T_1 and T_2 , a LHTES stores the energy needed for the phase transition of the storage medium.

Figure 2.3: Heat stored inside a sensible and a latent TES over the temperature of the storage medium, after [24, 25]

The storage capacity Q of a LHTES between two temperatures T_1 and T_2 consists of three terms because of different values for the specific heat capacity c_p in the solid and in the liquid phase and is described in Equation (2.2). Hereby, T_m represents the melting temperature, m the mass and Δh the phase change enthalpy of the medium and a_m the mass fraction of molten PCM [11, 23].

$$Q = \int_{T_1}^{T_m} m c_{p,solid} dT + a_m m \Delta h + \int_{T_m}^{T_2} m c_{p,liquid} dT \quad (2.2)$$

It should be noted that, apart from isothermal phase change (i.e. melting/ solidification occurs at a constant melting temperature), commercial PCMs often show ranges during melting [26]. In the process of the so called mushy phase change, the transition from one phase to another is taking place over a finite temperature interval [27].

Every LHTES system consists of three components, namely a heat storage material that undergoes a phase change in the desired temperature range, a storage vessel that holds the storage substance and a heat exchange surface that passes thermal energy from the heat source or sink to the storage material [15]. Heat transfer concepts for latent heat storage are divided into active and passive concepts. When the PCM is solely moved through free convection and is in no direct contact with the heat transfer fluid, heat transfer happens through a defined surface area and one speaks of a passive transfer system. On the contrary, in active concepts, the phase change material is actively kept moving through an agitator, and is in either indirect or direct contact with the heat transfer material [11].

2.2.1 Phase Change Materials

Choosing the appropriate PCM for the attempted LHTES concept should be based on the material's thermodynamic, chemical and economic properties, as listed in Table 2.1. Especially the melting temperature and enthalpy, as well as availability and cost are the pivotal criteria when deciding on a material [28]. Generally, PCMs are categorized into organic and inorganic composites, as well as eutectics of organic and inorganic components. Inorganic

PCMs, e.g. water or salt hydrates, have almost twice the volumetric storage capacity and higher melting temperatures than organic ones like paraffins or sugar alcohols [22]. The most popular PCMs to implement in latent heat storage are water, salt hydrates and paraffins [11].

Table 2.1: Criteria for choosing a PCM, after [15, 22–25, 28, 29]

Thermophysical properties	Chemical properties	Economic properties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Phase change temperature • Specific latent heat • Thermal conductivity • Heat capacity • Density • Volume change • Vapor pressure • Phase separation • Supercooling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Corrosion • Chemical stability • Toxicity • Fire hazard • Environmental pollution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs • Availability • Recycling

Normally, not all of the listed criteria are met by a material [25]. In the following, solution approaches for frequent problems with PCMs are sketched [22, 25, 30].

Supercooling / subcooling

Contrary to an ideal PCM, which solidifies and liquefies at the same temperature, in reality, supercooling is necessary for many inorganic PCMs to release latent heat, which means that a temperature well below the phase change temperature has to be reached in order to start the solidification process. In order to reduce subcooling, a suitable nucleator has to be added to the PCM.

Phase separation

A PCM consisting of several components (e.g. salt hydrates or eutectics) may form two or more phases during melting because of differences in densities. This leads to bad reproducibility of the phase change (i.e. undergoing solidification and liquification as many times as desired, also called cycling stability), but can be prevented by adding gelling and

thickening additives that form a fine net with small compartments for the components in the PCM to decrease phase separation.

Compatibility with other materials

Corrosion of metals and stability loss of plastics in contact with inorganic and organic PCMs, respectively, are very common problems when it comes to the containment of the materials. It is therefore crucial to perform compatibility tests and select suitable material combinations.

Low thermal conductivity

Nonmetallic fluids generally have low thermal conductivities, that of inorganic PCMs is ranging under $17 \text{ W}/(\text{m K})$, that of organic ones under $0.4 \text{ W}/(\text{m K})$. In order to accelerate charging and discharging processes despite bad conductivities, several measurements can be taken. Installing fins or ribs directly into the storage increases the heat exchange area which again increases heat transfer. Encapsulation also enlarges the heat transfer surface and improves compatibility with other materials as well as cycling stability. Another option is the use of composite materials, which consist of a PCM and a second material that has a higher heat conductivity, for example graphite.

2.3 HyStEPs - Hybrid Storage for Efficient Processes

The novel hybrid thermal storage approach, designed within the HyStEPs project to which this thesis makes a contribution, is now aiming to combine the quick reaction time of a Ruths steam storage and the possibility of long-term storage with a latent heat thermal energy storage. Although numerous concepts of hybrid sensible and latent TES systems can be found in the literature (e.g. [31–33]), even including approaches to extend existing RSSs with PCM (e.g. [34, 35]), the one investigated in the HyStEPs project stands out by the unique method of encasing the storage vessel with PCM, instead of placing encapsulated PCM inside it, in order to increase the storage capacity while maintaining the fast reaction

time of the RSS. This makes it possible to retrofit a RSS to a hybrid storage component which can be advantageous and cost-effective [36].

Figure 2.4 shows the schematic composition of the concept with a common Ruths steam accumulator surrounded by modules filled with PCM. During discharging, the top part of a horizontal steam storage vessel contains dry steam, which has a very poor heat transfer coefficient. Therefore, the modules of the hybrid storage are not forming a full 180° half-circle, but only surround the accumulator to approximately 80%. These modules are filled with the solid PCM to only up to 120° so that it can expand upwards when melting.

Figure 2.4: Basic concept of the hybrid storage. Cross section of a RSS encased with PCM modules.

As demonstrated in Figure 2.5, for the final construction and prototype of the HyStEPs storage, the PCM modules are divided into eight pieces, four on each side of the vessel. Due to the low thermal conductivity of PCMs (see Section 2.2.1) an inner heat conducting structure out of s-shaped aluminium fins is placed inside the modules and thus forms the smallest entity of the storage which is called a PCM cell.

Figure 2.5: Components of the hybrid storage concept, after [9]

Within the course of the project, several approaches to maximize the storage efficiency were being investigated. The integration of an additional heat source like electrical heating elements or heat exchangers inside the PCM containers is discussed in [7, 37, 38]. This would allow the user to store electrical energy without having to previously generate steam for the RSS [38]. Further, in [37] and [38], the concept of partitioning the PCM modules into smaller chambers and filling them with different PCMs in order to increase the adaptability to the process requirements is presented.

For the prototype, the use of a single PCM and no additional heat sources was set. More precisely, the PCM modules are filled with an eutectic salt of lithium nitrate and sodium nitrate ($\text{LiNO}_3 - \text{NaNO}_3$). Other salt mixtures like $\text{KNO}_3 - \text{KOH}$, $\text{KNO}_3 - \text{NaNO}_3$ and $\text{LiNO}_3 - \text{NaCl}$ were taken into account as well, but ultimately, $\text{LiNO}_3 - \text{NaNO}_3$ was chosen because of its melting temperature (about 192°C) aligning with the feasible temperature range, between 180°C and 230°C , at voestalpine Stahl Donawitz GmbH, where the functional model of the HyStEPs storage will be tested within the existing steam storage infrastructure. Even though it is more expensive than the other considered PCMs, it convinces through overall better properties, especially with its lower melting temperature, compared to the other materials, enabling the possibility to operate the steam storage with lower pressures.

2.4 Design of Experiment

In general, an experiment is performed in order to analyze a process's or a system's performance [39] and the statistical design of experiment (DoE) represents a method to efficiently plan and execute it [40]. The goal of implementing a DoE is to obtain the desired information within a limited number of experimental runs [41]. In general, it involves the systematic allocation of the experimental conditions, the conduct of the experiment and the statistical analysis of the results, whereby numerous mathematical and statistical theories to implement a DoE exist [42]. As stated in Section 1.2, this thesis will cover the first part, more precisely the detailed computation of an optimal experimental design (OED).

To begin with, the terms *design of experiment* and *optimal experimental design* have to be distinguished. While both methods have the objective of facilitating experiments and making them more effective, the DoE is a more general approach on how to conduct an experiment while OED distinctively seeks to design the best possible experiments based on a given model [43]. The accuracy and the information content by which the results will be acquired are maximized [44, 45]. In order to predict the behaviour of a system to be experimentally investigated, a mathematical model that describes its input and output as well as known and unknown parameter variables, is built. For clarity, we will regard a model described by the state-space formulation of a deterministic ordinary differential equation (ODE) (Equations 2.3 and 2.4, [43]), even though other model types can be covered by OED as well - as done in the work for this thesis.

$$\frac{d\mathbf{x}}{dt} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\theta}, t) \quad (2.3)$$

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\theta}, t) \quad (2.4)$$

Hereby \mathbf{x} is the vector of n_x state variables, \mathbf{u} the vector of inputs, $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ the vector of n_θ model parameters and \mathbf{y} the vector of n_y measured states [43, 45].

2.4.1 Parameter Estimation

The aim of the OED is now to ex ante define the operating conditions and inputs in a way that the values of unknown (or uncertain) parameters can be estimated with the greatest statistical confidence from ex post measured data [44]. Any prior knowledge of the uncertain parameters is of advantage to the optimal DoE. To this end, parameter estimation (i.e. model calibration), where the regarded parameters which cannot be measured directly are getting adjusted in a way that the experimental results are fitted best with the given model structure, is used [43]. To do so, a cost function that measures the goodness of the fit is minimized. The most popular cost functions to approximate parameters are the Bayesian, the maximum likelihood and the least squares estimator [43, 44].

The model building cycle in Figure 2.6, a concept that derives from system identification model theories (e.g. [46]), vividly describes the co-dependence of the model, its analysis and the conduct of experiments. Parameter estimation and an optimal experimental design influence each other, since the validation of the model is becoming more accurate with more experimental data. In this thesis, an OED was attained by formulating a dynamic optimization problem and afterwards validated through parameter identification with estimated experimental data. Accordingly, the generated results are to be confirmed by future experiments.

2.4.2 Optimal Experimental Design

After a preliminary calibration of the model, the optimal experimental design can be formulated as a dynamic optimization problem with the aim of finding a set of input variables \mathbf{u} that optimize the statistical quality of parameter estimation [45]. Thereby, a widespread, mathematically convenient and effective approach to measure the goodness of the experiment is the use of the Fisher Information Matrix (FIM, [47]) [44]. This matrix can be interpreted as a quantification of the total sensitivity of the measured output to all parameters. Its detailed calculation is, for example, described by L. Ljung in [46].

Figure 2.6: Model building loop, after [43]

With a local sensitivity analysis, the influence of small perturbations in a parameter on the output is evaluated. Building on a model's state-space form (Equation 2.4), the first order derivative of an output y with respect to a regarded input parameter θ_i can be, among other approaches, obtained numerically by model simulations with a small perturbation of the input parameter $\Delta\theta_i$ around their nominal value $\theta_{i,0}$ using a forward perturbation [48]:

$$\left. \frac{dy(t; \theta_i)}{d\theta_i} \right|_{\theta_{i,0}} = \frac{y(t; \theta_{i,0} + \Delta\theta_i) - y(t; \theta_{i,0})}{\Delta\theta_i} \quad (2.5)$$

Once the local sensitivity functions are calculated, parameter significance can be directly assessed, whereby large absolute values of the derivative indicate that a parameter is highly influential on the output, while values close to zero suggests little to no effect of the parameter [48]. For a more precise assessment, the $(n_t \times n_\theta)$ sensitivity matrix ψ is formed by evaluating the derivative from Equation 2.5 for each of the n_θ uncertain parameters θ

at each of the n_t points in time t [49]:

$$\boldsymbol{\psi} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{dy(1; \theta_{1,0})}{d\theta_1} & \frac{dy(1; \theta_{2,0})}{d\theta_2} & \dots & \frac{dy(1; \theta_{n_\theta,0})}{d\theta_{n_\theta}} \\ \frac{dy(2; \theta_{1,0})}{d\theta_1} & \frac{dy(2; \theta_{2,0})}{d\theta_2} & \dots & \frac{dy(2; \theta_{n_\theta,0})}{d\theta_{n_\theta}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{dy(n_t; \theta_{1,0})}{d\theta_1} & \frac{dy(n_t; \theta_{2,0})}{d\theta_2} & \dots & \frac{dy(n_t; \theta_{n_\theta,0})}{d\theta_{n_\theta}} \end{bmatrix} . \quad (2.6)$$

Divided by the standard deviation of measurement, σ_{noise}^2 , this sensitivity matrix provides the basis to formulate the $(n_\theta \times n_\theta)$ FIM $\boldsymbol{\mathcal{I}}$ (note that in the literature it is often also denoted with $\boldsymbol{\mathcal{M}}$) [50]:

$$\boldsymbol{\mathcal{I}} = \sigma_{noise}^{-2} [\boldsymbol{\psi}^T \boldsymbol{\psi}] . \quad (2.7)$$

For simplification of the computation, the standard deviation is considered as a factor of one and the FIM is approximated through Equation 2.8. This is legitimated through the aim of this thesis being of qualitative nature. The experiment will be designed with the intention of maximizing parameter influence without claiming a statistical interpretation or statistical accuracy. Additionally, in the performed OED, weighting of input variables and parameters, as well as quite good a priori estimations or knowledge about the parameters to be examined, supports the accuracy of the results.

$$\boldsymbol{\mathcal{I}} \approx \boldsymbol{\psi}^T \boldsymbol{\psi} \quad (2.8)$$

The FIM thus holds information on the expected accuracy of the degree of parameter correlation [51]. Its eigenvalues λ provide insight to the influence of the regarded parameters on the model output in the same way as the sensitivity functions: large eigenvalues indicate high influence while small eigenvalues mean that a perturbation of the selected parameters has little effect. With the help of the FIM, an input trajectory for the model can be optimized in order to maximize the parameters' influence on the output. Therefore, scalar functions of the FIM are formulated as optimal design criteria for the dynamic optimization problem [51]. In the literature, these are known as various optimal design criteria for OED, the most popular ones being the D-, E- and A-optimality criteria [52–55]. Rodriguez-

Fernandez, et al. [45] additionally define two modifications of the criteria that are of interest to this work:

- A-optimality criterion = $\min \text{trace}(\mathcal{I}^{-1})$
- Modified A-optimality criterion = $\max \text{trace}(\mathcal{I})$
- D-optimality criterion = $\max \det(\mathcal{I})$
- E-optimality criterion = $\max \lambda_{\min}(\mathcal{I})$
- Modified E-optimality criterion = $\min \frac{\lambda_{\max}(\mathcal{I})}{\lambda_{\min}(\mathcal{I})}$

With the optimization of these criteria by shaping the system input trajectory accordingly, an input for the regarded model can be found so that parameter sensitivity is maximized.

Chapter 3

Preparing the Design of Experiment

The main objective of this thesis was the preparation for the experimental validation of existing models for the HyStEPs hybrid thermal energy storage. At the test infrastructure of the project partner voestalpine Stahl Donawitz GmbH, where the HyStEPs prototype will be integrated, three RSSs are operating and storing arising process steam from steel production. An effortless approach to obtain experimental data would be to charge and discharge the storage with trivial loading conditions of the pressure of the arising steam and to conclude the storage behaviour only retrospectively. Aiming to prepare efficient experimental investigations and to bring more transparency into the black box model of the hybrid storage, it was decided to plan a detailed design of experiment in this thesis. An optimal experimental design ensures faster and more accurate determination of a models' characteristics and therefore accelerates and facilitates the experiment (see Section 2.4). In order to successfully execute this aim, the following objectives were established:

1. Defining and estimating uncertain parameters.
2. Modelling the dynamic optimization problem for the OED.
3. Executing and analysing the optimizations.
4. Validating the results through parameter identification.

More precisely, the following research questions were concluded to be answered within the DoE: *Which parameters are uncertain and are of interest to be investigated? How do they influence the model's output? Which input trajectory is optimal to gain most information on the parameters from experimental data? Are they significantly superior to trivial inputs?*

In the next sections, the first two objectives are treated by describing the theoretical preparations for the optimal DoE. First, uncertain parameters are identified and selected for the OED. Subsequently, the underlying models for simulating the HyStEPs storage and the structure of the optimization program are presented. The results of the OED and their assessment are discussed in the following Chapter 4.

3.1 Parameter Selection

Before the parameter sensitivity to the model's output can be determined, we first have to define which parameters are already certain, which have to be estimated and finally which ones will be subject to the optimal experimental design. Thereby, we also have to regard identifiability, e.g. whether or not the experimental measurements will permit us to estimate the parameters' values [56]. The experimental investigations of the HyStEPs storage will be divided into tests on the pure steam storage and tests with the whole hybrid storage. Therefore, two optimal experimental design strategies with different parameter estimation approaches were developed. In Table 3.1 relevant parameters for the entire hybrid storage are listed. A scale from 0 to 3 for evaluating the level of uncertainty (LoU) was established by comparing the thermo-physical parameter values of the respective materials with minimum and maximum values from the literature. For the geometric parameters of the prototype the uncertainty level is "0", because the values are fixed. If the variance between the values used for the simulation models and the literature values is smaller than 10%, the LoU is designated as "1", if it is bigger, the LoU is "2". Parameter values that are unknown, or if no reference values could be found in the literature, an uncertainty level of "3" is allocated. The properties of the selected PCM $\text{LiNO}_3 - \text{NaNO}_3$ are not well

known or documented, so that the uncertainties for the PCM material properties are to be rated higher in general. In addition to the evaluation of the uncertainty of the parameter values, a weighting of the probable influence of a variation in the parameter values on the relevant output values was applied. The LoU of parameters, whose variance is most likely to reproduce significant variations in the model's output values, is annotated with a "+" in order to indicate the importance of their identification through the OED. Parameters without significant influence on the model's performance, even if their uncertainty is high, are weighted with a "-". The following selection of the parameters to be investigated in the course of the OED is based on these two criteria: the uncertainty of a parameter and its influence of the model's output. Other parameters relevant for the hybrid model that are not listed in Table 3.1, like material properties of other materials or geometric parameters for the PCM modules, are not considered for the DoE.

3.1.1 Ruths Steam Storage

Concerning the experiments on the pure RSS, its storage capacity and energy losses are of highest interest. The thermal energy storage capacity depends on the amount of steam mass which can be derived from the water filling volume of the storage [59] (for detailed calculations of steam accumulators see, for example, [4, 59, 60]) and it is hence crucial to be able to recalculate the water volume from the experimental data. For the ODE, the volume of the storage tank was therefore selected as a volumetric parameter V . The actual pressure vessel is a cylinder with hemispherical sides, but for simplification the volume can be assumed as that of a cylinder with plane side faces [36], calculated with Equation 3.1 out of the geometric parameters of the RSS.

$$V = \frac{l \cdot d^2 \cdot \pi}{4} \quad (3.1)$$

The values of the heat transfer coefficients for the individual physical states show large deviations within the literature, because they are strongly dependent on the general system conditions. A distinctive inference on the parameter values will not be possible through the experimental investigations. Accordingly, an overall heat transfer coefficient h was

Table 3.1: Relevant parameters for the hybrid storage model parameter estimation. Unless otherwise specified, the parameter values are taken from the HyStEPs prototype data sheet.

Parameter	Sym- bol	Unit	Value with [min;max] range	LoU
Geometric parameters of the storage vessel				
Length	l	m	2.25 [-]	0+
Inner diameter	d	m	0.711 [-]	0+
Wall thickness	s	m	0.0125 [-]	0+
Thickness isolation	s_{iso}	m	0.2 [-]	0+
Thickness outer plate	s_o	m	0.003 [-]	0+
Heat transfer parameters^{1,2}				
Heat transfer coefficient condensing steam	h_{cs}	W/(m ² K)	5000 [5600;17000]	2+
Heat transfer coefficient dry steam	h_{ds}	W/(m ² K)	10 [17;280]	2+
Heat transfer coefficient stationary air	h_a	W/(m ² K)	5 [5;37]	2+
Heat transfer coefficient liquid water	h_{lw}	W/(m ² K)	700 [100;1200]	2+
Heat transfer coefficient boiling water	h_{bw}	W/(m ² K)	1000 [800;2000]	2+
Heat conductivity insulation	k_{iso}	W/(m K)	0.062 [0.04]	2+
Heat conductivity steel	k_{st}	W/(m K)	48 [20;54]	2+
Material properties of PCM				
Density	ρ	kg/m ³	2317 [-]	3-
Melting temperature ³	T_m	°C	192 [194]	1+
Area of melting	dT_m	°C	±0.4 [-]	3-
Heat capacity solid PCM	c_s	J/(kg K)	1350 [-]	3-
Heat capacity liquid PCM	c_l	J/(kg K)	1720 [-]	3-
Latent heat ⁴	Δh	kJ/kg	309.1 [262;±9.3]	1-
Heat conductivity solid PCM	k_s	W/(m K)	0.87 [-]	3-
Heat conductivity liquid PCM ^{4,5}	k_l	W/(m K)	0.575 [0.54;0.59]	1-
Thermal expansion ⁶	β	1/K	3.5×10^{-4} [-]	3-
Dynamic viscosity ⁶	μ	N s/m ²	5.8×10^{-3} [-]	3-
Other parameters				
Inlet mass flow geometric coefficient ⁷	$c_{m,in}$	1	5×10^{-5} [-]	3+

¹ parameter values taken from [9]² maximum and minimum values taken from https://www.engineersedge.com/thermodynamics/overall_heat_transfer-table.htm (heat transfer coefficients), and https://www.engineeringtoolbox.com/thermal-conductivity-d_429.html (heat conductivities), last accessed March 13, 2021³ maximum value taken from [57]⁴ minimum value taken from [57]⁵ maximum value taken from [35]⁶ no values available in the literature for LiNO₃ – NaNO₃, value taken from [58] for KNO₃ – NaNO₃⁷ estimated value validated through comparison with the simulation results from [37]

calculated with Equation 3.2 by summarizing the heat losses through the storage wall [7].

$$h = \pi \left[\frac{1}{h_{cs} d} + \frac{1}{2 k_{st}} \log \left(\frac{d + 2 s}{d} \right) + \frac{1}{2 k_{iso}} \log \left(\frac{d + 2 s + 2 s_{iso}}{d + 2 s} \right) + \frac{1}{2 k_{st}} \log \left(\frac{d + 2 s + 2 s_{iso} + 2 s_o}{d + 2 s + 2 s_{iso}} \right) + \frac{1}{h_a (d + 2 s + 2 s_{iso} + 2 s_o)} \right]^{-1} \quad (3.2)$$

At the testing infrastructure, only inlet steam pressure can be regulated, therefore the inlet steam mass flow can only be approximated through the roughly proportional relation of mass flow and pressure difference Δp between the pressure of the charging steam and the pressure inside the storage vessel. The same goes for the outlet mass flow, whereby Δp is defined as the pressure difference between the pressure inside the storage vessel and the discharging steam pressure.

$$\dot{m} = c_m \sqrt{\Delta p} \quad (3.3)$$

The constant c_m is dependent on geometric conditions of the inlet and outlet nozzle and yet to be validated through experimental data. For the sake of simplicity, the same constant $c_{m,in}$ is presumed for the injected and extracted steam mass flow. In order to be able to make a statement on the mass flow as well as to properly define the coefficient in the first place, the third parameter regarded in the pure steam accumulator experiments is the inlet mass flow nozzle parameter $c_{m,in}$.

3.1.2 Hybrid Storage

Research on LHTES systems is still at an earlier stage of development, especially the material properties and the melting behaviour of certain PCMs are to some extent unknown [11], which is the case with the PCM used for the HyStEPs storage prototype ($\text{LiNO}_3 - \text{NaNO}_3$). Accordingly, the melting temperature T_m and the solid and liquid heat conductivities of the PCM k_s and k_l , respectively, were taken into account as parameters that could be observed within the OED. Internal preliminary experiments yielded varying results for the latent heat Δh of the PCM, therefore, a parameter estimation with the OED should be pursued. Additionally, a cumulated heat transfer parameter, similar to the heat losses parameter

from the RSS model, describing the incoming heat transition coefficient through the steam storage vessel wall, was chosen as a parameter for the OED. Considering only one PCM cell, it is valid to assume this incoming heat transfer parameter α_{in} as a fixed value, when in fact it is dependent on the state of the fluid (liquid or boiling water, (condensing) steam) in the vessel to which the studied cell is located next to.

In addition to these five parameters, it would be of interest to consider the thermal expansion β and the dynamic viscosity μ of the PCM in the course of a separate OED, since their values are to this date not documented in the scientific literature. They are relevant to the temperature distribution inside the PCM cell during liquification, when natural convection is not negligible, which is the case for cells with upward orientation, i.e. cells that are attached to the upper part of the storage vessel (compare Figure 2.4). Convection can be neglected within downward facing cells as well as during solidification of the PCM [8]. The regarded test cell for the experimental design is orientated horizontally, and even though natural convection is still a significant factor for charging the cell, it is not considered during the optimization of the DoE with regards to the above listed parameters, but only when it is carried out with regards to the "convection parameters" β and μ .

In this thesis, only the heat conductivity of the solid PCM k_s and the heat transfer parameter α_{in} were chosen for examination during the DoE, due to the large computation times of the OED for the PCM. With regard to the forthcoming range of the experiments, a DOE for all the parameters discussed above should be considered.

3.2 Models for the Optimal Experimental Design

Before an optimal DoE can be modelled, the MATLAB codes for simulating the hybrid storage and its separate components have to be grasped. In the following, a quick overview of the numeric implementations of the RSS, the PCM cell and the entire hybrid storage is given.

3.2.1 RSS Model

For the dynamic RSS model by Dusek and Hofmann [7], on which the DoE for the steam storage is based, the so called equilibrium approach (see e.g. [4]), whereby thermodynamic equilibrium between the two phases inside the pressure vessel (i.e. the water and steam phases are considered to have the same temperatures and pressures) at all times is assumed, was used, which yields in one energy and one mass balance equation (Equations 3.4 and 3.5, respectively), treating the two-phase-fluid as one fluidic mixture [9, 17]. Hereby, the variable m denotes the mass of the fluid, \dot{m}_{in} and \dot{m}_{out} the inlet and outlet mass flow, respectively, h_{RSS} , h_{in} and h_{out} the specific enthalpy of the water-steam mixture, the inlet and the outlet mass flow, respectively, \dot{Q} the total heat flow through the vessel wall, V the volume inside the RSS and p_{RSS} and ρ_{RSS} the pressure and the density of the equivalent fluidic mixture, respectively.

$$m \frac{dh_{RSS}}{dt} = \dot{m}_{in} (\Delta h_{in} - \Delta h_{RSS}) + \dot{m}_{out} (\Delta h_{out} - \Delta h_{RSS}) + \dot{Q} + V \frac{dp_{RSS}}{dt} \quad (3.4)$$

$$V \frac{d\rho_{RSS}}{dt} = \dot{m}_{in} + \dot{m}_{out} \quad (3.5)$$

For this thesis, these equilibrium equations were adapted with respect to the limitation of not being able to control the mass flow directly at the storage test site. With the approximation for the injected and extracted mass flows \dot{m}_{in} and \dot{m}_{out} , respectively, from

Equation 3.3, Equations 3.4 and 3.5 therefore result in:

$$m \frac{dh_{RSS}}{dt} = c_{m,in} \sqrt{p_{in} - p_{RSS}} (\Delta h_{in} - \Delta h_{RSS}) + c_{m,out} \sqrt{p_{RSS} - p_{out}} (\Delta h_{out} - \Delta h_{RSS}) + \dot{Q} + V \frac{dp_{RSS}}{dt} \quad (3.6)$$

$$V \frac{dp_{RSS}}{dt} = c_{m,in} \sqrt{p_{in} - p_{RSS}} + c_{m,out} \sqrt{p_{RSS} - p_{out}} \quad (3.7)$$

According to Pernsteiner et al. [9], the following simplifying assumptions were made:

- Potential and kinetic energies are negligible.
- The properties of the outgoing fluid (extracted steam) are those of the pure vapour phase.
- Heat conduction in the circumferential direction of the RSS steel shell is neglected.

Thereupon, the differential equations were characterized in an implicit descriptor state-space form (Equation 3.8) and can be solved in MATLAB [6] via the `ode15i` solver [9].

$$\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{x}) \dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}) \quad (3.8)$$

Here, \mathbf{M} is a mass matrix, \mathbf{x} the state vector and \mathbf{u} the input vector. The detailed description of the RSS model can be found in [7, 9, 37], but for the DoE it is sufficient to comprehend how the model output is influenced by the input vector and how to modify initial values and parameters (see Section 3.3).

3.2.2 PCM Cell Model

For the observation and later the optimization of the experimental design of a sole PCM cell, the numerical model developed by Kasper [8], where the thermodynamic behaviour of a phase change material during melting and solidification in a two-dimensional, rectangular domain is considered, is used. In this model, heat transfer through conduction as well as through natural convection can be studied, though for the development of the experimental design, apart from the calculations with the goal to optimize the sensitivity of the experi-

ment with regards to the convection parameters β and μ (Table 3.1), the effect of natural convection was neglected. The apparent heat capacity method (see e.g. [61]), supposing a mushy phase change, was used to model the phase change [9]. Because it would be beyond the scope of this thesis, the author refers to [8] for an in-depth documentation and explanation of the model's governing equations and their implementation. For the purpose of the experimental design it is only essential to be able to handle the PCM cell code, whose main function is run by passing an input datafile in which geometry specifications, initial and boundary conditions, material properties and other input parameters are defined [8].

3.2.3 Co-Simulation Model

The coupling of the RSS and the PCM cells was modeled by Pernsteiner et al. [9] via the heat flow from the steam storage vessel to the attached PCM modules. The total heat flow from Equations 3.4 and 3.6 from the RSS model, \dot{Q} , is therefore divided into heat losses to the environment and the heat flow to the PCM cells:

$$\dot{Q} = \dot{Q}_{RSS_losses} + \dot{Q}_{RSS2PCM} \quad . \quad (3.9)$$

With the assumption that the state variables inside the RSS do not change significantly within a minor time step, two different time steps for the RSS and the PCM cell sub-models were chosen. This makes it possible to save computation time by parallel computing the connecting heat flows to the desired number of individually considered PCM cells at a minor time step, while the RSS is computed separately on a major time step [9]. Again, the author refers to [9] for a detailed description of the modeling of the co-simulation. Since the sub-models are defined individually in the respective manner, no further comprehension of the coupling mechanisms of the co-simulation model is necessary.

3.3 Structure of the Optimization Model

In order to find the optimal input trajectory for charging and discharging the storage, two separate optimal design strategies were developed. The RSS model was used for finding the optimal pressure of the inlet steam flow in order to maximize the influence of the volumetric, heat transfer and inlet mass flow parameters. In contrast, with the PCM cell model the optimal input temperature, i.e. the temperature inside the attached RSS, in order to increase sensitivity to the considered parameters, was sought to be found. The co-simulation model was finally utilized to transfer the results from the latter into the form of the input trajectory for the RSS, the inlet steam flow pressure, with that being the only variable to set during the experimental investigation.

Although the two models are built fundamentally different, the methodology for the optimal experimental design is the same for both cases. The flowchart for the execution procedure of the OED in MATLAB [6], including the here called *main simulation* (either the RSS or the PCM cell code), is presented in Figure 3.1. This allows the application of the OED code to any model. The optimization of the objective function, i.e. the maximization of the pre set optimality criterion (see Section 2.4.2), was conducted via two nonlinear programming solvers, `fmincon` and `ga`, over the course of the DoE. The solver `fmincon` finds the local minimum of a constrained nonlinear multivariable function with a gradient based approach¹ while `ga` uses a genetic algorithm to find the minimum², which relies on natural selection, mutation and other biologically inspired mechanisms [62]. As optimal design criteria, the modified A-optimality criterion, the D-optimality criterion and the E-optimality criterion from [45], from now on called *trace*, *det* and *mineig*, respectively, as described in Section 2.4.2, were used. Since the optimization solvers aim to minimize the objective value, the optimality criteria are turned negative for the optimization.

The program is started with the designated run-file, in which preprocessing for the optimizer is carried out. Initial and boundary conditions for the computation of the main model are

¹<https://de.mathworks.com/help/optim/ug/fmincon.html>, last accessed March 13, 2021

²<https://de.mathworks.com/help/gads/ga.html>, last accessed March 13, 2021

Figure 3.1: Flowchart for executing the optimal experimental design model

either defined or loaded from an input-datafile as well as optimization options, boundary conditions and constraints for the objective function are set. In addition, if `fmincon` is utilized as the optimization solver, an initial point for the solution, in this case the input trajectory, which is either the pressure of the incoming mass flow (RSS model) or the input temperature from the vessel wall to the PCM cell (PCM cell model), has to be specified. Furthermore, one of the three optimality criteria *det*, *trace* or *mineig*, which will determine how the objective function value is being calculated, must be chosen. Additionally, the parameters that are of interest, i.e. with which the sensitivity matrix and therefore the FIM should be built, have to be initialized in the `eval_param`-file that executes the parametrization.

The respective solver then starts to minimize the objective function value and calls the objective evaluation-file. With a first guess for the input trajectory, the parametrization is called. From there, the main simulation is called again, the first time with the nominal values for the parameters, then as many times as the number of chosen parameters, every evaluation another parameter's value is perturbed. After all state vectors, one perturbed one for every parameter plus the nominal vector, are calculated, the sensitivity matrix can be constructed and passed back to the objective evaluation. The Fisher information matrix and with it the optimality criterion is being determined and a new input trajectory vector is being set. This process is reiterated until stopping criteria of the solver are met and the solution to the problem is found. The optimal input trajectory in order to plan an experiment that will show the highest sensitivity to a change in the regarded parameters is displayed and the OED is completed.

Chapter 4

Results and Discussion of the OED

Based on the presented code structure, the dynamic optimization problem for establishing an optimal experimental design, aiming to obtain the most information on the selected parameters, was performed. This chapter is organized by first documenting the results of the OED along with validations of the results by means of hypothetical measurements and an assessment of the different optimization strategies and design criteria. In the following, difficulties to look out for and further advices for the conduction of the experiments are discussed. In conclusion, a fully developed experimental matrix is identified with regards to the actual experimental set-up (experimental conditions, sensor locations, etc.), the typical storage behaviour and the established optimal DoE.

4.1 Results

The calculations of the optimal experimental plan were divided into optimizations of the input trajectory for the pure RSS and a single PCM cell. In general, the optimization problems were solved with the local solver `fmincon`¹ from the MATLAB Optimization Toolbox and the Global Optimization Toolbox's solver `ga`² [6]. The former finds a local minimum of

¹<https://de.mathworks.com/help/optim/ug/fmincon.html>, last accessed March 13, 2021

²<https://de.mathworks.com/help/gads/ga.html>, last accessed March 13, 2021

the objective function near a starting point, the latter searches randomly for global solutions by applying evolutionary principles and hence doesn't need to get passed a starting point. All MATLAB code listings necessary for the conduction of the optimization problems can be found in Appendix A.

In a first step, each sub-component of the hybrid storage was optimized with both solvers and all three optimality criteria that were established in Section 2.4. For the optimality criterion *det*, the negated determinant of the FIM is the objective value that gets minimized by the solver, the *trace* criterion determines the negated trace of the FIM as minimization objective and when utilising the *mineig* criterion, the negated minimum eigenvalue of the FIM gets minimized. Since the FIM consists of the sensitivity matrix which again depends on the model's output, a change in the input trajectory affects the optimality criterion value. The sensitivity functions of the respective parameters are calculated by Equation 2.5 for a relative perturbation of the parameter value ($\Delta\theta_i = 0.01 \cdot \theta_{i,0}$). In order to simplify the optimization problem, four distinct optimization variables are defined. Over the course of one hour, each of the input values is held constant for 15 minutes. To obtain the input vector for every n_t time step, needed to run the respective sub-model simulation, the vector containing the four distinct input values γ is multiplied by the $n_t \times 4$ step sequence matrix \mathbf{T} , that allocates the same into the input vector with the length n_t , $u_{in} = \mathbf{T} \cdot \gamma$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ \vdots \\ u_1 \\ u_2 \\ \vdots \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \\ \vdots \\ u_3 \\ u_4 \\ \vdots \\ u_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & 0 & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 1 & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & 1 & 0 & \vdots \\ \vdots & 0 & 1 & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & 1 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & 0 & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \\ u_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.1)$$

4.1.1 Ruths Steam Storage

With the goal of the OED to find an input trajectory for the steam storage that produces an output showing a significant increase in the sensitivity to the selected storage parameters, all optimized cases were compared to the results obtained when charged and discharged with a trivial choice of input trajectories. For the RSS model, the input trajectory u is not only defined as the inlet mass flow but as a combination of charging and discharging flows by designating the exterior pressure p_{ext} in bar with which the storage is filled or emptied. If the given pressure is higher than the pressure inside the storage vessel the RSS is being charged, if it is lower the RSS is being discharged.

Figure 4.1: Trivial load case: pressure of the inlet mass flow, pressure and temperature inside the RSS over time

As initial conditions inside the storage, a liquid water filling level of 60% and a pressure of 10 bar are assumed at all times. In the Listing A.1 in the Appendix A.1, all necessary input parameters for the simulation of the RSS model are listed, and the Cool-Prop library [63] is used to determine the specific enthalpy of the charging mass flow. The values hold for the prototype test storage. Figure 4.1 displays the inlet pressure and the simulated storage behaviour for the trivial load case, where the RSS is charged for 30 minutes with $p_{ext} = 20$ bar and then discharged for 30 minutes with $p_{ext} = 10$ bar ($\gamma_{triv} = [20, 20, 10, 10]^T$). As shown in Figure 4.1, the temperature and the pressure in the storage show the exact same behaviour over time. Henceforth, it was decided to regard the pressure as the only state variable for the optimization of the experimental design. For the optimization with

`fmincon`, γ_{triv} was chosen as the starting point. For both solvers, minimum (7 bar) and maximum pressure (23 bar) inside the storage serve as lower (lb) and upper bound (ub) on the optimization variable γ , respectively, so that the solution is always in the range $lb \leq \gamma \leq ub$. No other (in)equality constraints were set.

Optimization results

In Figure 4.2 the results of the optimization with the `fmincon` and the `ga` solvers are displayed. The storage behaviour as well as the sensitivity to the considered parameters α (heat transfer parameter), V (volumetric parameter) and $c_{m,in}$ (inlet mass flow geometric parameter) (see Section 3.1) when loaded with the trivial input trajectory are compared to the input trajectories and corresponding output and sensitivity trajectories, derived from optimizing the input vector γ after all three optimality criteria *det*, *trace* and *mineig*.

While the *trace*-optimized trajectory in Figure 4.2a is to charge the storage continuously with maximum pressure, the *det*- and *mineig*-optimized ones practically remain the shape of the starting input trajectory, but change in pressure at every 15 minute step and show a steeper leap in pressure between charging and discharging after 30 minutes. The according pressure distribution inside the RSS and the sensitivity functions for the regarded parameters are shown below the input plots. In this figure, the sensitivities towards the parameters show no remarkable deviations from the *trivial* input load case, except for the negative peak in the α -sensitivity for the *mineig*-optimized trajectory.

Similar observations can be made when looking at the optimization results for the `ga` solver (Figure 4.2b). Since `ga` does not need to get passed a starting point, it is plausible that the resulting trajectories show a more dynamic (dis-)charging behaviour than the *trivial* case. The *det*-optimized trajectory charges the storage for 30 minutes with maximum pressure and then discharges it with minimum pressure for another 30 minutes, the *trace*-optimized trajectory oscillates between maximum charging and minimum discharging pressure every 15 minutes, and the *mineig*-optimized trajectory also indicates to change between charging

and discharging every 15 minutes but with less extreme leaps. Regarding the parameter sensitivity functions, the *mineig* trajectory shows greatest sensitivity towards α , the *det* trajectory towards V and the *trace* trajectory towards $c_{m,in}$, which also applies to the `fmincon` optimized load cases. In order to understand how the different optimality criteria influence the shape of the input trajectory and thereby the parameter sensitivities, an analysis of the FIM and its eigenvalues is of interest.

In Table 4.1 the FIM \mathcal{I} along with its eigenvalues arranged in a vector \mathbf{e} for each of the seven (the *trivial* plus two times three optimized) cases is enlisted. In providing these matrices, the influence of the three parameters on the eigenvalues can directly be deduced. The vector of eigenvalues is arranged in the order that the first entry corresponds to the sensitivity of the first parameter, α , the second one to V and the third one to $c_{m,in}$.

Table 4.1: Fisher Information analysis for the trivial and optimized load cases for the RSS model

input case		FIM	eigenvalues
A	<i>trivial</i>	$\mathcal{I}_A = \begin{bmatrix} 1.46E+01 & -1.82E+02 & -2.36E+07 \\ -1.82E+02 & 5.75E+05 & -4.76E+09 \\ -2.36E+07 & -4.76E+09 & 8.51E+13 \end{bmatrix}$	$e_A = \begin{bmatrix} 7.50E-01 \\ 3.08E+05 \\ 8.51E+13 \end{bmatrix}$
optimized with fmincon			
B.1	<i>det - optimized</i>	$\mathcal{I}_{B.1} = \begin{bmatrix} 2.66E+01 & -1.59E+03 & -3.51E+07 \\ -1.59E+03 & 1.19E+06 & -6.67E+09 \\ -3.51E+07 & -6.67E+09 & 1.19E+14 \end{bmatrix}$	$e_{B.1} = \begin{bmatrix} 8.14E-01 \\ 8.19E+05 \\ 1.19E+14 \end{bmatrix}$
B.2	<i>trace-optimized</i>	$\mathcal{I}_{B.2} = \begin{bmatrix} 9.41E+00 & 1.98E+03 & -3.51E+07 \\ 1.98E+03 & 4.38E+05 & -7.83E+09 \\ -3.51E+07 & -7.83E+09 & 1.40E+14 \end{bmatrix}$	$e_{B.2} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.34E-01 \\ 1.37E+02 \\ 1.40E+14 \end{bmatrix}$
B.3	<i>mineig-optimized</i>	$\mathcal{I}_{B.3} = \begin{bmatrix} 2.56E+03 & -2.06E+04 & 1.29E+07 \\ -2.06E+04 & 6.26E+05 & -5.37E+09 \\ 1.29E+07 & -5.37E+09 & 9.01E+13 \end{bmatrix}$	$e_{B.3} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.27E+03 \\ 3.08E+05 \\ 9.01E+13 \end{bmatrix}$
optimized with ga			
C.1	<i>det-optimized</i>	$\mathcal{I}_{C.1} = \begin{bmatrix} 2.49E+01 & -2.10E+03 & -3.51E+07 \\ -2.10E+03 & 1.54E+06 & -7.58E+09 \\ -3.51E+07 & -7.58E+09 & 1.35E+14 \end{bmatrix}$	$e_{C.1} = \begin{bmatrix} 9.86E-01 \\ 1.11E+06 \\ 1.35E+14 \end{bmatrix}$
C.2	<i>trace-optimized</i>	$\mathcal{I}_{C.2} = \begin{bmatrix} 8.85E+01 & 1.19E+03 & -1.99E+08 \\ 1.19E+03 & 6.21E+05 & -7.85E+09 \\ -1.99E+08 & -7.85E+09 & 4.92E+14 \end{bmatrix}$	$e_{C.2} = \begin{bmatrix} 3.06E-01 \\ 4.96E+05 \\ 4.92E+14 \end{bmatrix}$
C.3	<i>mineig-optimized</i>	$\mathcal{I}_{C.3} = \begin{bmatrix} 2.63E+03 & -1.61E+04 & -1.16E+07 \\ 1.61E+04 & 5.68E+05 & -7.35E+09 \\ -1.16E+07 & -7.35E+09 & 1.65E+14 \end{bmatrix}$	$e_{C.3} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.47E+03 \\ 2.41E+05 \\ 1.65E+14 \end{bmatrix}$

(a) optimized with `fmincon`

(b) optimized with `ga`

Figure 4.2: Comparison of the optimization results for different load cases: pressure of the inlet mass flow, pressure inside the RSS, sensitivity of parameters over time

Theoretically, the larger the eigenvalues of the FIM deriving from an input trajectory are, the more sensible the model's output should react to a small perturbation in the parameter, and it is therefore easier to deduce its value. Overall, it is apparent, that the first and second eigenvalues of the FIMs are significantly smaller than the third eigenvalue. A change in the parameter $c_{m,in}$ is hence most influential on the RSS model's output, which is only to be expected, given that this parameter is directly affecting the incoming mass flow. The first eigenvalue, which is corresponding to the heat transfer parameter α , is extremely small for the *trivial* (case A) as well as the *det*- and *trace*- optimized cases (cases B.1, B.2, C.1, C.2), but not for the *mineig*- optimized result (cases B.3, C.3).

Figure 4.3: Comparison of the objective values obtained after optimizing the input trajectories and with a trivial input case

That is because the latter optimality criterion's objective is to maximize the minimum eigenvalue, the peaks in the α -sensitivity functions in Figure 4.2 for the *mineig*-optimized input are therefore explained. The *trace* optimality criterion seeks to maximize the sum of the elements on the main diagonal of the FIM and thus focuses on maximizing the most significant parameter's influence - reflected in the biggest values for the third eigenvectors for the *trace*-optimized cases - hence it is logical that the optimal input trajectory for this objective is to charge the storage with maximum pressure (*fmincon*) or rather push its limits by charging and discharging with maximum and minimum pressure, respectively, within short intervals (*ga*). The improvement of the input, optimized with the *det*-optimality criterion, compared to the *trivial* load case is only visible in a slight increase in the FIM as well as in the eigenvalue entries. In order to visualize the improvement of all the optimized input trajectories, Figure 4.3 shows

the objective values $\det(\mathcal{I})$, $\text{trace}(\mathcal{I})$ and $\min(\text{eig}(\mathcal{I}))$ of the FIM for the cases solved with the two solvers compared to the values of the FIM of the trivial load case. As expected, the optimized input trajectories all achieve objective function values higher than the *trivial* input case, and the **ga**- optimized cases' values are again by several orders of magnitude higher than the ones optimized with **fmincon**, except for the *mineig*- optimality criterion, where the solutions of both solvers are quite similar. According to the solvers' results, the **ga**- optimized input trajectories should obtain the most accurate reconstructions of the three parameters.

Parameter estimation

In the following, the question whether the optimality criteria are a good fit to the problem and if the optimizations do improve the sensitivity of the experiment to a change in the parameters in the orders as imposed by the solvers' results will be answered. By assuming a distorted experimental outcome and using the **fmincon** solver to recalculate the actual values for the parameters, the input case's performance in parameter estimation can be validated. A common measurement error is, for example, that the experimental data is not as exact as anticipated. Therefore, the pressure inside the storage vessel, simulated with the load cases A, B.1-3 and C.1-3, is simplified by rounding the continuous output measurement trajectory to integer pressure values. This actually models a common type of measurement error in which the data acquisition in an industrial plants may be configured to store values only with low accuracy.

The optimization solver then optimizes a column vector $\theta = [\alpha, V, c_{m,in}]^T$ that includes the regarded parameters, with the objective to converge the output trajectory obtained with false starting values for the parameters in θ to the presumed experimental output curve, i.e. to minimize the norm between the measured data and the calculated pressure inside the RSS. The starting vector for the **fmincon** solver is defined as 10% of the actual parameter's values ($\theta_0 = 0.1 \times \theta_{actual}$), the upper and lower bounds for the solver are set as $10 \times \theta_{actual}$ and $0.01 \times \theta_{actual}$, respectively. The real parameter values are only assumed, and the actual

storage behaviour remains to be seen during experimental investigations, but this proof is considered effective in order to demonstrate the general performance of the OED.

In Figure 4.4, the actual pressure curve, the measured pressure curve, which is the actual pressure rounded to the next integer number of bar, and the optimized pressure curve for all seven input cases are shown. It appears that the actual output trajectory is met with every load case, solely for the B.1 input case, a slight, thus insignificant, deviation during discharging is visible (Figure 4.4b). There are two possible explanations for this behaviour: either the parameter values are correctly estimated through the optimization with all input cases, which would mean that an optimized input trajectory is no improvement to operating the RSS with a trivial load case with respect to parameter sensitivity, or the influence of the parameters to the model's output is negligibly small, which would make it impossible to determine the actual parameters' values through the experiment.

Figure 4.5 depicts the calculated parameter values in comparison to the actual values. It can be seen that a combination of both given explanations for the accurate pressure approximations for all load cases holds true. The actual values for α are barely met through the optimization for any load case. Only the estimation with the B.3 input yields a good fit for the heat transfer coefficient. Since the objective of this case is to maximize the minimum eigenvalue, which is the eigenvalue corresponding to α , it is to be expected that it achieves the best approximation for this parameter. However, it is surprising that this does not hold true for the *mineig*-optimized case, resulting from the optimization with *ga* (case C.3), where the estimation result is no better than that of the approximation with the trivial load case. This is especially remarkable since the augmentation of the *mineig* objective values from the input trajectory optimizations for *fmincon* and *ga* were similar (see Figure 4.3). Therefore, it is presumable that the heat transfer parameter, subject to the calculation of the heat losses through the storage vessel wall, only has little influence on the storage behaviour.

(a) Input case A

(b) Input case B.1

(c) Input case C.1

(d) Input case B.2

(e) Input case C.2

(f) Input case B.3

(g) Input case C.3

Figure 4.4: Approximation of the pressure inside the RSS to fictive experimental data through parameter estimation over time. Thereby, the blue line represents the measured pressure, rounded to the next integer number of bar, the red line the actual pressure and the yellow line the estimated pressure.

Figure 4.5: Comparison of the parameter fit for the seven load cases for the RSS model

Concerning the volumetric parameter V and the geometric constant for calculating the incoming mass flow $c_{m,in}$ the minimizations of the distance between the measured and the simulated pressure inside the RSS result in similar parameter approximations for the different load cases. Apart from the B.2 input case, where the optimization solver immediately declares a local minimum at the initial point (at 10% of the actual parameters' values), all cases show a good parameter estimation fit. This indicates no improvement through the OED with regards to parameter sensitivity. However, a closer look to the parameter approximations reveals differences in the accuracies of the fits. Table 4.2 shows the actual as well as the estimated parameter values.

Table 4.2: Actual and estimated parameters for the RSS model

	actual value	value from load case						
		A	B.1	B.2	B.3	C.1	C.2	C.3
α	0.8546	0.5110	0.0089	0.0855	0.9919	1.4267	1.5353	0.5048
V	0.8933	0.8915	0.9163	0.0893	0.8939	0.8954	0.8960	0.8921
cm_{in}	5.0000E-05	4.9803E-05	5.1050E-05	4.9978E-06	5.0026E-05	5.0258E-05	5.0304E-05	4.9835E-05

In Table 4.3 the relative approximation errors ϵ between the actual and the estimated parameter vector θ , as well as between the actual and the estimated values for every single parameter, calculated with Equation 4.2, are listed, with the best and worst fit in every column marked in green and red, respectively.

$$\epsilon = \frac{\|\theta_{actual} - \theta_{estimated}\|}{\|\theta_{actual}\|} \quad (4.2)$$

Table 4.3: Parameter approximation errors for the trivial and optimized load cases for the RSS model

	input case	ϵ_{θ}	ϵ_{α}	ϵ_V	$\epsilon_{cm_{in}}$
A	<i>trivial</i>	$2.778E-01$	$4.02E-01$	$2.07E-03$	$3.95E-03$
	optimized with fmincon				
B.1	<i>det - optimized</i>	$6.843E-01$	$9.90E-01$	$2.57E-02$	$2.10E-02$
B.2	<i>trace-optimized</i>	$8.999E-01$	$9.00E-01$	$9.00E-01$	$9.00E-01$
B.3	<i>mineig-optimized</i>	$4.635E-02$	$6.71E-02$	$5.85E-04$	$5.29E-04$
	optimized with ga				
C.1	<i>det-optimized</i>	$4.628E-01$	$6.69E-01$	$2.35E-03$	$5.15E-03$
C.2	<i>trace-optimized</i>	$5.506E-01$	$7.97E-01$	$3.04E-03$	$6.09E-03$
C.3	<i>mineig-optimized</i>	$2.829E-01$	$4.09E-01$	$1.42E-03$	$3.30E-03$

It is apparent, in case of charging and discharging, that the solver achieves parameter values closest to the actual values for the **fmincon** *mineig*- optimized input trajectory (case B.3), even though the measurement curve is distorted, and worst parameter estimations are attained with the other trajectories resulting from the **fmincon** optimizations with the *det* and the *trace* optimality criteria (B.1 and B.2). In contrast to what the high objective values from the **ga** optimizations appeared to predict, the input cases C.1-3 only show moderate quality in the estimation of the parameter values.

As a next step, a second series of input trajectory optimizations is recommended, a method for increasing the certainty to find a global optimum would, for example, be to start the **fmincon** solver with the optimized input vectors from the **ga** optimization. However, since the parameter estimation test showed that the solver accomplished to find the actual pres-

sure curves with all input cases, even though some parameter estimation errors were immense, it was concluded that the model in general is not sensitive to the regarded parameters and the OED does not lead to a significant improvement for the experimental design for the RSS model. Nevertheless, it is advised to include the `fmincon` *mineig*- optimized input trajectory into the experimental plan in order to ensure the gain of informative measurement data for parameter estimation.

4.1.2 PCM Cell

Due to large computation times of the PCM cell model, a simpler test geometry, larger time steps, and selected sensor locations were chosen for the analytical search for the optimal DoE in order to be able to efficiently characterize and get most information from the simulations. Figure 4.6 shows the temperature distribution at the location of sensor 1 (see Figure 4.7) inside the test cell for different numbers of computation mesh elements and two different simulation time steps, when charged with a constant temperature of 200°C over 30 minutes.

Figure 4.6: Temperature at sensor location 1 per second for different numbers of mesh elements. Initial temperature = 180°C, charging temperature = 210°C

It is apparent that the finer the mesh, the smoother the temperature curve for the PCM is, and the later liquification starts. However, computation time increases a lot with more mesh elements, hence it was decided to run the DOE with a mesh element count of 3520, since the smoothness of the respective curve is not significantly inferior to the graphs re-

sulting from the simulation with 7920 and 14080 elements. It has to be noted that the accuracy of the PCM melting behaviour may be suffering under the coarser mesh size for the simulation, but computation is much faster which is of great importance for the OED, since one simulation run is performed hundreds of times during the optimization. A smaller time step does not result in relevant refinements in the modelled temperature distribution, therefore a time step of $\Delta t = 1\text{s}$ was determined as sufficient.

For the optimization of the DoE for the PCM modules, two adjacent PCM cells are considered, because the heat conducting structure is arranged in a meandering shape, and one cell lying above another shows different melting behaviour. In Figure 4.7, the cell geometries for the actual hybrid storage (Figure 4.7a) as well as for the chosen test PCM unit (Figure 4.7b) are shown.

The process for conducting the OED for the PCM cell is the same as for the RSS, though instead of the input trajectory u being described by the pressure of the incoming mass flow, it is characterized as the input temperature T_{in} , originating in the heat transfer from the steam storage through the vessel wall into the side wall of the PCM cell, as pictured in Figure 4.7. The state variable for the optimization is defined as the temperature distribution of the PCM, observed at two locations inside the regarded two PCM cells. All necessary input parameters are defined in the according `input_geom_test.m` file which can be found in Listing A.7 in Appendix A.2. The initial temperature of the PCM is 180°C at all times. During the trivial load case for comparison, the PCM is charged with 210°C for 30 minutes and then discharged for the remaining 30 minutes with 180°C ($\gamma_{triv} = [210, 210, 180, 180]^T$). This input vector also serves as the starting point for the first optimizations with the `fmincon` solver. The minimum and maximum temperature of the PCM (170°C and 220°C , respectively, deriving from the minimum and maximum operational pressure inside the RSS) are set as lower and upper bounds for both optimization solvers, `fmincon` and `ga`. Again, no other (in)equality constraints were set.

(a) actual cell geometries

(b) OED test cell geometries

Figure 4.7: Structure of the PCM unit with sensor placements.

(a) optimized with fmincon

(b) optimized with ga

Figure 4.8: Comparison of the optimization results for different load cases: input temperature trajectory over time, and temperature of the PCM and sensitivity of parameters at sensor location 1 (solid line) and 2 (dashed line) over time.

Figure 4.9: Sensitivity functions optimized with *ga* from Figure 4.8b zoomed out

Optimization results

Figure 4.8 shows the input trajectories for the trivial and the optimized load cases as well as the respective PCM temperature distributions at both sensors and the sensitivities to the two parameters k_s and α_{in} . The scales for the sensitivity functions optimized with *fmincon* and *ga* are adjusted for comparability in Figures 4.8a and 4.8b, the peak values for the sensitivities in Figure 4.8b can be seen in Figure 4.9. The graphs reveal that the sensitivity functions contain very noisy parts during melting and solidification of the PCM. This is caused by the inaccuracy of the PCM simulation that was accepted due to reduced computation time, and intensifies with forming the derivative of the temperature distribution. Especially regarding the optimizations performed with the *ga* solver (Figure 4.8b), it is apparent that the signal noise distorts the attempted optimization results. The solver seeks to maximize or minimize a single peak, arisen from the fluctuations around the melting temperature. An input trajectory that maximizes the influence of a parameter at a singular point that is only derived from the model's imprecision will certainly not reflect the actual experimental behaviour.

In order to smoothen the curves without having to sacrifice computation speed, a filter was applied to every sensitivity function. Therefore, a transfer function model was used to damp the noise oscillation and to prolong its period. The filtered trajectories are displayed in Figure 4.10 in comparison with the unfiltered ones. The peak visibly gets reduced without losing the characteristics of the sensitivities. Henceforth, the sensitivity functions are filtered before being passed to calculate the FIM which determines the optimality criteria for the optimizations. Further, it was decided to no longer pursue the optimality criterion of maximizing the trace of the FIM, because it has not proven to help finding an optimal experimental design for all parameters. Its nature is to always maximize the biggest eigenvalue of the FIM and all parameters responsible for the lower eigenvalues will remain with little influence on the model. The goal of the OED is to increase the sensitivity of the output to all regarded parameters, and therefore the *det* and the *mineig* criteria are better suited for achieving this.

Figure 4.10: Comparison of the filtered and unfiltered sensitivity functions over time for the trivial and the **ga** optimized load cases at sensor location 1

In Figure 4.11, the new optimization results conducted with the **ga** solver and the *det*- and *mineig*- optimality criteria, compared with the temperature distribution and the filtered sensitivities derived from the trivial input, are displayed. This time, the **fmincon** solver was not given the trivial input vector as the optimization starting point, but the results from the **ga** optimization (Figure 4.12). This is a common method to increase the possibil-

ity that the `fmincon` solver finds a global optimum and thus to improve the optimization results. The resulting optimal input trajectory from the optimization with `fmincon` for the *det*-optimality criterion is exactly the same as its starting point, namely the `ga` optimized trajectory. Concerning the *mineig*-optimized case, the `fmincon` solution adds a second charging period to the initial `ga` optimized trajectory. Since the solution of the optimizations with the `ga` solver are basically included in the solutions from the `fmincon` optimization, only the results of the latter will be analyzed henceforth.

Figure 4.11: Comparison of the optimization results for different load cases: input temperature trajectory over time, and temperature of the PCM and sensitivity of parameters at sensor location 1 (solid line) and 2 (dashed line) over time, optimized with `ga`

Other than when loaded with the trivial input case, none of the optimized input trajectories provoke melting of the PCM, they all heat it up to the melting point and cool it down to the minimum temperature. The model reacts most sensitive to the parameters at the beginning of the cooling process after it was held at the melting temperature. This can be explained by the influence of the heat capacity of the solid PCM, which will show no effect on the

Figure 4.12: Comparison of the optimization results for different load cases: input temperature trajectory over time, and temperature of the PCM and sensitivity of parameters at sensor location 1 (solid line) and 2 (dashed line) over time, optimized with `fmincon`

sensitivity functions when the PCM is molten. However, comparing Figure 4.12 with Figure 4.8a, the sensitivity of α_{in} decreases when no liquification takes place, but the optimization solver nevertheless finds solutions with overall higher objective values, as displayed in Figure 4.13. In Table 4.4, the FIM as well as the respective eigenvalues for the trivial and the two optimized load cases are listed. The vector \mathbf{e} is arranged in the way that its first entry is the eigenvalue corresponding to the parameter k_s , and the second entry the one to α_{in} .

Table 4.4: Fisher Information analysis for the trivial and optimized load cases for the PCM cell model

input case		FIM	eigenvalues
A	<i>trivial</i>	$\mathcal{I}_A = \begin{bmatrix} 8.54E+02 & 4.09E+00 \\ 4.09E+00 & 1.05E-01 \end{bmatrix}$	$\mathbf{e}_A = \begin{bmatrix} 8.54E+02 \\ 8.51E-02 \end{bmatrix}$
optimized with <code>fmincon</code>			
B.1	<i>det - optimized</i>	$\mathcal{I}_{B.1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.09E+05 & -9.25E+01 \\ -9.25E+01 & 3.01E-01 \end{bmatrix}$	$\mathbf{e}_{B.1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.09E+05 \\ 2.22E-01 \end{bmatrix}$
B.2	<i>mineig-optimized</i>	$\mathcal{I}_{B.2} = \begin{bmatrix} 7.37E+03 & 2.25E+01 \\ 2.25E+01 & 2.04E-01 \end{bmatrix}$	$\mathbf{e}_{B.2} = \begin{bmatrix} 7.37E+03 \\ 1.35E-01 \end{bmatrix}$

The optimizations led to a considerable increase of the elements of the FIM and its eigenvalues, which is also visible in the increase of the function values for the respective objectives (see Figure 4.13). The determinant of the FIM is three orders of magnitude larger with the optimized input trajectory than with the trivial load case. The minimum eigenvalue for the B.2 input case is almost 60% bigger than the one calculated with the trivial input. This predicts higher parameter sensitivities of the optimized input cases than of the trivial case, and by that more accurate estimations of the actual parameter values.

Parameter estimation

The analysis of the parameter estimation is performed following the same structure as the one for the RSS (see Section 4.1.1). The assumed experimental data is constructed by rounding the temperature distribution at the sensor locations, calculated with the assumed actual parameter values and the respective input temperature trajectories, to integer values. Thereupon, the optimization solver `fmincon` seeks to find the actual values for the parameter vector $\theta = [k_s, \alpha_{in}]^T$ by minimizing the vector norm between the output temperature trajectory calculated with the optimization variable θ and the measured temperature curve. The parameter estimation proof is conducted with different starting vectors for the optimizations in order to compare the reliabilities of the estimations, namely with 10%, 50% and 90% of the actual parameters' values (see Figure 4.14). Lower and upper bounds for the solver are set as $0.1 \times \theta_{actual}$ and $10 \times \theta_{actual}$, respectively.

Figure 4.13: Comparison of the objective values obtained after optimizing the input trajectories and with a trivial input case

When loaded with the trivial input case, the temperature distribution approximations become more accurate the closer the starting values for the parameters are to the actual values. In contrast to that, the optimized input trajectories seem to satisfactorily approach the measured temperature no matter how close the starting values for the parameter estimations are to the actual values. Considering that the optimized cases never invoke liquefaction of the PCM, it can be assumed that this behaviour is beneficial to approximating the experimental data. With the trivial input case it is apparent that it is more difficult to approach the

(a) Input case A, Sensor 1

(b) Input case A, Sensor 2

(c) Input case B.1, Sensor 1

(d) Input case B.1, Sensor 2

(e) Input case B.2, Sensor 1

(f) Input case B.2, Sensor 2

Figure 4.14: Approximation of the temperature of the PCM at sensor locations 1 and 2 to fictive experimental data through parameter estimation over time. Comparison of the accuracy of the approximations with different starting values for the parameters.

temperature distribution through the approximation of the heat conductivity of the solid material and the incoming heat transfer parameter, when having to surpass the melting temperature. This is especially visible in Figure 4.14b, where no estimated temperature trajectory succeeds in approximating the simulated melting process, probably because the location of the second sensor is further away from the heat conducting structure inside the cell than the first sensor is, the reaction to a change in temperature is therefore faster at sensor 1 than at sensor 2. However, looking at the cooling phases of the trajectories, the parameter estimation of the *mineig*- optimized trajectories seem to succeed even better in meeting the actual temperature of the PCM than the *det*- optimized ones. In order to analyze the accuracy of the parameter values, Figure 4.15 shows the distance between the optimized and actual values for the parameters for all load cases and starting parameter vectors.

Figure 4.15: Comparison of the parameter fit for the load cases for the PCM cell model for different optimization starting points

Looking at the scales of Figures 4.15a and 4.15b, it is apparent that the optimizer tends to find values larger than the actual ones for the parameter k_s , and smaller values for α_{in} . When charging with the trivial input trajectory, the optimizer declares the starting values for the heat transfer parameter α_{in} as initial optima and finds values for the heat capacity of the solid PCM k_s many times larger than the actual values. This indicates that the large heat capacity is responsible for the melting of the simulated temperature distribution in Figure 4.14a and that α_{in} has little influence on the model's output. This does not reflect the expected behaviour of the PCM under real experimental conditions, and furthermore, the parameters are generally badly fitted, therefore the trivial input trajectory is not recommended for the DoE when aiming to estimate the parameters k_s and α_{in} . The optimized trajectories perform, as assumed, much better. Both cases B.1 and B.2 perform best when given the starting parameter values closest to the actual ones. As it can be seen in Figure 4.15, as well as in Table 4.5, where the estimated parameter values are enlisted next to the actual values, when given 50% of the parameter values to the optimizer as starting point, it approximates parameter values worse than when starting with only 10% of the actual values. This also holds true for the *det*- optimized case for the parameter α_{in} .

Table 4.5: Actual and estimated parameters for the PCM cell model

	actual value	value from load case								
		$\theta_0 = 0.1 \times \theta_{actual}$			$\theta_0 = 0.5 \times \theta_{actual}$			$\theta_0 = 0.9 \times \theta_{actual}$		
		A	B.1	B.2	A	B.1	B.2	A	B.1	B.2
k_s	0.8700	1.9565	6.3252	5.3000	8.4132	2.2249	5.5949	8.6282	1.7752	1.1721
α_{in}	700.0000	70.0850	608.6228	602.1907	350.5657	506.1630	587.3037	627.6865	629.9711	632.6985

In general, the artificial experimental data distortions modeled here do not allow good estimations of the parameters, especially the estimation of the heat conductivity parameter is highly inaccurate, considering the actual thermo-physical properties of the PCM. In Table 4.6, the relative errors for the parameter approximations, calculated with Equation 4.2, are listed. Hence, it is not surprising that the B.2 case with a 90% starting precision achieves the most exact parameter values for the overall parameter vector as well as the individual parameters, and that the largest approximation errors come with the trivial load cases.

Table 4.6: Parameter approximation errors for the trivial and optimized load cases for the PCM cell model

	input case	ϵ_{θ}	ϵ_{k_s}	$\epsilon_{\alpha_{in}}$
$\theta_0 = 0.1 \times \theta_{actual}$				
A	<i>trivial</i>	$9.00E - 01$	$1.38E + 00$	$9.00E - 01$
B.1	<i>det - optimized</i>	$1.31E - 01$	$6.40E + 00$	$1.31E - 01$
B.2	<i>mineig-optimized</i>	$1.40E - 01$	$5.22E + 00$	$1.40E - 01$
$\theta_0 = 0.5 \times \theta_{actual}$				
A	<i>trivial</i>	$4.99E - 01$	$8.67E + 00$	$4.99E - 01$
B.1	<i>det - optimized</i>	$2.77E - 01$	$1.56E + 00$	$2.77E - 01$
B.2	<i>mineig-optimized</i>	$1.61E - 01$	$5.43E + 00$	$1.61E - 01$
$\theta_0 = 0.9 \times \theta_{actual}$				
A	<i>trivial</i>	$1.04E - 01$	$8.92E + 00$	$1.03E - 01$
B.1	<i>det - optimized</i>	$1.00E - 01$	$1.04E + 00$	$1.00E - 01$
B.2	<i>mineig-optimized</i>	$9.61E - 02$	$3.47E - 01$	$9.61E - 02$

Summing up, it can be concluded that the OED is successful, since an augmentation in parameter sensitivity is achieved. However, looking at the values and relative errors for parameter k_s , it can be summarized that the difference in value between the two regarded parameters is too large for the optimization to find an input trajectory that efficiently increases the model's sensitivity to both parameters. Hence, it was decided to scale the parameter sensitivities, so that their effect on the FIM is equally weighted. Therefore, the calculation of the sensitivity of a parameter θ_i on the output y , described in Equation 2.5, is being adjusted by dividing the model's deviation for a small perturbation of the parameter $\Delta\theta_i$ around their nominal value $\theta_{i,0}$ by the nominal output $y(t; \theta_{i,0})$. This ensures that the sensitivity functions represent a relative variation in the PCM's temperature distribution which improves numeric conditioning of the FIM. Accordingly, the relative sensitivities are henceforth calculated with Equation 4.3:

$$\left. \frac{dy(t; \theta_i)}{d\theta_i} \right|_{\theta_{i,0}} = \frac{y(t; \theta_{i,0} + \Delta\theta_i) - y(t; \theta_{i,0})}{y(t; \theta_{i,0})} \quad (4.3)$$

Optimization results

The results of the optimizations with the newly determined relative parameter sensitivities for the two parameters k_s and α_{in} are shown in Figures 4.16 and 4.17. The resulted optimal input vector γ from the optimization with the `ga` solver is again utilized as the starting input vector γ_0 for the optimization with `fmincon`. While the *mineig*- optimized trajectory remains the same after the renewed optimization, the *det*- optimized trajectory not only differs between Figures 4.16 and 4.17 but also provokes melting of the PCM which is directly reproduced in an increased sensitivity of the output to the parameter α_{in} .

Figure 4.16: Comparison of the optimization results for different load cases: input temperature trajectory over time, and temperature of the PCM and relative sensitivities of parameters at sensor location 1 (solid line) and 2 (dashed line) over time, optimized with `ga`

Figure 4.17: Comparison of the optimization results for different load cases: input temperature trajectory over time, and temperature of the PCM and relative sensitivities of parameters at sensor location 1 (solid line) and 2 (dashed line) over time, optimized with `fmincon`

The FIM for the input cases optimized with `fmincon` is now weighted. As apparent in Table 4.7, compared to when composed of the absolute sensitivities to the parameters, the entries of the FIM as well as its eigenvalues decrease in value but the difference between the smaller and the larger eigenvalue is also significantly reduced, and numeric conditioning of the FIM is much improved.

Table 4.7: Fisher Information analysis composed with the relative sensitivities to the parameters for the trivial and optimized load cases for the PCM cell model

input case		FIM	eigenvalues
A	<i>trivial</i>	$\mathcal{I}_A = \begin{bmatrix} 1.65E-06 & 3.45E-06 \\ 3.45E-06 & 1.34E-04 \end{bmatrix}$	$e_A = \begin{bmatrix} 1.56E-06 \\ 1.34E-04 \end{bmatrix}$
optimized with <code>fmincon</code>			
B.1	<i>det - optimized</i>	$\mathcal{I}_{B.1} = \begin{bmatrix} 8.17E-07 & 1.47E-05 \\ 1.47E-05 & 4.52E-04 \end{bmatrix}$	$e_{B.1} = \begin{bmatrix} 3.38E-07 \\ 4.52E-04 \end{bmatrix}$
B.2	<i>mineig-optimized</i>	$\mathcal{I}_{B.2} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.45E-05 & -1.82E-06 \\ -1.82E-06 & 1.77E-04 \end{bmatrix}$	$e_{B.2} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.45E-05 \\ 1.77E-04 \end{bmatrix}$

Parameter estimation

The assumption of the change in the calculation of the sensitivity matrix increasing the model's ability to accurately estimate the parameters through the optimizations is analyzed through the parameter estimation test. As done previously, this test is performed by fitting the model's output to a distorted, fictive measured temperature curve. In Figure 4.18, the measured, actual and estimated temperature distributions for the three input cases A, B.1 and B.2 are displayed. The estimations are again conducted with 10%, 50% and 90% of the actual parameter value vector as starting vector.

Once again, it can be observed that the smaller the distance between the actual and the starting parameter vector is, the better the temperature curve is approximated. Nevertheless, it is apparent that the trajectory obtained from the optimization with the starting vector $\theta_0 = 0.5 \times \theta$ diverges most from the actual temperature distribution for the optimized input cases B.1-2. This is also visible in Figure 4.19b, but not true for the parameter estimation of k_s (see Figure 4.19a), which can be explained by the smaller influence of the

(a) Input case A, Sensor 1

(b) Input case A, Sensor 2

(c) Input case B.1, Sensor 1

(d) Input case B.1, Sensor 2

(e) Input case B.2, Sensor 1

(f) Input case B.2, Sensor 2

Figure 4.18: Approximation of the temperature of the PCM at sensor locations 1 and 2 to fictive experimental data through parameter estimation over time. Comparison of the accuracy of the approximations with different starting values for the parameters.

PCM's heat capacity on the temperature than of the incoming heat transfer parameter.

Figure 4.19: Comparison of the parameter fit for the load cases for the PCM cell model with relative sensitivities for different optimization starting points

In general, the parameter estimation with the trajectories derived from the optimization, using the FIM calculated with the relative sensitivity functions, does not show any improvement compared to the use of the absolute sensitivities. The estimated parameter values and the parameter approximation errors are listed in Table 4.8 and Table 4.9.

Table 4.8: Actual and estimated parameters for the PCM cell model with relative sensitivities

actual value	value from load case									
	$\theta_0 = 0.1 \times \theta_{actual}$			$\theta_0 = 0.5 \times \theta_{actual}$			$\theta_0 = 0.9 \times \theta_{actual}$			
	A	B.1	B.2	A	B.1	B.2	A	B.1	B.2	
k_s	0.8700	1.9565	3.7166	5.7771	8.4132	8.6989	0.4349	8.6282	8.3347	1.6619
α_{in}	700.0000	70.0850	667.9731	595.2386	350.5657	470.4681	349.9999	627.6865	630.2439	631.4138

Even though the overall approximation errors have been reduced, the effect of using the relative sensitivities is not as significant as expected. Furthermore, narrowing the distance from the starting parameters for the `fmincon` optimization solver to the actual parameter values was not effective in improving the parameter estimations for the optimized input cases. However, an in depth analysis and further revision and enhancement of the OED were beyond the scope of this thesis.

The results of the parameter estimation prove, nevertheless, that charging and discharging with the optimized input trajectories, leads to the PCM model reacting more sensitively to a change in the regarded parameters than when (dis-)charged with a trivial input trajectory. The smallest approximation error for the analysis of both parameters, k_s and α_{in} , is achieved with the *det*- optimized trajectory under the assumption that the difference between the actual and the presumed parameter values is large. The actual material properties of the PCM utilized for the hybrid storage are not expected to differ a lot from the presumed values. Therefore, the *mineig*- optimized input is likely to provide better parameter estimations.

Table 4.9: Parameter approximation errors for the trivial and optimized load cases for the PCM cell model with relative sensitivities

input case		ϵ_{θ}	ϵ_{k_s}	$\epsilon_{\alpha_{in}}$
$\theta_0 = 0.1 \times \theta_{actual}$				
A	<i>trivial</i>	$9.00E - 01$	$1.38E + 00$	$9.00E - 01$
B.1	<i>det - optimized</i>	$4.59E - 02$	$3.40E + 00$	$4.58E - 02$
B.2	<i>mineig-optimized</i>	$1.50E - 01$	$5.77E + 00$	$1.50E - 01$
$\theta_0 = 0.5 \times \theta_{actual}$				
A	<i>trivial</i>	$4.99E - 01$	$8.67E + 00$	$4.99E - 01$
B.1	<i>det - optimized</i>	$3.28E - 01$	$9.00E + 00$	$3.28E - 01$
B.2	<i>mineig-optimized</i>	$5.00E - 01$	$5.00E - 01$	$5.00E - 01$
$\theta_0 = 0.9 \times \theta_{actual}$				
A	<i>trivial</i>	$1.04E - 01$	$8.92E + 00$	$1.03E - 01$
B.1	<i>det - optimized</i>	$1.00E - 01$	$8.58E + 00$	$9.97E - 02$
B.2	<i>mineig-optimized</i>	$9.80E - 02$	$9.10E - 01$	$9.80E - 02$

4.2 Discussion of the Results

The present results from the OEDs for the pure RSS as well as the PCM unit provide a lot of information on the behaviour of the hybrid storage and the reaction of the simulation models to the regarded parameters. Even though the RSS model and the PCM cell model are based on different numerical approaches, and the computation methods are not similar, it was shown that the presented OED is applicable for both models and hence can be adapted for any use case. Yet, the level of enhancement in parameter sensitivity that the optimized DoE will bring is strongly dependent on the model itself and the influence the parameter has on its output, along with which parameters and in which combinations they are to be evaluated.

For the RSS model, the parameters that were most influential on the pressure distribution inside the storage were also the ones that were easily estimated, even with a trivial input trajectory. The observations of the estimation of the parameter with the minimum influence showed that the best optimality criterion for OEDs with parameters of different significances to the model's output is the maximization of the minimum eigenvalue of the FIM, and that maximizing the FIM's trace is not very effective to improve the sensitivity to all regarded parameters. Furthermore, it was noticed that even though the optimizations with the `ga` solver achieved much higher values for the optimality criteria than the `fmincon` solver, the trial validations showed no increase in approximation accuracies for the `ga` optimized input trajectories.

The OED for the PCM unit required several adjustments to the optimization model. The optimization procedure was modified by no longer comparing the results from the optimizations with the two MATLAB solvers, but to use the result from `ga` as starting point for `fmincon`, improving solution quality under the present computational limitations. Additionally, the remarkable amplifications of the noise within the temperature distribution of the PCM in the sensitivity functions made it difficult to prevent the optimization solvers from focusing on the artificially produced oscillation peaks. Analysing the parameter val-

idation results, it was noticed that the numerical value of one parameter was significantly smaller than that of the other one, hence it was decided to normalize the sensitivity functions so that their influence on the model is comparable. However, this method did not show great improvement in the parameter estimation results, which implies that the parameter smaller in value also has less impact on the output. Accordingly, a difference in orders of magnitude between the parameter values is not as influential on the performance of the OED as the influence that a parameter's variance has to the simulation model. On the basis of the discussed optimization for the PCM cell, further optimizations with other parameters such as the heat conductivity of liquid PCM, the melting temperature, the dynamic viscosity or the thermal expansion of the PCM can be performed. In order to include the OED results in the experimental plan for the prototype testing of the hybrid storage, the optimizations have to be conducted again with the actual cell geometries and sensor locations, and accordingly refined mesh (and thus increased computation times).

The present optimization results provide an insight to the methodical approach for establishing an optimal input trajectory for improving parameter sensitivity. It was successfully proven that the application of an OED led to higher parameter sensitivities to the model's output than by passing a trivial input to the model. The actual experiments on the test storage will reveal if these theoretical improvements sustain in reality.

4.3 Final Design of the Experimental Plan

The experimental plan covers a detailed list of experiments that should be conducted during the testing of the storage prototype. After taking the existing storage infrastructure and the local possibilities to charge, discharge and measure the state variables of the storage into consideration, it was decided that the experimental plan should contain the following information for each distinct experimental run:

1. **Run label**
2. **Total duration of the experiment**
3. **Initial values:** Filling level, temperature and pressure inside the RSS, temperature of the PCM*
4. **Charging conditions:** Duration of charging, charging pressure, duration of holding pressure at constant value**
5. **Values after charging is completed:** Filling level, temperature and pressure inside the RSS, temperature of the PCM*
6. **Discharging conditions:** Duration of discharging, discharging pressure, duration of holding pressure at constant value**
7. **Values after discharging is completed:** Filling level, temperature and pressure inside the RSS, temperature of the PCM*
8. **Description of the experimental run**

For charging and discharging of the storage, the pressure can either be predefined as a constant value (i.e. a step function) that is kept for the given time, or as the final value that should be reached with a linear function (i.e. a ramp function) over the course of the given time. The indicated values for the state variables after (dis-)charging are only simulated, non-binding benchmarks for the experiments. They are supposed to help to understand its aim and how the results should look like, which is important for being able to quickly realize when problems occur.

*Not necessary for the experiments on the pure steam storage

**Not necessary for the experiments with constant (dis-)charging pressure

The trials are organized into two times four groups, as shown in Table 4.10. In order to ensure comparability, the same experiments should be performed on the pure RSS and the hybrid storage under the exact same conditions.

Table 4.10: Structure of experimental plan

Storage type	Label	Description	Type of (dis-)charging
pure RSS	A	trivial load cases	with step function
	B	trivial load cases	with ramp function
	C	detailed load cases	with ramp function
	D	optimized load cases	with step function
hybrid storage	E	trivial load cases	with step function
	F	trivial load cases	with ramp function
	G	detailed load cases	with ramp function
	H	optimized load cases	with step function

The trivial load cases (cases A,B and E,F) include first charging and afterwards discharging the storage with different mass flow pressures, as well as charging the storage until a quasi-stationary condition is met and then observing cooling behaviour and storage losses. The detailed load cases (C and G) describe longer sequences of charging and discharging, aiming to provoke more extreme storage operation and hence depict the storage behaviour as broadly as possible. Finally, the optimized load cases (D and H) are the ones resulting from the performed OED, with the objective to accurately estimate unknown parameter values. The optimized input trajectories for the hybrid storage will be calculated with the actual storage geometries and not with the test PCM unit that has been discussed in Section 4.1.2. The process of obtaining the load cases is not described in this thesis, because the optimizations will be performed after the thesis was finalised. The detailed experimental plan with all the listed information can be found in Appendix B.1.

After having defined which experiments to conduct in the experimental plan, an experimental sequence (i.e. an experimental matrix) was derived. In order to set up the experimental matrix, two factors have to be considered [39]:

- **Number of replicates:** How often will the individual experimental runs be repeated?
- **Run order:** In which order will the experimental runs be conducted?

For the experimental investigation of the HyStEPs prototype, no statistical design, but a thought-through order of the experimental runs, based on internal discussions, was established. The final run order of the experiments, assigned to the days intended for the conduct of the tests, is listed in Appendix B.2.

Chapter 5

Upscaling of the Hybrid Storage

Looking forward, the economic and technical feasibility of the hybrid storage concept has to be analyzed. Embedded in the HyStEPs project, Hofmann et al. [36] published a design optimization tool that assesses the economic feasibility of a hybrid storage system and evaluated the cost-effectiveness of retrofitting already implemented RSS systems. Emerging from this model based analysis, a techno-economic analysis based on experimental results is planned. For this purpose, among other studies, further scientific work is embedded in the project that aims to optimize the storage operation with regards to available and needed energy in the form of steam, required charging and discharging rates, energy prices and other factors, based on actual conditions given at the energy storage grid at voestalpine Stahl Donawitz GmbH. The present thesis makes a contribution to the development of this optimization model by developing a MATLAB function that models the required dimensions and material costs for the hybrid storage for a range of maximum loading capacities. This model and a few interpretations are presented in this chapter.

5.1 Basic Assumptions and Evaluations

The basic concept of the presented model is to calculate the required RSS dimensions, and thereby the dimensions of the attached PCM modules, for a range of storage capacities. Hereby, the following assumptions were made:

- The energy stored in the vessel steel is negligible.
- The length to diameter ratio is constant for all regarded RSS scales, and holds for the ratio between cylindrical length and inner as well as outer diameter, the difference between inner and outer diameter of the RSS vessel is hence negligible for the ratio.
- P460NH is chosen as material for the RSS vessel.
- EN AW 1200 is chosen as material for the heat conducting structure.
- $\text{LiNO}_3 - \text{NaNO}_3$ is chosen as the PCM.
- The mass of the PCM module case is negligible.
- The mass of the supporting steel structure is one third of the vessel steel mass.
- The costs are calculated with fixed cost coefficients, see Table 5.1.
- The PCM modules have the same layer thickness and width for all RSS storage dimensions due to a predefined storage cycle time.

With the energy balance equation for the RSS (Equation 5.1) the liquid-steam volume $V_{RSS} = V_{v,RSS} + V_{l,RSS}$ can be calculated for a known total stored energy Q_{RSS} . Hereby, the density, and the specific enthalpy of the liquid and the steam phases, $\rho_{v,RSS}$ and $\rho_{l,RSS}$, and $h_{v,RSS}$ and $h_{l,RSS}$, respectively, are determined for a given operating pressure with the MATLAB implementation `XSteam` [64].

$$Q_{RSS} = V_{v,RSS} \rho_{v,RSS} h_{v,RSS} + V_{l,RSS} \rho_{l,RSS} h_{l,RSS} \quad (5.1)$$

The steam volume can be expressed through the liquid volume and the filling level fl of the storage:

$$V_{v,RSS} = V_{l,RSS} \frac{1 - fl}{fl}. \quad (5.2)$$

Differing from the dynamic RSS model used for the DoE (see Section 3.2.1), the storage vessel is not assumed as a cylinder with plane side faces, but with the actual hemispherical dished bottoms. The calculation of the steam vessel is done after *DIN EN 12953-3:2016-12* [65], the torispherical heads are calculated after *DIN 28011:2012-06* [66]. The volume of the liquid-steam mixture is the same as the inner volume of the vessel, composed of the cylindrical volume $V_{Z,RSS}$ and the torispherical head volume $V_{K,RSS}$ (Equation 5.3), hence, for a fixed length to diameter ratio L/D , the inner diameter D_i , and with that the necessary

wall thicknesses s and s_K , can be derived.

$$\begin{aligned} V_{RSS} &= V_{v,RSS} + V_{i,RSS} = V_{Z,RSS} + V_{K,RSS} \\ &= \frac{\pi D_i^2 (D_i \cdot L/D)}{4} + 2 \left(0.1 D_i^3 + \frac{\pi}{4} D_i^2 3.5 s_K \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5.3)$$

The total surface A_{RSS} of the RSS vessel is calculated with Equation 5.4 by adding the shell surface of the cylindrical vessel $A_{Z,RSS}$ to twice the surface of a torispherical head $A_{K,RSS}$.

$$\begin{aligned} A_{RSS} &= A_{Z,RSS} + A_{K,RSS} \\ &= \pi D_a (D_a \cdot L/D) + 2 \left(0.99 D_a^2 + \pi D_a 3.5 s_K \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5.4)$$

The number of modules N_M attached to the RSS are estimated with Equation 5.5 and rounded to the next smaller integer value, whereby b_{PCM} denotes the width of one module.

$$N_M = 2 \frac{(D_a \cdot L/D)}{b_{PCM}} \quad (5.5)$$

Adding the wall thickness of the PCM module s_M twice to the RSS's outer diameter D_a yields the inner diameter of the module $d_{i,PCM}$. The outer diameter of the PCM module $d_{a,PCM}$ is the inner diameter $d_{i,PCM}$ plus twice the PCM layer thickness s_{PCM} and the wall thickness s_M . As illustrated in Figure 2.4, the modules do not surround the whole storage vessel, but only to an angle φ_M , and are only up to φ_{PCM} degree filled with PCM. Equation 5.6 describes the calculation of the volume inside one PCM module.

$$V_M = \frac{\pi \cdot \varphi_M}{4 \cdot 360} (d_{a,PCM}^2 - d_{i,PCM}^2) b_{PCM} \quad (5.6)$$

Assuming that the angle enclosed by one PCM cell is small compared to the whole module, the number of cells N_{cell} , and hence the volume inside a module that is taken up by the aluminium heat conducting structure V_{alu} , can be calculated through the mean distance x_{alu} between the aluminium fins with the width s_{alu} , that define the PCM cell, with Equations 5.7 and 5.8. The obtained value for N_{cell} is rounded to the next smaller integer value.

$$N_{cell} = \frac{\pi \cdot \varphi_M}{360} \frac{d_{a,PCM}}{x_{alu}} \quad (5.7)$$

$$V_{alu} = N_{cell} (2 s_{PCM} s_{alu} + (x_{alu} - s_{alu}) s_{alu}) b_{PCM} \quad (5.8)$$

The volume of the PCM V_{PCM} constitutes of the volume of one module minus the volume of the aluminium fins that is within the part of the module that is filled with PCM:

$$V_{PCM} = V_M - \frac{\varphi_{PCM}}{\varphi_M} V_{alu} . \quad (5.9)$$

Further, the masses of the steel vessel m_{RSS} , the heat conducting structure m_{alu} and the PCM m_{PCM} can be derived through multiplication of the volumes with the respective densities (see Equations 5.10, 5.11 and 5.12).

$$\begin{aligned} m_{RSS} &= m_{Z,RSS} + 2 m_{K,RSS} \\ &= \rho_{St} \left(\frac{\pi}{4} (D_a^2 - D_i^2) (D_a \cdot L/D) + 2 \left(0.1 (D_a^3 - D_i^3) + \frac{\pi}{4} (D_a^2 - D_i^2) 3.5 s_K \right) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5.10)$$

$$m_{PCM} = \rho_{PCM} V_{PCM} N_M \quad (5.11)$$

$$m_{alu} = \rho_{alu} V_{alu} N_M \quad (5.12)$$

With the mass of the PCM, the energy stored in the PCM can be calculated with the energy balance equation for a considered temperature difference $T_2 - T_1$ (Equation 5.13). Hereby, Δh denotes the phase change enthalpy and $c_{p,PCM}$ the specific heat capacity of the PCM.

$$Q_{PCM} = m_{PCM} (\Delta h + c_{p,PCM} (T_2 - T_1)) \quad (5.13)$$

For the surface that needs to be covered with insulation A_{iso} , as calculated in Equation 5.14, the outer surface of the hybrid storage A_{hybrid} , calculated with the outer diameter of the PCM, plus the surfaces of the parabolic dishes $A_{K,RSS}$, is considered. If only the costs for a pure RSS are considered, A_{iso} is the surface area of the RSS A_{RSS} .

$$\begin{aligned} A_{iso} &= A_{hybrid} + A_{K,RSS} \\ &= \pi (d_{a,PCM} + s_M) (D_a \cdot L/D) + 2 (0.99 D_a^2 + \pi D_a 3.5 s_K) \end{aligned} \quad (5.14)$$

Finally, the total costs add up to:

$$C_{total} = c_{RSS} m_{RSS} + c_{iso} A_{iso} + c_{sup} \frac{m_{RSS}}{3} + c_{PCM} m_{PCM} + c_{alu} m_{alu} . \quad (5.15)$$

The values for the input variables used to model the upscaling of the RSS are enlisted in Table 5.1. The model was implemented in MATLAB [6], and the code listing can be found in Appendix A.3.

5.2 Upscaling Results and Cost Estimations

In order to be able to characterize the heat transfer between the RSS and the PCM modules for a range of maximum capacities and for different maximum pressures inside the steam storage vessel, the heat transfer surface, which is the outer surface of the cylindrical part of the RSS, has to be known. As elaborated in the preceding section, the desired capacity influences the volume of the steam storage vessel. The necessary wall thickness of the vessel is increasing with higher maximum pressures and subsequently higher maximum temperatures inside the storage. The temperatures of the liquid-steam mixture for different pressures is shown in Figure 5.1.

Figure 5.1: Temperature over pressure inside the RSS

Table 5.1: Input variable values for the RSS upscaling model. Unless otherwise specified, the values are estimated from internal practical experience.

Description	Symbol	Value
RSS properties		
Length to diameter ratio	L/D	3
Filling level at maximum loading	fl	0.9
PCM module properties¹		
Width of PCM module	b_{PCM}	0.555 m
Vessel encasing angle of PCM module	φ_M	135°
Filling angle PCM	φ_{PCM}	120°
Layer thickness PCM	s_{PCM}	0.03 m
Wall thickness PCM module	s_M	0.003 m
Thickness aluminium fin	s_{alu}	0.001 m
Mean distance between aluminium fins	x_{alu}	0.008 m
Material properties		
Density of vessel steel	ρ_{St}	7850 kg/m ³
Density of PCM ¹	ρ_{PCM}	2317 kg/m ³
Density of aluminium ¹	ρ_{alu}	2800 kg/m ³
Melting temperature of PCM ¹	Tm_{PCM}	192 °C
Phase change enthalpy PCM ¹	Δh	309.1 kJ/kg
Specific heat capacity liquid PCM ¹	$c_{p,l,PCM}$	1.726 kJ/(kg K)
Cost coefficients		
Costs per kg steel	c_{RSS}	10 €/kg
Costs per m ² insulation	c_{iso}	120 €/m ²
Costs per kg supporting steel structure	c_{sup}	2 €/kg
Costs per kg PCM ²	c_{PCM}	3.7 €/kg
Costs per kg aluminium ³	c_{alu}	2.15 €/kg

¹ values from the HyStEPs prototype data sheet

² value calculated for a constitution of 49% by weight LiNO₃ and 51% by weight NaNO₃, prices from [www.alibaba.com/LiNO₃](http://www.alibaba.com/LiNO3) and [www.alibaba.com/NaNO₃](http://www.alibaba.com/NaNO3), last accessed June 12, 2020

³ value taken from [36]

The wall thickness of the cylindrical RSS part, the outer diameter, the volume and the surface area of the RSS as a function of the maximum stored energy is displayed in Figure 5.2, Figure 5.3, Figure 5.4 and Figure 5.5, respectively, for different pressures. The steps that are visible in the wall thickness functions are originating in its iteration after the *DIN EN 12953-3:2016-12* norm. The values for the wall thicknesses are rounded to integer values, which is depicted in the smaller steps in figure 5.2. The bigger leaps at wall thickness values of 1.6 mm, 4 mm and 6 mm are caused by the permissible stresses on the vessel wall increasing by leaps for classes of wall thicknesses. As mentioned before, the wall thickness significantly increases with higher pressures. The necessary diameters, and hence the volume and surface area, however, are smaller for higher pressures inside the storage, because the energy density is higher for bigger pressures.

Figure 5.2: Wall thickness of the RSS over maximum capacities for different pressures

The main cost driver for RSSs is the steel mass, but costs for insulation and the supporting steel structure are taken into account as well. In Figure 5.6, the composition of the costs for a RSS with an operating pressure of 30 bar over the maximum capacity is shown.

Figure 5.3: Outer diameter of the RSS over maximum capacities for different pressures

Figure 5.4: Inner volume of the RSS over maximum capacities for different pressures

It is apparent, that the cost function is linearly increasing. For a better analysis, the specific RSS costs per MWh stored energy are plotted over the necessary storage volumes in Figure 5.7 for different pressures.

Even though the steps within the specific cost functions are irritating the picture, the trend of the cost development for increasing vessel volumes to quickly decrease and then remain constant is visible, the inclination of the steps indicate the overall function profile of the

Figure 5.5: Outer surface of the RSS over maximum capacities for different pressures

specific RSS costs. For higher pressures, the costs per MWh show upward leaps, which are emerging from the belonging to a higher class of allowable stress and by this a significant increase in the necessary wall thickness. The upscaling function only considers maximum loading capacities up to 40 MWh, accordingly, the required vessel volume for the highest maximum capacity is smaller for higher operating pressures, and the specific cost functions are cut off at the respective value for the maximum RSS volume. The plotted functions could, however, be prolonged to larger volumes.

The precise amount of energy stored in the PCM modules could not be considered in this model, since the charging behaviour is dependent on the heat transfer as well as the temperature difference over a regarded time period, and the upscaling function is only considering the maximum stored heat inside the RSS at a distinct operating pressure. Nevertheless, the geometric dimensions of the PCM modules can be calculated for the different maximum loading capacities and thus the maximum possible capacity of the PCM modules can be approximated through the amount of heat stored in the liquid PCM for a temperature range between the melting temperature of the PCM and the maximum temperature inside the RSS, plus the energy stored during phase transition. Figure 5.8 shows the increase of the storage capacity of the PCM modules over the maximum RSS loading capacity.

Figure 5.6: Cost composition for a RSS loaded with 30 bar over maximum capacities

Figure 5.7: Specific costs over RSS volume for different pressures

Figure 5.8: Maximum capacities of the PCM modules over maximum capacities of the RSS for different pressures

It is apparent, that the RSS capacity constitutes the majority of the total storage capacity of the hybrid storage, the additional energy stored in the PCM only ranges between 0.01 MW h and 0.08 MW h. With an increase in the PCM layer thickness according to the outer diameter of the RSS vessel, the additional storage capacity of the hybrid storage compared to the pure RSS would augment proportionally. In this model, a fixed layer thickness was chosen because the duration of the melting process was considered fixed.

With the cost functions for the RSS vessel, including costs for the insulation and supporting steel structure, the PCM and the heat conducting structure, the total costs for the hybrid storage can be estimated. Note, that the costs for the casing of the PCM modules are not considered in this cost evaluation. For the total amount of stored energy, only the loading capacities of the RSS and the PCM are taken into account. The energy stored within the steel mass as well as in the aluminium heat conducting structure is negligibly small.

In Figure 5.9, the composition of the costs for the hybrid storage with an operating pressure of 30 bar over the total maximum capacity for the hybrid storage, and in Figure 5.10 the comparison of the total costs for a pure RSS with the total costs for the hybrid storage is depicted.

Figure 5.9: Cost composition for the hybrid storage loaded with 30 bar over total maximum capacities

Figure 5.10: Total costs for the pure RSS and the hybrid storage over the respective maximum capacities for different pressures

Figure 5.10 shows, that, according to this model, the total costs for the hybrid storage are proportionally higher than for a RSS with the same maximum capacity. This originates in the fact, that the additionally stored energy in the PCM modules is almost negligibly small compared to the capacity of the RSS (compare Figure 5.8). In their cost analysis, Hofmann et al. [36] have taken the charging and discharging rates of the PCM modules into account and used an adjusted PCM layer thicknesses and a different, cheaper PCM. They came to the conclusion, that the retrofitting of RSSs is economically feasible for long charge/discharge times, small RSS vessel volumes and small additional storage capacities. It can be deduced, that the dimensions of the storages considered in the present upscaling model are not suitable for a significant analysis of the hybrid storage concept's economic efficiency.

5.3 Future Implementation

After having calculated the variables for the fictive storages, the obtained vectors with the information on the required dimensions and estimated costs of the pure RSS as well as the hybrid storage for the regarded maximum loading capacities are passed to another function that determines the transmitted heat capacity between RSS and PCM modules. The switch-over point at which charging and discharging of the PCM takes place is being calculated and passed to the main optimization model that finally defines the optimal storage operation with regard to economic efficiency.

After the experiments on the HyStEPs prototype will be concluded, a thorough techno-economic analysis referring to the actual increase in the storage capacity, and pay off and amortisation rates is planned.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

6.1 Summary

The main objective of this thesis was to develop an optimal design of experiment for the planned experimental investigations on the novel hybrid thermal energy storage that was invented within the framework of the HyStEPs project, in which this thesis is embedded. After giving a short introduction to the topic and the development of this diploma thesis in Chapter 1, the necessary theoretical background for the subject matter was given in Chapter 2. First, the fundamental mechanisms and important features of the two hybrid storage components, the RSS as sensible and the PCM as the latent heat TES part, were explained. Thereupon, the final HyStEPs storage concept was presented. Ultimately, the basics of optimal experimental design as applied in system identification theory were given. In Chapter 3, the approaches to model an OED were discussed. After having established the guiding research questions for the DoE, the parameters to be investigated were selected according to a scheme that evaluates the uncertainty of a parameter according to the divergence in its values that were found in the literature. Subsequently, the models for the hybrid storage sub components, on which the OED was performed, were outlined, and the structure of the optimization code that was established in the course of this thesis was mapped.

The results of the OED can be found in Chapter 4. Divided into results of the optimizations of the experiments on a pure RSS and on the PCM modules, the obtained optimal inputs, along with a validation of these results that was based on fictive measurement data, were set out and discussed. It was achieved to prove, that the optimized storage loading scenarios lead to higher parameter sensitivities within the model's output than if charged and discharged with a trivial, yet reasonable load case. Based on the final set of optimal loading scenarios for the storage, as well as personal expertise of project partners, the experimental plan was derived.

The answers to the research questions posed in Chapter 3 can be summarized as follows:

1. The heat transfer parameters through the RSS storage vessel, the heat conductivity parameters of the PCM, the convection parameters and the geometric coefficient for the calculation of the inlet mass flow are the parameters deemed most uncertain within the hybrid storage model.
2. Compared to the geometric parameters, examined within the OED for the RSS model, the heat transfer parameter has a smaller impact on the model's output, meaning that it is more difficult to retrospectively estimate the actual heat transfer coefficient than the volumetric or the mass flow parameter. The sensitivity of the RSS model to the volumetric parameter is visible during the whole charging and discharging cycle, while a change in the inlet mass flow geometric parameter seemingly only affects the pressure inside the storage vessel during the charging process. The model's sensitivity to the heat transfer parameter is only noticeable during fast discharging of the storage.
3. Concerning the PCM cell model, it was discovered that the heat transfer from the RSS vessel wall has great influence on the temperature distribution inside the PCM unit during the process of melting. The model's sensitivity to the heat conductivity of the solid PCM is maximized when the PCM is heated up to its melting temperature and subsequently cooled down. The influence of the other uncertain parameters were not further investigated in this thesis.
4. The criterion to maximize the minimum eigenvalue of the FIM yielded the most ac-

curate parameter estimations for all models, determining factors and optimization solvers. The obtained optimal input trajectories can be found in the respective Sections in Chapter 4.

Apart from the experimental preparation, this thesis also covered the development of an upscaling model for the RSS that later was used to determine and evaluate the amelioration of the hybrid storage system with regard to heat transfer, energy density and cost effectiveness. This upscaling model was outlined in Chapter 5.

6.2 Further Research

Even though the presented OED succeeded in establishing input trajectories for the experimental investigations that are showing an increased sensitivity to the considered parameters, the actual improvements of the optimized loading cases towards trivial loading cases are yet to be confirmed by the experiments. This thesis provides more a general approach on how to build an optimal DoE for complex simulation models by demonstrating its limitations and challenges, and assessing optimality criteria, optimization solvers and the framework for a successful OED.

For future research, it is advised to carry out the optimizations for combinations of parameters with similar influence on the model, in order to pursue an evenly distributed sensitivity to all parameters whose estimation is desired. Further, it could be considered to adapt the form of the input trajectories from constant values to a more dynamic form to give the model the opportunity to react actively to smaller changes. Also a longer simulation time could be advantageous to the OED results.

In the future, the experiments on the lab-scale hybrid storage will validate the simulation models and reveal the actual storage behaviour. The obtained data will enable a direct comparison between the hybrid and the reference steam storage, so that the economic efficiency of the novel concept can be assessed.

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Appendix A

MATLAB Code Listings

In this appendix, the MATLAB code files that were formed or adapted in this theses are enlisted. First, the codes for the OED of the RSS (Section 4.1.1) and, subsequently, of the PCM (Section 4.1.2) are presented. Lastly, the code for the upscaling model from Chapter 5 is listed.

A.1 Optimal Experimental Design RSS

Listing A.1: Code of run file for the RSS OED model run_oed_RSS

```

1  %% OED RSS
2  % Author: Carlotta Tubeuf
3  % Last modified: 28.02.2020
4  %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
5  %% preprocessing OED RSS
6  % add open-source thermophysical property library CoolProp
7  addpath('.\CoolProp');
8  % general input data
9  f_max=0.95;           % maximum filling level [1]
10 f_min=0.05;          % minimum filling level [1]
11 p_max=23e5;          % maximum pressure inside the storage [Pa]
12 p_min=7e5;           % minimum pressure inside the storage [Pa]
13 t_start=0;           % simulation start [s]
14 t_ende=1*3600;       % simulation end [s]
15 dt=1;                % time step [s]
16 alpha_i=5000;        % heat transfer coefficient inside [W/(m^2*K)]
17                     % (condensing steam)
18 alpha_a=5;           % heat transfer coefficient outside [W/(m^2*K)]
19                     % (stationary air)
20 lambda_iso=0.062;    % thermal conductivity of isolation [W/(m*K)]
21 lambda_st=48;        % thermal conductivity of steel [W/(m*K)]
22 T_u=293.15;          % ambient temperature [K]
23 A_o=1;               % shell surface ratio without PCM modules
24 % geometric parameters
25 l=2.25;              % length of storage vessel [m]
  
```

```

26 d=0.711; % inner diameter of storage vessel [m]
27 s=0.0125; % wall thickness of storage vessel [m]
28 s_iso=0.2; % thickness of isolation [m]
29 s_o=0.003; % thickness of outer plate [m]
30 % initial values
31 f_start=0.6; % start for the filling level [1]
32 p_start=10e5; % start for the pressure inside the storage [Pa]
33 Q_punkt_pcm=[0;0;0]; % heat flow from RSS to PCM modules
34 % (zero for mere RSS)
35 % load coefficients for calculating the differential equation system
36 load('Koeffizienten28012016.mat');
37 % inlet steam mass flow
38 m_punkt_ein_max=9; % maximum inlet steam mass flow [kg/s]
39 cm_ein=5e-5; % inlet mass flow geometric coefficient [1]
40 T_ein=227+273.15; % temperature of the inlet steam mass flow [K]
41 % outlet steam mass flow
42 m_punkt_aus_max=7; % maximum outlet steam mass flow [kg/s]
43 cm_aus=cm_ein; % outlet mass flow geometric coefficient [1]
44 % generating of input vectors
45 n_p=4; % number of distinct input pressures
46 % generating step sequence matrix
47 T = zeros(t_ende,n_p);
48 idx_set = 1:(t_ende/n_p);
49 for jj = 1:n_p
50     T(idx_set,jj) = 1;
51     idx_set = idx_set+(t_ende/n_p);
52 end
53 gamma_0 = [20,20,10,10]; % distinct input pressures
54 p_ein_gew = T*gamma_0'; % input pressure vector
55 cm_ein_vec = T*[1;1;1;1]; % vector for inlet mass flow nozzle
56 % calculation of specific enthalpy with CoolProp
57 h_ein(1) = py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',...
58     p_ein(1)*1e+5,'Water');
59 h_ein(2) = py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',...
60     p_ein(2)*1e+5,'Water');
61 h_ein(3) = py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',...
62     p_ein(3)*1e+5,'Water');
63 h_ein(4) = py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',...
64     p_ein(4)*1e+5,'Water');
65 h_ein_gew = T*h_ein'; % specific enthalpy of inlet mass flow over
66 % time
67 %% optimization
68 % objective function
69 my_obj = @(gamma) eval_obj_RSS(gamma,T,T_ein,dt,Q_punkt_pcm,A_o,d,l,s,
70     s_iso,s_o,alpha_i,alpha_a,lambda_iso,lambda_st,m_punkt_ein_max,
71     m_punkt_aus_max,cm_ein,cm_ein_vec,cm_aus,cm_aus_vec,p_aus_gew,p_start,
72     f_start,T_u,p_min,p_max,f_min,f_max,t_start,t_ende,dKT,dKhv1,dKhv2,
73     dKhv3,dKhv4,dKhv5,dKhv6,dKhv7,dKhv8,dKhv9,dKh11,dKh12,dKh13,dKh14,
74     dKh15,dKh16,dKh17,dKh18,dKh19,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,
75     dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,dKrhov9,dKrhov11,dKrhov12,dKrhov13,dKrhov14,
76     dKrhov15,dKrhov16,dKrhov17,dKrhov18,dKrhov19,KT,Khv1,Khv2,Khv3,Khv4,Khv5,
77     Khv6,Khv7,Khv8,Khv9,Kh11,Kh12,Kh13,Kh14,Kh15,Kh16,Kh17,Kh18,Kh19,
78     Krhov1,Krhov2,Krhov3,Krhov4,Krhov5,Krhov6,Krhov7,Krhov8,Krhov9,Krhov11,
79     Krhov12,Krhov13,Krhov14,Krhov15,Krhov16,Krhov17,Krhov18,Krhov19,'mineig');
80 % amplitude constraints for gamma
81 ub = p_max*e-5 * ones(1,4); % upper bound
82 lb = p_min*e-5 * ones(1,4); % lower bound
83 solver = 0; % choose optimization solver: "0" = fmincon
84 % "1" = ga
85 if solver == 1
86     my_opts = optimoptions('ga','PlotFcn','gaplotbestf',...
87         'UseParallel',true,'MaxGenerations',100);
88     [gamma,fval,exitflag,output] = ga(my_obj,4,[],[],[],[],...
89         [],lb,ub,[],my_opts);
90 else
91     my_opts = optimoptions('fmincon','Display','iter');
92     [gamma,fval,exitflag,output] = fmincon(my_obj, gamma_0, [],...
93         [],[], [], lb,ub,[],my_opts);

```

83 end

Listing A.2: Code of OED objective evaluation function eval_obj_RSS

```

1 %% objective evaluation RSS
2 % Author: Carlotta Tubeuf
3 % Last modified: 28.02.2020
4 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
5 function FIM_obj = eval_obj_RSS(gamma_vec, T_basis, T_ein, dt, Q_punkt_pcm,
  A_o, d, l, s, s_iso, s_o, alpha_i, alpha_a, lambda_iso, lambda_st,
  m_punkt_ein_max, m_punkt_aus_max, cm_ein, cm_ein_vec, cm_aus, cm_aus_vec,
  p_aus_gew, p_start, f_start, T_u, p_min, p_max, f_min, f_max, t_start, t_ende,
  dKT, dKhv1, dKhv2, dKhv3, dKhv4, dKhv5, dKhv6, dKhv7, dKhv8, dKhv9, dKh11, dKh12,
  dKh13, dKh14, dKh15, dKh16, dKh17, dKh18, dKh19, dKrhov1, dKrhov2, dKrhov3,
  dKrhov4, dKrhov5, dKrhov6, dKrhov7, dKrhov8, dKrhov9, dKrhov11, dKrhov12,
  dKrhov13, dKrhov14, dKrhov15, dKrhov16, dKrhov17, dKrhov18, dKrhov19, KT, Khv1, Khv2,
  Khv3, Khv4, Khv5, Khv6, Khv7, Khv8, Khv9, Kh11, Kh12, Kh13, Kh14, Kh15, Kh16, Kh17,
  Kh18, Kh19, Krhov1, Krhov2, Krhov3, Krhov4, Krhov5, Krhov6, Krhov7, Krhov8,
  Krhov9, Krhov11, Krhov12, Krhov13, Krhov14, Krhov15, Krhov16, Krhov17, Krhov18, Krhov19,
  str_measure)
6 p_ein_gew = T_basis * gamma_vec'; % calculate pressure vector
7 h_ein(1)=py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',...
8     gamma_vec(1)*1e+5,'Water');
9 h_ein(2)=py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',...
10    gamma_vec(2)*1e+5,'Water');
11 h_ein(3)=py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',...
12    gamma_vec(3)*1e+5,'Water');
13 h_ein(4)=py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',...
14    gamma_vec(4)*1e+5,'Water');
15 h_ein_gew=T_basis*h_ein'; % calculate specific enthalpy vector
16 % call sensitivity analysis
17 [dYdTheta,penalty] = eval_param_RSS(dt, Q_punkt_pcm, A_o, d, l, s, s_iso, s_o,
  alpha_i, alpha_a, lambda_iso, lambda_st, h_ein_gew, m_punkt_ein_max,
  m_punkt_aus_max, cm_ein, cm_ein_vec, cm_aus, cm_aus_vec, p_ein_gew,
  p_aus_gew, p_start, f_start, T_u, p_min, p_max, f_min, f_max, t_start, t_ende,
  dKT, dKhv1, dKhv2, dKhv3, dKhv4, dKhv5, dKhv6, dKhv7, dKhv8, dKhv9, dKh11, dKh12,
  dKh13, dKh14, dKh15, dKh16, dKh17, dKh18, dKh19, dKrhov1, dKrhov2, dKrhov3,
  dKrhov4, dKrhov5, dKrhov6, dKrhov7, dKrhov8, dKrhov9, dKrhov11, dKrhov12,
  dKrhov13, dKrhov14, dKrhov15, dKrhov16, dKrhov17, dKrhov18, dKrhov19, KT, Khv1, Khv2,
  Khv3, Khv4, Khv5, Khv6, Khv7, Khv8, Khv9, Kh11, Kh12, Kh13, Kh14, Kh15, Kh16, Kh17,
  Kh18, Kh19, Krhov1, Krhov2, Krhov3, Krhov4, Krhov5, Krhov6, Krhov7, Krhov8,
  Krhov9, Krhov11, Krhov12, Krhov13, Krhov14, Krhov15, Krhov16, Krhov17, Krhov18, Krhov19)
18 % add penalty if optimizer goes into thermodynamically infeasible
  direction
19 if penalty >0
20     FIM_obj=penalty;
21     return
22 end
23 % calculate Fisher Information Matrix
24 FIM = dYdTheta' * dYdTheta;
25 % calculate optimality criterion value
26 switch (str_measure)
27     case 'det'
28         FIM_obj = -det(FIM);
29     case 'trace'
30         FIM_obj = -trace(FIM);
31     case 'mineig'
32         FIM_obj = -min(eig(FIM));
33 end

```

Listing A.3: Code of parameter sensitivity function eval_param_RSS

```

1 %% sensitivity analysis RSS
2 % Author: Carlotta Tubeuf
3 % Last modified: 28.02.2020

```

```

4 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
5 function [dYdTheta,penalty] = eval_param_RSS(dt,Q_punkt_pcm,A_o,d,l,s,
    s_iso,s_o,alpha_i,alpha_a,lambda_iso,lambda_st,h_e,m_punkt_ein_max,
    m_punkt_aus_max,cm_ein,cm_ein_vec,cm_aus,cm_aus_vec,p_ein_gew,
    p_aus_gew,p_start,f_start,T_u,p_min,p_max,f_min,f_max,t_start,t_ende,
    dKT,dKhv1,dKhv2,dKhv3,dKhv4,dKhv5,dKhv6,dKhv7,dKhv8,dKhv9,dKhl1,dKhl2,
    dKhl3,dKhl4,dKhl5,dKhl6,dKhl7,dKhl8,dKhl9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,
    dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,dKrhov9,dKrhov11,dKrhov12,
    dKrhov13,dKrhov14,dKrhov15,dKrhov16,dKrhov17,dKrhov18,dKrhov19,KT,Khv1,Khv2,
    Khv3,Khv4,Khv5,Khv6,Khv7,Khv8,Khv9,Khl1,Khl2,Khl3,Khl4,Khl5,Khl6,Khl7,
    Khl8,Khl9,Krhov1,Krhov2,Krhov3,Krhov4,Krhov5,Krhov6,Krhov7,Krhov8,
    Krhov9,Krhov11,Krhov12,Krhov13,Krhov14,Krhov15,Krhov16,Krhov17,Krhov18,Krhov19)
6 %% initialize parameters
7 n_theta = 3; % number of parameters
8 k0 = pi/((1/(alpha_i*d))+((1/(2*lambda_st))*log((d+(2*s))/d))+((1/(2*
    lambda_iso))*log((d+(2*s)+(2*s_iso))/(d+2*s)))+(1/(2*lambda_st))*log
    ((d+(2*s)+(2*s_iso)+2*s_o)/(d+2*s+2*s_iso)))+(1/(alpha_a*(d+(2*s)+2*
    s_iso+2*s_o))))); % heat transfer coefficient [W/(mK)]
9 V0 = ((d^2*pi)/4)*1; % volume of the storage vessel [m^3]
10 cm_ein0=cm_ein; % inlet mass flow geometric constant [1]
11 % calculate nominal state variables
12 [t_sim,Y,penalty] = Ruthsspeicher(dt,Q_punkt_pcm,A_o,V0,l,k0,h_ein_gew,
    m_punkt_ein_max,m_punkt_aus_max,cm_ein0,cm_ein_vec,cm_aus,cm_aus_vec,
    p_ein_gew_det,p_aus_gew,p_start,f_start,T_u,p_min,p_max,f_min,f_max,
    t_start,t_ende,dKT,dKhv1,dKhv2,dKhv3,dKhv4,dKhv5,dKhv6,dKhv7,dKhv8,
    dKhv9,dKhl1,dKhl2,dKhl3,dKhl4,dKhl5,dKhl6,dKhl7,dKhl8,dKhl9,dKrhov1,
    dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,dKrhov9,
    dKrhov11,dKrhov12,dKrhov13,dKrhov14,dKrhov15,dKrhov16,dKrhov17,dKrhov18,
    dKrhov19,KT,Khv1,Khv2,Khv3,Khv4,Khv5,Khv6,Khv7,Khv8,Khv9,Khl1,Khl2,Khl3,
    Khl4,Khl5,Khl6,Khl7,Khl8,Khl9,Krhov1,Krhov2,Krhov3,Krhov4,Krhov5,
    Krhov6,Krhov7,Krhov8,Krhov9,Krhov11,Krhov12,Krhov13,Krhov14,Krhov15,
    Krhov16,Krhov17,Krhov18,Krhov19);
13 % initialize sensitivity matrix
14 dYdTheta = zeros(2*length(t_sim),n_theta);
15 if penalty > 0
16     return
17 end
18 %% determine k derivative
19 dk = k0/100;
20 k = k0 + dk;
21 V = V0;
22 cm_ein=cm_ein0;
23 [~,Y_perturbed1] = Ruthsspeicher(dt,Q_punkt_pcm,A_o,V,l,k,h_ein_gew,
    m_punkt_ein_max,m_punkt_aus_max,cm_ein,cm_ein_vec,cm_aus,cm_aus_vec,
    p_ein_gew_det,p_aus_gew,p_start,f_start,T_u,p_min,p_max,f_min,f_max,
    t_start,t_ende,dKT,dKhv1,dKhv2,dKhv3,dKhv4,dKhv5,dKhv6,dKhv7,dKhv8,
    dKhv9,dKhl1,dKhl2,dKhl3,dKhl4,dKhl5,dKhl6,dKhl7,dKhl8,dKhl9,dKrhov1,
    dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,dKrhov9,
    dKrhov11,dKrhov12,dKrhov13,dKrhov14,dKrhov15,dKrhov16,dKrhov17,dKrhov18,
    dKrhov19,KT,Khv1,Khv2,Khv3,Khv4,Khv5,Khv6,Khv7,Khv8,Khv9,Khl1,Khl2,Khl3,
    Khl4,Khl5,Khl6,Khl7,Khl8,Khl9,Krhov1,Krhov2,Krhov3,Krhov4,Krhov5,
    Krhov6,Krhov7,Krhov8,Krhov9,Krhov11,Krhov12,Krhov13,Krhov14,Krhov15,
    Krhov16,Krhov17,Krhov18,Krhov19);
24 dYdTheta(:,1) = (Y_perturbed1-Y)./dk;
25 %% determine V derivative
26 dV = V0/100;
27 k = k0;
28 V = V0 + dV;
29 cm_ein=cm_ein0;
30 [~,Y_perturbed2] = Ruthsspeicher(dt,Q_punkt_pcm,A_o,V,l,k,h_ein_gew,
    m_punkt_ein_max,m_punkt_aus_max,cm_ein,cm_ein_vec,cm_aus,cm_aus_vec,
    p_ein_gew_det,p_aus_gew,p_start,f_start,T_u,p_min,p_max,f_min,f_max,
    t_start,t_ende,dKT,dKhv1,dKhv2,dKhv3,dKhv4,dKhv5,dKhv6,dKhv7,dKhv8,
    dKhv9,dKhl1,dKhl2,dKhl3,dKhl4,dKhl5,dKhl6,dKhl7,dKhl8,dKhl9,dKrhov1,
    dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,dKrhov9,
    dKrhov11,dKrhov12,dKrhov13,dKrhov14,dKrhov15,dKrhov16,dKrhov17,dKrhov18,
    dKrhov19,KT,Khv1,Khv2,Khv3,Khv4,Khv5,Khv6,Khv7,Khv8,Khv9,Khl1,Khl2,Khl3,
    Khl4,Khl5,Khl6,Khl7,Khl8,Khl9,Krhov1,Krhov2,Krhov3,Krhov4,Krhov5,

```

```

    Krhov6, Krhov7, Krhov8, Krhov9, Krhol1, Krhol2, Krhol3, Krhol4, Krhol5, Krhol6,
    Krhol7, Krhol8, Krhol9);
31 dYdTheta(:,2) = (Y_perturbed2-Y)./dV;
32 %% determine cm_ein derivative
33 dcm_ein = cm_ein0/100;
34 k = k0;
35 V = V0;
36 cm_ein=cm_ein0 + dcm_ein;
37 [~,Y_perturbed3] = Ruthsspeicher(dt,Q_punkt_pcm,A_o,V,l,k,h_ein_gew,
    m_punkt_ein_max,m_punkt_aus_max,cm_ein,cm_ein_vec,cm_aus,cm_aus_vec,
    p_ein_gew_det,p_aus_gew,p_start,f_start,T_u,p_min,p_max,f_min,f_max,
    t_start,t_ende,dKT,dKhv1,dKhv2,dKhv3,dKhv4,dKhv5,dKhv6,dKhv7,dKhv8,
    dKhv9,dKh11,dKh12,dKh13,dKh14,dKh15,dKh16,dKh17,dKh18,dKh19,dKrhov1,
    dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,dKrhov9,
    dKrhoh1,dKrhoh2,dKrhoh3,dKrhoh4,dKrhoh5,dKrhoh6,dKrhoh7,dKrhoh8,
    dKrhoh9,KT,Khv1,Khv2,Khv3,Khv4,Khv5,Khv6,Khv7,Khv8,Khv9,Kh11,Kh12,Kh13,
    Kh14,Kh15,Kh16,Kh17,Kh18,Kh19,Krhov1,Krhov2,Krhov3,Krhov4,Krhov5,
    Krhov6,Krhov7,Krhov8,Krhov9,Krhol1,Krhol2,Krhol3,Krhol4,Krhol5,Krhol6,
    Krhol7,Krhol8,Krhol9);
38 dYdTheta(:,3) = (Y_perturbed3-Y)./dcm_ein;

```

Listing A.4: Code of RSS main simulation function Ruthsspeicher

```

1 %% RSS calculation
2 % Author: Dominik Pernsteiner, Alexander Schirrer
3 % Last modified: 28.02.2020 by Carlotta Tubeuf
4 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
5 function [m,h,T,f,p,t_sim,Yn,m_p_ein,m_p_aus,penalty]=Ruthsspeicher(dt,
    Q_punkt_pcm,A_o,V,l,k,h_e,m_punkt_ein_max,m_punkt_aus_max,cm_ein,
    cm_ein_vec,cm_aus,cm_aus_vec,p_ein_gew,p_aus_gew,p_start,f_start,T_u,
    p_min,p_max,f_min,f_max,t_start,t_ende,dKT,dKhv1,dKhv2,dKhv3,dKhv4,
    dKhv5,dKhv6,dKhv7,dKhv8,dKhv9,dKh11,dKh12,dKh13,dKh14,dKh15,dKh16,
    dKh17,dKh18,dKh19,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,
    dKrhov7,dKrhov8,dKrhov9,dKrhoh1,dKrhoh2,dKrhoh3,dKrhoh4,dKrhoh5,
    dKrhoh6,dKrhoh7,dKrhoh8,dKrhoh9,KT,Khv1,Khv2,Khv3,Khv4,Khv5,Khv6,Khv7,
    Khv8,Khv9,Kh11,Kh12,Kh13,Kh14,Kh15,Kh16,Kh17,Kh18,Kh19,Krhov1,Krhov2,
    Krhov3,Krhov4,Krhov5,Krhov6,Krhov7,Krhov8,Krhov9,Krhol1,Krhol2,Krhol3,
    Krhol4,Krhol5,Krhol6,Krhol7,Krhol8,Krhol9,t_beladen_start,
    t_beladen_ende,t_entladen_start,t_entladen_ende)
6 penalty=0;
7 % Calculation of starting values
8 [Y0,YP0,penalty]=Startwerte(0,f_start,p_start,V,T_u,k,l,p_ein_gew(1),
    p_aus_gew(1),cm_ein,cm_ein_vec(1),cm_aus,cm_aus_vec(1),h_e(1),dKT,
    dKhv1,dKhv2,dKhv3,dKhv4,dKhv5,dKhv6,dKhv7,dKhv8,dKhv9,dKh11,dKh12,
    dKh13,dKh14,dKh15,dKh16,dKh17,dKh18,dKh19,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,
    dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,dKrhov9,dKrhoh1,dKrhoh2,
    dKrhoh3,dKrhoh4,dKrhoh5,dKrhoh6,dKrhoh7,dKrhoh8,dKrhoh9,KT,Khv1,Khv2,
    Khv3,Khv4,Khv5,Khv6,Khv7,Khv8,Khv9,Kh11,Kh12,Kh13,Kh14,Kh15,Kh16,Kh17,
    Kh18,Kh19,Krhov1,Krhov2,Krhov3,Krhov4,Krhov5,Krhov6,Krhov7,Krhov8,
    Krhov9,Krhol1,Krhol2,Krhol3,Krhol4,Krhol5,Krhol6,Krhol7,Krhol8,Krhol9,
    A_o,Q_punkt_pcm); %Berechnung der Startwerte
9 if penalty>0
10     m=[];
11     h=[];
12     T=[];
13     f=[];
14     p=[];
15     t_sim=[];
16     Yn=[];
17     m_p_ein=[];
18     m_p_aus=[];
19     return
20 end
21 u=false;
22 for i=1:t_ende-1;
23     t_span=[i-1 i];
24     % check which coefficients to use for polynomials according to the

```

```

25     % pressure inside the storage
26     while u==false;
27         if p_start<=4500;
28             dKhv=dKhv1;
29             dKhl=dKhl1;
30             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
31             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
32             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
33             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
34             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
35             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
36             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
37             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
38             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
39             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
40             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
41             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
42             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
43             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
44             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
45             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
46             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
47             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
48             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
49             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
50             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
51             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
52             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
53             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
54             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
55             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
56             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
57             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
58             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
59             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
60             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
61             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
62             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
63             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
64             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
65             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
66             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
67             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
68             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
69             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
70             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
71             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
72             dKrhov=dKrhov1;
73         end
74
75     F=@(t,Y,YP)Differentialgleichungssystem(t,Y,YP,p_ein_gew(i),
76         p_aus_gew(i),cm_ein,cm_ein_vec(i),cm_aus,cm_aus_vec(i),h_e(i),
77         V,k,l,dKT,dKhv,dKhl,dKrhov,dKrhov,A_o, Q_punkt_pcm);
78     % solve differential equation
79     sol=ode15i(F,t_span,Y0,YP0);
80     t=sol.x';
81     [Y,YP]=deval(sol,t);
82     YP=YP';
83     n=length(t);
84     % filling level
85     f_test1=(1-((Y(1,7)/Y(1,8))*Y(1,10)));
86     f_test=(1-((Y(n,7)/Y(n,8))*Y(n,10)));
87
88     % change between charging and discharging of the storage
89     if i==1
90         if (p_ein_gew(1)*1e+5)-Y(1,2)<=0
91             cm_ein_vec(1)=0;
92             cm_aus_vec(1)=1;
93         elseif Y(1,2)-(p_ein_gew(1)*1e+5)<=0

```

```

91         cm_ein_vec(1)=1;
92         cm_aus_vec(1)=0;
93     end
94 else
95     if (p_ein_gew(i)*1e+5)-Y(n,2)<=0
96         cm_ein_vec(i)=0;
97         cm_aus_vec(i)=1;
98     elseif (Y(n,2)-p_ein_gew(i)*1e+5)<=0
99         cm_ein_vec(i)=1;
100        cm_aus_vec(i)=0;
101    end
102 end
103
104 % check if maximum or minimum pressure or filling level is
105 % reached
106 % if yes, the mass flow is set 0 and the system of differential
107 % equations is calculated again for this time step
108 if (Y(n,2)>=p_max || f_test>=f_max) && cm_ein_vec(i)>0
109     cm_ein_vec(i)=0;
110     m_pe(i)=cm_ein*cm_ein_vec(i)*sqrt((p_ein_gew(i)*1e+5)-Y(n,2))
111     ;
112     m_pa(i)=cm_aus*cm_aus_vec(i)*sqrt(Y(n,2)-(p_ein_gew(i)*1e+5))
113     ;
114     R0=[0;0;0;0;0;0;(m_pe(i)-m_pa(i))/V;0;0;0;m_pe(i)-m_pa(i)];
115     [Y0,YP0]=decic(F,i-1,Y0,[1;1;1;1;1;1;1;1;1;1;1],R0
116     ,[0;0;0;0;0;0;0;0;0;0;0]);
117     disp('gewuenschte Dampfmasse konnte nicht gespeichert werden'
118     )
119     u=false;
120 elseif (Y(n,2)<=p_min || f_test<=f_min) && cm_aus_vec(i)>0
121     cm_aus_vec(i)=0;
122     m_pe(i)=cm_ein*cm_ein_vec(i)*sqrt((p_ein_gew(i)*1e+5)-Y(n,2))
123     ;
124     m_pa(i)=cm_aus*cm_aus_vec(i)*sqrt(Y(n,2)-(p_ein_gew(i)*1e+5))
125     ;
126     R0=[0;0;0;0;0;0;(m_pe(i)-m_pa(i))/V;0;0;0;m_pe(i)-m_pa(i)];
127     [Y0,YP0]=decic(F,i-1,Y0,[1;1;1;1;1;1;1;1;1;1;1],R0
128     ,[0;0;0;0;0;0;0;0;0;0;0]);
129     disp('gewuenschte Dampfmasse konnte nicht gespeichert werden'
130     )
131     u=false;
132 else
133     % if no limit is reached, the actual values are the next
134     % starting
135     % values
136     m_pe(i)=cm_ein*cm_ein_vec(i)*sqrt((p_ein_gew(i)*1e+5)-Y(n,2))
137     ;
138     m_pa(i)=cm_aus*cm_aus_vec(i)*sqrt(Y(n,2)-(p_ein_gew(i)*1e+5))
139     ;
140     u=true;
141     [Y0,YP0]=deval(sol,i);
142 end
143 end
144 u=false;
145 % saving of current values
146 if i==1;
147     t_sim=[t(1);t(n)];
148     h=[Y(1,1);Y(n,1)];
149     p=[Y(1,2);Y(n,2)];
150     h_v=[Y(1,3);Y(n,3)];
151     h_l=[Y(1,4);Y(n,4)];
152     Q_p=[Y(1,5);Y(n,5)];
153     T=[Y(1,6);Y(n,6)];
154     rho=[Y(1,7);Y(n,7)];
155     rho_v=[Y(1,8);Y(n,8)];
156     rho_l=[Y(1,9);Y(n,9)];
157     x=[Y(1,10);Y(n,10)];
158     m=[Y(1,11);Y(n,11)];

```

```

147     f=[f_test1;f_test];
148     p_ein=p_ein_gew(1);
149     p_aus=p_aus_gew(1);
150     m_p_ein=[cm_ein*cm_ein_vec(i)*sqrt(p_ein_gew(i)*1e+5-Y(1,2));
             cm_ein*cm_ein_vec(i)*sqrt((p_ein_gew(i)*1e+5)-Y(n,2))];
151     m_p_aus=[cm_aus*cm_aus_vec(i)*sqrt(Y(1,2)-(p_ein_gew(i)*1e+5));
             cm_aus*cm_aus_vec(i)*sqrt(Y(n,2)-(p_ein_gew(i)*1e+5))];
152     Yp=[Y(1,2)*1e-05;Y(n,2)*1e-05];
153     Yt=[Y(1,6)-273.15;Y(n,6)-273.15];
154     Yn=[Yp;Yt];
155     else
156         t_sim=[t_sim;t(n)];
157         h=[h;Y(n,1)];
158         p=[p;Y(n,2)];
159         h_v=[h_v;Y(n,3)];
160         h_l=[h_l;Y(n,4)];
161         Q_p=[Q_p;Y(n,5)];
162         T=[T;Y(n,6)];
163         rho=[rho;Y(n,7)];
164         rho_v=[rho_v;Y(n,8)];
165         rho_l=[rho_l;Y(n,9)];
166         x=[x;Y(n,10)];
167         m=[m;Y(n,11)];
168         f=[f;f_test];
169         p_ein=[p_ein;p_ein_gew(i)];
170         p_aus=[p_aus;p_aus_gew(i)];
171         m_p_ein=[m_p_ein;cm_ein*cm_ein_vec(i)*sqrt((p_ein_gew(i)*1e+5)-Y(
             n,2))];
172         m_p_aus=[m_p_aus;cm_aus*cm_aus_vec(i)*sqrt(Y(n,2)-(p_ein_gew(i)*1
             e+5))];
173         Yp=[Yp;Y(n,2)*1e-05];
174         Yt=[Yt;Y(n,6)-273.15];
175         Yn=[Yp;Yt];
176     end
177 end

```

Listing A.5: Code of run file for the parameter estimation proof run_param_proof_RSS

```

1  %% parameter estimation proof RSS
2  % Author: Carlotta Tubeuf
3  % Last modified: 28.02.2020
4  %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
5  %% preprocessing OED RSS
6  % add open-source thermophysical property library CoolProp
7  addpath('.\CoolProp');
8  % general input data
9  f_max=0.95;           % maximum filling level [1]
10 f_min=0.05;          % minimum filling level [1]
11 p_max=23e5;          % maximum pressure inside the storage [Pa]
12 p_min=7e5;           % minimum pressure inside the storage [Pa]
13 t_start=0;           % simulation start [s]
14 t_ende=1*3600;       % simulation end [s]
15 dt=1;                % time step [s]
16 alpha_i=5000;        % heat transfer coefficient inside [W/(m^2*K)]
17                      % (condensing steam)
18 alpha_a=5;           % heat transfer coefficient outside [W/(m^2*K)]
19                      % (stationary air)
20 lambda_iso=0.062;    % thermal conductivity of isolation [W/(m*K)]
21 lambda_st=48;        % thermal conductivity of steel [W/(m*K)]
22 T_u=293.15;          % ambient temperature [K]
23 A_o=1;               % shell surface ratio without PCM modules
24 % geometric parameters
25 l=2.25;              % length of storage vessel [m]
26 d=0.711;             % inner diameter of storage vessel [m]
27 s=0.0125;           % wall thickness of storage vessel [m]
28 s_iso=0.2;           % thickness of isolation [m]
29 s_o=0.003;           % thickness of outer plate [m]

```

```

30 % initial values
31 f_start=0.6; % start for the filling level [1]
32 p_start=10e5; % start for the pressure inside the storage [Pa]
33 Q_punkt_pcm=[0;0;0]; % heat flow from RSS to PCM modules
34 % (zero for mere RSS)
35 % load coefficients for calculating the differential equation system
36 load('Koeffizienten28012016.mat');
37 % inlet steam mass flow
38 m_punkt_ein_max=9; % maximum inlet steam mass flow [kg/s]
39 cm_ein=5e-5; % inlet mass flow geometric coefficient [1]
40 T_ein=227+273.15; % temperature of the inlet steam mass flow [K]
41 % outlet steam mass flow
42 m_punkt_aus_max=7; % maximum outlet steam mass flow [kg/s]
43 cm_aus=cm_in; % outlet mass flow geometric coefficient [1]
44 % generating of input vectors
45 n_p=4; % number of distinct input pressures
46 % generating step sequence matrix
47 T = zeros(t_ende,n_p);
48 idx_set = 1:(t_ende/n_p);
49 for jj = 1:n_p
50 T(idx_set,jj) = 1;
51 idx_set = idx_set+(t_ende/n_p);
52 end
53
54 %% trivial input case
55 % load OED results
56 load('results/triv_rss.mat');
57 p_ein_triv=gamma;
58 p_ein_gew_triv=T*p_ein_triv';
59 cm_ein_vec=T*[1;1;1;1];
60 h_ein(1)=py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',p_ein_triv(1)*1e
+5,'Water');
61 h_ein(2)=py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',p_ein_triv(2)*1e
+5,'Water');
62 h_ein(3)=py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',p_ein_triv(3)*1e
+5,'Water');
63 h_ein(4)=py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',p_ein_triv(4)*1e
+5,'Water');
64 h_ein_gew=T*h_ein';
65 % calculate "measured" Y
66 [~,Y_tats_triv] = Ruthsspeicher(dt,Q_punkt_pcm,A_o,V,l,k,h_ein_gew,
m_punkt_ein_max,m_punkt_aus_max,cm_ein,cm_ein_vec,cm_aus,cm_aus_vec,
p_ein_gew_det,p_aus_gew,p_start,f_start,T_u,p_min,p_max,f_min,f_max,
t_start,t_ende,dKT,dKhv1,dKhv2,dKhv3,dKhv4,dKhv5,dKhv6,dKhv7,dKhv8,
dKhv9,dKh11,dKh12,dKh13,dKh14,dKh15,dKh16,dKh17,dKh18,dKh19,dKrhov1,
dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,dKrhov9,
dKrh11,dKrh12,dKrh13,dKrh14,dKrh15,dKrh16,dKrh17,dKrh18,
dKrh19,KT,Khv1,Khv2,Khv3,Khv4,Khv5,Khv6,Khv7,Khv8,Khv9,Kh11,Kh12,Kh13,
Kh14,Kh15,Kh16,Kh17,Kh18,Kh19,Krhov1,Krhov2,Krhov3,Krhov4,Krhov5,
Krhov6,Krhov7,Krhov8,Krhov9,Krh11,Krh12,Krh13,Krh14,Krh15,Krh16,
Krh17,Krh18,Krh19);
67 % rounding Y to integer values
68 Y_noise_triv=Y_tats_triv;
69 for i=1:length(Y_tats_triv)
70 Y_noise_triv(i)=round(Y_tats_triv(i));
71 end
72 % actual parameter values
73 param = [k;V;cm_ein];
74 % initial parameter values for the estimation
75 gamma_0=param*0.1;
76 % objective function
77 my_obj = @(gamma) eval_obj_proof_RSS(gamma,Y_noise_triv,dt,Q_punkt_pcm,
A_o,l,h_ein_gew,m_punkt_ein_max,m_punkt_aus_max,cm_ein,cm_ein_vec,
cm_aus,cm_aus_vec,p_ein_gew_triv,p_aus_gew,p_start,f_start,T_u,p_min,
p_max,f_min,f_max,t_start,t_ende,dKT,dKhv1,dKhv2,dKhv3,dKhv4,dKhv5,
dKhv6,dKhv7,dKhv8,dKhv9,dKh11,dKh12,dKh13,dKh14,dKh15,dKh16,dKh17,
dKh18,dKh19,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,
dKrhov8,dKrhov9,dKrh11,dKrh12,dKrh13,dKrh14,dKrh15,dKrh16,

```

```

    dKrh17,dKrh18,dKrh19,KT,Khv1,Khv2,Khv3,Khv4,Khv5,Khv6,Khv7,Khv8,
    Khv9,Kh11,Kh12,Kh13,Kh14,Kh15,Kh16,Kh17,Kh18,Kh19,Krhov1,Krhov2,Krhov3
    ,Krhov4,Krhov5,Krhov6,Krhov7,Krhov8,Krhov9,Krh11,Krh12,Krh13,Krh14
    ,Krh15,Krh16,Krh17,Krh18,Krh19);
78 my_opts = optimoptions('fmincon');
79 my_opts.Display = 'iter';
80 % lower and upper bounds
81 lb=param*0.01;
82 ub=param*10;
83 % call optimization
84 [gamma_triv,fval,exitflag,output] = fmincon(my_obj, gamma_0, [], [], [],
    [], lb,ub,[],my_opts);
85 % calculate estimated temperature curve
86 k=gamma_triv(1); V=gamma_triv(2); cm_ein=gamma_triv(3);
87 [~,~,~,~,~,Y_opt_triv] = Ruthspeicher(dt,Q_punkt_pcm,A_o,V,l,k,
    h_ein_gew,m_punkt_ein_max,m_punkt_aus_max,cm_ein,cm_ein_vec,cm_aus,
    cm_aus_vec,p_ein_gew_det,p_aus_gew,p_start,f_start,T_u,p_min,p_max,
    f_min,f_max,t_start,t_ende,dKT,dKhv1,dKhv2,dKhv3,dKhv4,dKhv5,dKhv6,
    dKhv7,dKhv8,dKhv9,dKh11,dKh12,dKh13,dKh14,dKh15,dKh16,dKh17,dKh18,
    dKh19,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
    dKrhov9,dKrh11,dKrh12,dKrh13,dKrh14,dKrh15,dKrh16,dKrh17,
    dKrh18,dKrh19,KT,Khv1,Khv2,Khv3,Khv4,Khv5,Khv6,Khv7,Khv8,Khv9,Kh11,
    Kh12,Kh13,Kh14,Kh15,Kh16,Kh17,Kh18,Kh19,Krhov1,Krhov2,Krhov3,Krhov4,
    Krhov5,Krhov6,Krhov7,Krhov8,Krhov9,Krh11,Krh12,Krh13,Krh14,Krh15,
    Krh16,Krh17,Krh18,Krh19);
88 k=param(1); V=param(2); cm_ein=param(3);
89
90 %% det-optimized input case
91 load('results/det_rss.mat');
92 p_ein_det=gamma;
93 p_ein_gew_det=T*p_ein_det';
94 cm_ein_vec=T*[1;1;1;1];
95 h_ein(1)=py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',p_ein_det(1)*1e
    +5,'Water');
96 h_ein(2)=py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',p_ein_det(2)*1e
    +5,'Water');
97 h_ein(3)=py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',p_ein_det(3)*1e
    +5,'Water');
98 h_ein(4)=py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',p_ein_det(4)*1e
    +5,'Water');
99 h_ein_gew=T*h_ein';
100
101 [~,~,~,~,~,Y_tats_det] = Ruthspeicher(dt,Q_punkt_pcm,A_o,V,l,k,h_e,
    m_punkt_ein_max,m_punkt_aus_max,cm_ein,cm_ein_vec,cm_aus,cm_aus_vec,
    p_ein_gew,p_aus_gew,p_start,f_start,T_u,p_min,p_max,f_min,f_max,
    t_start,t_ende,dKT,dKhv1,dKhv2,dKhv3,dKhv4,dKhv5,dKhv6,dKhv7,dKhv8,
    dKhv9,dKh11,dKh12,dKh13,dKh14,dKh15,dKh16,dKh17,dKh18,dKh19,dKrhov1,
    dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,dKrhov9,
    dKrh11,dKrh12,dKrh13,dKrh14,dKrh15,dKrh16,dKrh17,dKrh18,
    dKrh19,KT,Khv1,Khv2,Khv3,Khv4,Khv5,Khv6,Khv7,Khv8,Khv9,Kh11,Kh12,Kh13,
    Kh14,Kh15,Kh16,Kh17,Kh18,Kh19,Krhov1,Krhov2,Krhov3,Krhov4,Krhov5,
    Krhov6,Krhov7,Krhov8,Krhov9,Krh11,Krh12,Krh13,Krh14,Krh15,Krh16,
    Krh17,Krh18,Krh19);
102 Y_noise_det=Y_tats_det;
103 for i=1:7200
104     Y_noise_det(i)=round(Y_tats_det(i));
105 end
106 gamma_0=param*0.1;
107 my_obj = @(gamma) eval_obj_proof_RSS(gamma,Y_noise_det,dt,Q_punkt_pcm,A_o
    ,l,h_ein_gew,m_punkt_ein_max,m_punkt_aus_max,cm_ein,cm_ein_vec,cm_aus,
    cm_aus_vec,p_ein_gew_det,p_aus_gew,p_start,f_start,T_u,p_min,p_max,
    f_min,f_max,t_start,t_ende,dKT,dKhv1,dKhv2,dKhv3,dKhv4,dKhv5,dKhv6,
    dKhv7,dKhv8,dKhv9,dKh11,dKh12,dKh13,dKh14,dKh15,dKh16,dKh17,dKh18,
    dKh19,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
    dKrhov9,dKrh11,dKrh12,dKrh13,dKrh14,dKrh15,dKrh16,dKrh17,
    dKrh18,dKrh19,KT,Khv1,Khv2,Khv3,Khv4,Khv5,Khv6,Khv7,Khv8,Khv9,Kh11,
    Kh12,Kh13,Kh14,Kh15,Kh16,Kh17,Kh18,Kh19,Krhov1,Krhov2,Krhov3,Krhov4,
    Krhov5,Krhov6,Krhov7,Krhov8,Krhov9,Krh11,Krh12,Krh13,Krh14,Krh15,

```

```

108 Krhol6,Krhol7,Krhol8,Krhol9);
109 my_opts = optimoptions('fmincon');
110 my_opts.Display = 'iter';
111 lb=param*0.01;
112 ub=param*10;
113 [gamma_det,fval,exitflag,output] = fmincon(my_obj, gamma_0, [], [], [],
114 [], lb,ub, [],my_opts);
115 k=gamma_det(1); V=gamma_det(2); cm_ein=gamma_det(3);
116 [~,~,~,~,~,Y_opt_det] = Ruthsspeicher(dt,Q_punkt_pcm,A_o,V,l,k,
117 h_ein_gew,m_punkt_ein_max,m_punkt_aus_max,cm_ein,cm_ein_vec,cm_aus,
118 cm_aus_vec,p_ein_gew_det,p_aus_gew,p_start,f_start,T_u,p_min,p_max,
119 f_min,f_max,t_start,t_ende,dKT,dKhv1,dKhv2,dKhv3,dKhv4,dKhv5,dKhv6,
120 dKhv7,dKhv8,dKhv9,dKh11,dKh12,dKh13,dKh14,dKh15,dKh16,dKh17,dKh18,
121 dKh19,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
122 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
123 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
124 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
125 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
126 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
127 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
128 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
129 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
130 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
131 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
132 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
133 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
134 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
135 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
136 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
137 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
138 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
139 dKrhov9,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,

```

```

    [], lb,ub ,[],my_opts);
140 k=gamma_trace(1); V=gamma_trace(2); cm_ein=gamma_trace(3);
141 [~,~,~,~,~,Y_opt_trace] = Ruthsspeicher(dt,Q_punkt_pcm,A_o,V,l,k,
    h_ein_gew,m_punkt_ein_max,m_punkt_aus_max,cm_ein,cm_ein_vec,cm_aus,
    cm_aus_vec,p_ein_gew_trace,p_aus_gew,p_start,f_start,T_u,p_min,p_max,
    f_min,f_max,t_start,t_ende,dKT,dKhv1,dKhv2,dKhv3,dKhv4,dKhv5,dKhv6,
    dKhv7,dKhv8,dKhv9,dKh11,dKh12,dKh13,dKh14,dKh15,dKh16,dKh17,dKh18,
    dKh19,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
    dKrhov9,dKrhov11,dKrhov12,dKrhov13,dKrhov14,dKrhov15,dKrhov16,dKrhov17,
    dKrhov18,dKrhov19,KT,Khv1,Khv2,Khv3,Khv4,Khv5,Khv6,Khv7,Khv8,Khv9,Kh11,
    Kh12,Kh13,Kh14,Kh15,Kh16,Kh17,Kh18,Kh19,Krhov1,Krhov2,Krhov3,Krhov4,
    Krhov5,Krhov6,Krhov7,Krhov8,Krhov9,Krhov11,Krhov12,Krhov13,Krhov14,Krhov15,
    Krhov16,Krhov17,Krhov18,Krhov19);
142 k=param(1); V=param(2); cm_ein=param(3);
143
144 % mineig-optimized input case
145 load('results/mineig_rss.mat');
146 p_ein_mineig=gamma;
147 p_ein_gew_mineig=T*p_ein_mineig';
148 cm_ein_vec=T*[1;1;1;1];
149 h_ein(1)=py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',p_ein_mineig(1)*1
    e+5,'Water');
150 h_ein(2)=py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',p_ein_mineig(2)*1
    e+5,'Water');
151 h_ein(3)=py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',p_ein_mineig(3)*1
    e+5,'Water');
152 h_ein(4)=py.CoolProp.CoolProp.PropsSI('H','T',T_ein,'P',p_ein_mineig(4)*1
    e+5,'Water');
153 h_ein_gew=T*h_ein';
154
155 [~,~,~,~,~,Y_tats_mineig] = Ruthsspeicher(dt,Q_punkt_pcm,A_o,V,l,k,h_e,
    m_punkt_ein_max,m_punkt_aus_max,cm_ein,cm_ein_vec,cm_aus,cm_aus_vec,
    p_ein_gew,p_aus_gew,p_start,f_start,T_u,p_min,p_max,f_min,f_max,
    t_start,t_ende,dKT,dKhv1,dKhv2,dKhv3,dKhv4,dKhv5,dKhv6,dKhv7,dKhv8,
    dKhv9,dKh11,dKh12,dKh13,dKh14,dKh15,dKh16,dKh17,dKh18,dKh19,dKrhov1,
    dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,dKrhov9,
    dKrhov11,dKrhov12,dKrhov13,dKrhov14,dKrhov15,dKrhov16, dKrhov17,dKrhov18,
    dKrhov19,KT,Khv1,Khv2,Khv3,Khv4,Khv5,Khv6,Khv7,Khv8,Khv9,Kh11,Kh12,Kh13,
    Kh14,Kh15,Kh16,Kh17,Kh18,Kh19,Krhov1,Krhov2,Krhov3,Krhov4,Krhov5,
    Krhov6,Krhov7,Krhov8,Krhov9,Krhov11,Krhov12,Krhov13,Krhov14,Krhov15,Krhov16,
    Krhov17,Krhov18,Krhov19);
156 Y_noise_mineig=Y_tats_mineig;
157 for i=1:7200
158 Y_noise_mineig(i)=round(Y_tats_mineig(i));
159 end
160 gamma_0=param*0.1;
161 my_obj = @(gamma) eval_obj_proof_RSS(gamma,Y_noise_mineig,dt,Q_punkt_pcm,
    A_o,l,h_ein_gew,m_punkt_ein_max,m_punkt_aus_max,cm_ein,cm_ein_vec,
    cm_aus,cm_aus_vec,p_ein_gew_mineig,p_aus_gew,p_start,f_start,T_u,p_min,
    p_max,f_min,f_max,t_start,t_ende,dKT,dKhv1,dKhv2,dKhv3,dKhv4,dKhv5,
    dKhv6,dKhv7,dKhv8,dKhv9,dKh11,dKh12,dKh13,dKh14,dKh15,dKh16,dKh17,
    dKh18,dKh19,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,
    dKrhov8,dKrhov9,dKrhov11,dKrhov12,dKrhov13,dKrhov14,dKrhov15,dKrhov16,
    dKrhov17,dKrhov18,dKrhov19,KT,Khv1,Khv2,Khv3,Khv4,Khv5,Khv6,Khv7,Khv8,
    Khv9,Kh11,Kh12,Kh13,Kh14,Kh15,Kh16,Kh17,Kh18,Kh19,Krhov1,Krhov2,Krhov3,
    Krhov4,Krhov5,Krhov6,Krhov7,Krhov8,Krhov9,Krhov11,Krhov12,Krhov13,Krhov14,
    Krhov15,Krhov16,Krhov17,Krhov18,Krhov19);
162 my_opts = optimoptions('fmincon');
163 my_opts.Display = 'iter';
164 lb=param*0.01;
165 ub=param*10;
166 [gamma_mineig,fval,exitflag,output] = fmincon(my_obj, gamma_0, [], [],
    [], [], lb,ub ,[],my_opts);
167 k=gamma_mineig(1); V=gamma_mineig(2); cm_ein=gamma_mineig(3);
168 [~,~,~,~,~,Y_opt_mineig] = Ruthsspeicher(dt,Q_punkt_pcm,A_o,V,l,k,
    h_ein_gew,m_punkt_ein_max,m_punkt_aus_max,cm_ein,cm_ein_vec,cm_aus,
    cm_aus_vec,p_ein_gew_mineig,p_aus_gew,p_start,f_start,T_u,p_min,p_max,
    f_min,f_max,t_start,t_ende,dKT,dKhv1,dKhv2,dKhv3,dKhv4,dKhv5,dKhv6,

```

```

dKhv7,dKhv8,dKhv9,dKh11,dKh12,dKh13,dKh14,dKh15,dKh16,dKh17,dKh18,
dKh19,dKrhov1,dKrhov2,dKrhov3,dKrhov4,dKrhov5,dKrhov6,dKrhov7,dKrhov8,
dKrhov9,dKrhov11,dKrhov12,dKrhov13,dKrhov14,dKrhov15,dKrhov16,dKrhov17,
dKrhov18,dKrhov19,KT,Khv1,Khv2,Khv3,Khv4,Khv5,Khv6,Khv7,Khv8,Khv9,Kh11,
Kh12,Kh13,Kh14,Kh15,Kh16,Kh17,Kh18,Kh19,Krhov1,Krhov2,Krhov3,Krhov4,
Krhov5,Krhov6,Krhov7,Krhov8,Krhov9,Krhov11,Krhov12,Krhov13,Krhov14,Krhov15,
Krhov16,Krhov17,Krhov18,Krhov19);
169 k=param(1); V=param(2); cm_ein=param(3);

```

Listing A.6: Code of parameter estimation objective evaluation function eval_obj_proof_RSS

```

1 %% objective evaluation for parameter estimation RSS
2 % Author: Carlotta Tubeuf
3 % Last modified: 28.02.2020
4 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
5 function proof_obj = eval_obj_proof_RSS(gamma_vec, Y_measured, dt,
    Q_punkt_pcm, A_o, l, h_e, m_punkt_ein_max, m_punkt_aus_max, cm_ein,
    cm_ein_vec, cm_aus, cm_aus_vec, p_ein_gew, p_aus_gew, p_start, f_start, T_u,
    p_min, p_max, f_min, f_max, t_start, t_ende, dKT, dKhv1, dKhv2, dKhv3, dKhv4,
    dKhv5, dKhv6, dKhv7, dKhv8, dKhv9, dKh11, dKh12, dKh13, dKh14, dKh15, dKh16,
    dKh17, dKh18, dKh19, dKrhov1, dKrhov2, dKrhov3, dKrhov4, dKrhov5, dKrhov6,
    dKrhov7, dKrhov8, dKrhov9, dKrhov11, dKrhov12, dKrhov13, dKrhov14, dKrhov15,
    dKrhov16, dKrhov17, dKrhov18, dKrhov19, KT, Khv1, Khv2, Khv3, Khv4, Khv5, Khv6, Khv7,
    Khv8, Khv9, Kh11, Kh12, Kh13, Kh14, Kh15, Kh16, Kh17, Kh18, Kh19, Krhov1, Krhov2,
    Krhov3, Krhov4, Krhov5, Krhov6, Krhov7, Krhov8, Krhov9, Krhov11, Krhov12, Krhov13,
    Krhov14, Krhov15, Krhov16, Krhov17, Krhov18, Krhov19)
6 k=gamma_vec(1);
7 V=gamma_vec(2);
8 cm_ein=gamma_vec(3);
9 % call RSS computation
10 [~,~,~,~,~,~,Y,~,~,penalty] = Ruthsspeicher(dt, Q_punkt_pcm, A_o, V, l, k,
    h_ein_gew, m_punkt_ein_max, m_punkt_aus_max, cm_ein, cm_ein_vec, cm_aus,
    cm_aus_vec, p_ein_gew_det, p_aus_gew, p_start, f_start, T_u, p_min, p_max,
    f_min, f_max, t_start, t_ende, dKT, dKhv1, dKhv2, dKhv3, dKhv4, dKhv5, dKhv6,
    dKhv7, dKhv8, dKhv9, dKh11, dKh12, dKh13, dKh14, dKh15, dKh16, dKh17, dKh18,
    dKh19, dKrhov1, dKrhov2, dKrhov3, dKrhov4, dKrhov5, dKrhov6, dKrhov7, dKrhov8,
    dKrhov9, dKrhov11, dKrhov12, dKrhov13, dKrhov14, dKrhov15, dKrhov16, dKrhov17,
    dKrhov18, dKrhov19, KT, Khv1, Khv2, Khv3, Khv4, Khv5, Khv6, Khv7, Khv8, Khv9, Kh11,
    Kh12, Kh13, Kh14, Kh15, Kh16, Kh17, Kh18, Kh19, Krhov1, Krhov2, Krhov3, Krhov4,
    Krhov5, Krhov6, Krhov7, Krhov8, Krhov9, Krhov11, Krhov12, Krhov13, Krhov14, Krhov15,
    Krhov16, Krhov17, Krhov18, Krhov19);
11 % add penalty if optimizer goes into thermodynamically infeasible
    direction
12 if penalty > 0
13     proof_obj=penalty;
14     return
15 end
16 % calculate distance between measured and optimized temperature curve
17 proof_obj = norm(Y-Y_measured);
18 end

```

A.2 Optimal Experimental Design PCM

Listing A.7: Code of run file for the PCM OED model run_oed_PCM

```

1 %% OED PCM cell
2 % Author: Carlotta Tubeuf
3 % Last modified: 28.02.2020
4 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%

```

```

5 % call input parameters
6 [param] = input_me_geom_OED;
7 % generating of input vector
8 n_T=4; % number of distinct input temperatures
9 T = zeros(param.mesh.not,n_T); % generating step sequence matrix
10 idx_set = 1:(param.mesh.not/n_T);
11 for jj = 1:n_T
12     T(idx_set,jj) = 1;
13     idx_set = idx_set+(param.mesh.not/n_T);
14 end
15 gamma_0 = [210,210,180,180]; % initial input temperatures
16 %% optimization
17 % objective function
18 my_obj = @(gamma) eval_obj_PCM(gamma,param,'mineig');
19 % amplitude constraints for gamma
20 ub = 220 * ones(n_T,1); % upper bound
21 lb = 170 * ones(n_T,1); % lower bound
22 solver = 1; % choose optimization solver: "0" = fmincon
23 % "1" = ga
24 if solver == 1
25     my_opts = optimoptions('ga','PlotFcn','gaplotbestf',...
26         'UseParallel', true,'MaxGenerations',100);
27     [gamma,fval,exitflag,output] = ga(my_obj,4,[],[], [], [], ...
28         lb, ub,[],my_opts);
29 else
30     my_opts = optimoptions('fmincon','Display','iter');
31     [gamma,fval,exitflag,output] = fmincon(my_obj, gamma_0, [],[], ...
32         [], [], lb,ub ,[],my_opts);
33 end

```

Listing A.8: Code of test input parameter function input_me_geom_OED

```

1 %% Input Data File
2 % Author: Lukas Kasper
3 % Last modified: 28.02.2021 by Carlotta Tubeuf
4 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
5 function [param]=input_me_geom_OED
6 %% Save Name
7 % param.save.name = 'results_me_geom_test'; not used
8 %% simulate with convection
9 param.convection = 0; % (0 = off, 1 = on)
10 %% geometry specifications
11 % simplified geometry specifications
12 %param.geom.x_length_vec = [0.004 0.002 0.028 0.002 0.004];
13 %param.geom.y_length_vec = [0.002 0.008 0.002 0.008 0.002];
14 % actual geometry
15 param.geom.x_length_vec = [0.003 0.001 0.028 0.001 0.003];
16 param.geom.y_length_vec = [0.0005 0.007 0.001 0.007 0.0005];
17 % structure of simulated domain (left to right and top to bottom)
18 param.geom.mat_mtrx = flipud([4 3 3 3 4
19     4 1 1 3 4
20     4 3 3 3 4
21     4 3 1 1 4
22     4 3 3 3 4]);
23 % definition of material specifier
24 % must be in accordance with definition of material properties below
25 % pcm material specifier must be 1
26 param.geom.material = {1,'pcm'; % PCM material
27     2,'stl'; % steel
28     3,'alu'; % aluminium
29     4,'aus'}; % stainless austenitic steel
30 param.geom.x_length = sum(param.geom.x_length_vec); % length of PCM in x-
31     direction
32 param.geom.y_length = sum(param.geom.y_length_vec); % length of PCM in y-
33     direction
34 %% PCM cell at RSS

```

```

34 orientation = 87.5; % in degree
35 param.pcm.phi = pi/2 - orientation*pi/180;
36 % parametrization of where the PCM cell is mounted on the RSS
37 r_RSS = 0.711; % Ruths steam storage vessel radius
38 phi_cell_des = 10 /180*pi; % 10 degree opening area of the pcm
    segment
39 % location of the pcm segment
40 phi_mean = orientation*pi/180;
41 param.n_cells_on_RSShalf = floor(phi_cell_des *r_RSS / param.geom.
    y_length); % 32 cells on one modeled 30° sector on the RSS
42 dphi = phi_cell_des / 2; %param.geom.y_length * param.
    n_cells_on_RSShalf /2/r_RSS;
43 param.geom.phi_min = phi_mean-dphi;
44 param.geom.phi_max = phi_mean+dphi;
45 %% mesh specifications
46 nx = round(2000*param.geom.x_length); % minimum number of
    elements in x direction
47 ny = round(2000*param.geom.y_length); % minimum number of
    elements in y direction
48 param.mesh.nx = nx;
49 param.mesh.ny = ny;
50 param.mesh.nel = nx*ny; % number of elements
51 param.mesh.non = (nx+1)*(ny+1); % number of nodes
52 param.mesh.ngp = 2; % number of gauss integration points
53 param.geom.dx = param.geom.x_length/nx;
54 param.geom.dy = param.geom.y_length/ny;
55 %% timestep specifications
56 param.mesh.tt = 1*60*60; % Total time
57 param.mesh.d_t = 1; % Timestep
58 param.mesh.not = ceil(param.mesh.tt/param.mesh.d_t); % Nr of timesteps
59 %% initial and boundary condition
60 % T_init [°C] = initial temperature for element nodes
61 param.icbc.T_init=180*ones(param.mesh.non,1);
62 % T_in [°C] = input temperature dependent of time
63 % not used for OED, later specified in PCMsolver.m
64 param.icbc.Tin = @(t,y)(t<=param.mesh.not/2)*(220+delta_T)+...
65 (t>param.mesh.not/2)*(220-delta_T);
66 % alpha_in [W / m*K] = heat conductivity dependent of y and time
67 % not dependant for OED, because it is one of the parameters to be
68 % estimated
69 param.icbc.alpha_in = 700;
70 % T_out [°C] = output temperature dependent of time
71 param.icbc.Tout = @(t,y) 20; % output temperature [°C]
72 % alpha_out [W / m*K] = heat conductivity to environment
73 param.icbc.alpha_out = @(t,y) 0; % heat conductivity [W / m*K]
74 % constant heat flux
75 param.icbc.bc_type = 0; %(0 = Robin bc, 1 = Neumann bc)
76 % q_in [W / m] = heat flux to environment
77 param.icbc.qin = @(t,y) 0; % heat flux [W / m]
78 % q_out [W / m] = heat flux to environment
79 param.icbc.qout = @(t,y) 0; % heat flux [W / m]
80 % T_max [°C] = max. input-temperature from vessel
81 param.icbc.Tmax = 260;
82 % T_min [°C] = min. input-temperature from vessel
83 param.icbc.Tmin = 180;
84 %% material properties
85 % material properties of pcm
86 param.pcm.rho = 2317; % density [kg / m^3] (solid)
87 param.pcm.Tm = 192; % melting temperature [°C]
88 param.pcm.dTm = 0.4; % area of melting [°C]
89 param.pcm.c_s = 1350; % heat capacity of solid [J / kg*K]
90 param.pcm.c_l = 1720; % heat capacity of liquid [J / kg*K]
91 param.pcm.lh = 309*1000; % latent heat of PCM [J / kg]
92 param.pcm.k_s = 0.87; % heat conductivity, solid [W / m*K]
93 param.pcm.k_l = 0.575; % heat conductivity, liquid [W / m*K]
94 % convective properties of pcm
95 param.pcm.beta = 3.5e-4; % thermal expansion
96 param.pcm.T_0 = 160; % initial operating temperature

```

```

97 param.pcm.grav = 9.81; % standard gravity
98 param.pcm.mue = 5.8e-3; % viscosity
99 % material properties of aluminium
100 param.alu.rho = 2700; % density [kg / m^3] (solid)
101 param.alu.Tm = 1000; % melting temperature [°C]
102 param.alu.dTm = 0; % area of melting [°C]
103 param.alu.c_s = 910; % heat capacity of solid [J / kg*K]
104 param.alu.lh = 0; % latent heat of PCM [J / kg]
105 param.alu.k_s = 237; % heat conductivity, solid [W / m*K]
106 % material properties of steel
107 param.stl.rho = 7800; % density [kg / m^3] (solid)
108 param.stl.Tm = 1000; % melting temperature [°C]
109 param.stl.dTm = 0; % area of melting [°C]
110 param.stl.c_s = 540; % heat capacity of solid [J / kg*K]
111 param.stl.lh = 0; % latent heat of PCM [J / kg]
112 param.stl.k_s = 51; % heat conductivity, solid [W / m*K]
113 % material properties of air
114 param.air.rho = 1; % density [kg / m^3] (solid)
115 param.air.Tm = 1000; % melting temperature [°C]
116 param.air.dTm = 0; % area of melting [°C]
117 param.air.c_s = 1000; % heat capacity of solid [J / kg*K]
118 param.air.lh = 0; % latent heat of PCM [J / kg]
119 param.air.k_s = 0.024; % heat conductivity, solid [W / m*K]
120 % material properties of 'nichtrostender austenitischer Stahl 1.471
121 param.aus.rho = 8000; % density [kg / m^3] (solid)
122 param.aus.Tm = 1000; % melting temperature [°C]
123 param.aus.dTm = 0; % area of melting [°C]
124 param.aus.c_s = 500; % heat capacity of solid [J / kg*K]
125 param.aus.lh = 0; % latent heat of PCM [J / kg]
126 param.aus.k_s = 15; % heat conductivity, solid [W / m*K]
127 %% data recovery
128 % (0 = off, 1 = on)
129 param.save.intervall = 60; % timestep intervall in s, is used by co-
    simulation
130 % for T,U,V to be saved
131 param.save.make_snapshot = 0; % dump snapshots of data
132 param.save.snapshot_int = 5*60*ceil(1/param.mesh.d_t); % timestep
    intervall to make snapshots
133 %% display information for user
134 % (0 = off, 1 = on)
135 param.display.waitbar = 0; % show waitbar during run
136 % info: each waitbar update needs about 0.2 seconds computation time
137 param.display.update = 60; % minimum time between waitbar updates in
    seconds
138 param.display.Tplot = 0; % plot temperature distribution at the end
139 param.display.Vplot = 0; % plot velocity distribution at the end
140 param.display.matplot = 0; % plot visualisation of material in domain
141 %% Sensor location
142 param.sensor.dx=0.015;
143 param.sensor.dy=0.012;
144 param.sensor.nx=param.sensor.dx/param.geom.dx;
145 param.sensor.ny=param.sensor.dy/param.geom.dy;
146 param.sensor.non=(nx+1)*(param.sensor.ny)+param.sensor.nx;
147 % create sensor nodes ai and bi
148 % nx=param.mesh.nx;
149 % ny=param.mesh.ny;
150 % param.sensor.ai=round(nx/4)+(round(ny/4)*(nx+1));
151 % param.sensor.bi=(nx-round(nx/2))+((ny-round(ny/4))*(nx+1));

```

Listing A.9: Code of OED objective evaluation function eval_obj_PCM

```

1 %% objective evaluation PCM cell
2 % Author: Carlotta Tubeuf
3 % Last modified: 28.02.2020
4 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
5 function FIM_obj = eval_obj_PCM(gamma_vec, param, str_measure)

```

```

6 % call sensitivity analysis
7 [dYdTheta] = eval_param_PCM(param, gamma_vec);
8 % calculate Fisher Information Matrix
9 FIM = dYdTheta' * dYdTheta;
10 % calculate optimality criterion value
11 switch (str_measure)
12     case 'det'
13         FIM_obj = -det(FIM);
14     case 'trace'
15         FIM_obj = -trace(FIM);
16     case 'mineig'
17         FIM_obj = -min(eig(FIM));
18 end

```

Listing A.10: Code of parameter sensitivity function eval_param_PCM

```

1 %% sensitivity analysis PCM
2 % Author: Carlotta Tubeuf
3 % Last modified: 28.02.2020
4 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
5 function [dYdTheta_filtered] = eval_param_PCM(param, gamma_vec)
6 %% initialize parameters
7 n_theta=4; % number of parameters
8 k_l0=param.pcm.k_l; % heat conductivity, liquid [W / m*K]
9 k_s0=param.pcm.k_s; % heat conductivity, solid [W / m*K]
10 Tm_0=param.pcm.Tm; % melting temperature [°C]
11 dTm_0=param.pcm.dTm; % area of melting [°C]
12 alpha_0=param.icbc.alpha_in; % heat transfer parameter [W / m*K]
13 beta_0=param.pcm.beta; % thermal expansion [1/K]
14 mue_0=param.pcm.mue; % viscosity [N*s/m^2]
15 % calculate nominal state variables
16 [t, Y]=PCMsolver(param, gamma_vec);
17 % initialize sensitivity matrix
18 dYdTheta=zeros(param.mesh.not, n_theta);
19 % calculate transfer function
20 zeta = 0.05;
21 omega1 = 2*pi/100;
22 omega2 = 2*pi/120;
23 G = tf([1 2*omega1*zeta omega1^2], [1 2*omega1*1 omega1^2]) * ...
24     tf([1 2*omega2*zeta omega2^2], [1 2*omega2*1 omega2^2]) * ...
25     tf(2*omega2, [1 2*omega2])^2;
26 % initialize filtered sensitivity matrix
27 dYdTheta_filtered = zeros(param.mesh.not, n_theta);
28 %% determine k_l derivative
29 dk_l = k_l0/100;
30 param.pcm.k_l=k_l0+dk_l;
31 param.pcm.k_s=k_s0;
32 param.pcm.Tm=Tm_0;
33 param.pcm.dTm=dTm_0;
34 param.icbc.alpha_in=alpha_0;
35 [~, Yk_l]=PCMsolver(param, gamma_vec);
36 dYdTheta(:, 1)=(Yk_l-Y)./Y;
37 dYdTheta_filtered(1:param.mesh.not, 1) = lsim(G, dYdTheta(1:param.mesh.not
    , 1), t(1:param.mesh.not)'-t(1));
38 % dYdTheta_filtered(param.mesh.not+1:param.mesh.not*2, 1) = lsim(G,
    dYdTheta(param.mesh.not+1:param.mesh.not*2, 1), t(1:param.mesh.not)'-t
    (1));
39 %% determine k_s derivative
40 dk_s = k_s0/100;
41 param.pcm.k_l=k_l0;
42 param.pcm.k_s=k_s0+dk_s;
43 param.pcm.Tm=Tm_0;
44 param.pcm.dTm=dTm_0;
45 param.icbc.alpha_in=alpha_0;
46 % call PCM solver
47 [~, Yk_s]=PCMsolver(param, gamma_vec);
48 dYdTheta(:, 2)=(Yk_s-Y)./Y;

```

```

49 % filtering of sensitivity function
50 dYdTheta_filtered(1:param.mesh.not,2) = lsim(G,dYdTheta(1:param.mesh.not
,2),t(1:param.mesh.not)'-t(1));
51 % dYdTheta_filtered(param.mesh.not+1:param.mesh.not*2,1) = lsim(G,
dYdTheta(param.mesh.not+1:param.mesh.not*2,1),t(1:param.mesh.not)'-t
(1));
52 %% determine Tm derivative
53 dTm = Tm_0/100;
54 param.pcm.k_l=k_l0;
55 param.pcm.k_s=k_s0;
56 param.pcm.Tm=Tm_0+dTm;
57 param.pcm.dTm=dTm_0;
58 param.icbc.alpha_in=alpha_0;
59 [~,YTm]=PCMsolver(param,gamma_vec);
60 dYdTheta(:,3)=(YTm-Y)./dTm;
61 dYdTheta_filtered(1:param.mesh.not,3) = lsim(G,dYdTheta(1:param.mesh.not
,3),t(1:param.mesh.not)'-t(1));
62 % dYdTheta_filtered(param.mesh.not+1:param.mesh.not*2,3) = lsim(G,
dYdTheta(param.mesh.not+1:param.mesh.not*2,3),t(1:param.mesh.not)'-t
(1));
63 %% determine dTm derivative
64 % ddTm = dTm_0/100;
65 % param.pcm.k_l=k_l0;
66 % param.pcm.k_s=k_s0;
67 % param.pcm.Tm=Tm_0;
68 % param.pcm.dTm=dTm_0+ddTm;
69 % param.icbc.alpha_in=alpha_0;
70 % [~,YdTm]=PCMsolver(param,gamma_vec);
71 % dYdTheta(:,2)=(YdTm-Y)./ddTm;
72 % dYdTheta_filtered(1:param.mesh.not,2) = lsim(G,dYdTheta(1:param.mesh.
not,2),t(1:param.mesh.not)'-t(1));
73 % dYdTheta_filtered(param.mesh.not+1:param.mesh.not*2,2) = lsim(G,
dYdTheta(param.mesh.not+1:param.mesh.not*2,2),t(1:param.mesh.not)'-t
(1));
74 %% determine alpha_in derivate
75 dalpha=alpha_0/100;
76 param.pcm.k_l=k_l0;
77 param.pcm.k_s=k_s0;
78 param.pcm.Tm=Tm_0;
79 param.pcm.dTm=dTm_0;
80 param.icbc.alpha_in=alpha_0+dalpha;
81 [~,Yalpha]=PCMsolver(param,gamma_vec);
82 dYdTheta(:,4)=(Yalpha-Y)./Y;
83 dYdTheta_filtered(1:param.mesh.not,4) = lsim(G,dYdTheta(1:param.mesh.not
,4),t(1:param.mesh.not)'-t(1));
84 % dYdTheta_filtered(param.mesh.not+1:param.mesh.not*2,2) = lsim(G,
dYdTheta(param.mesh.not+1:param.mesh.not*2,2),t(1:param.mesh.not)'-t
(1));
85 %% determine beta derivate
86 % dbeta=beta_0/100;
87 % param.pcm.beta=beta_0+dbeta;
88 % param.pcm.mue=mue_0;
89 % [~,Ybeta]=PCMsolver(param,gamma_vec);
90 % dYdTheta(:,1)=(Ybeta-Y)./dbeta;
91 %% determine mue derivate
92 % dmue=mue_0/100;
93 % param.pcm.beta=beta_0;
94 % param.pcm.mue=mue_0+dmue;
95 % [~,Ymue]=PCMsolver(param,gamma_vec);
96 % dYdTheta(:,2)=(Ymue-Y)./dmue;

```

Listing A.11: Code of PCM main simulation function PCMsolver

```

1 %% PCM Solver
2 % Author:          Lukas Kasper
3 % Last modified:   06.11.2020 by Carlotta Tubeuf
4 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%

```

```

5 function [t_vec,T_save]=PCMsolver(param,gamma_vec)
6 strTimestamp = datestr(now(),30); tic; % get timestamp
7 % fprintf('Starting simulation / timestamp %s\n',strTimestamp);
8 %% preprocessing
9 % load input variables
10 % eval(input_data);
11 % additional input variables
12 non = param.mesh.non;
13 not = param.mesh.not;
14
15 % initialize waittime bar
16 if param.display.waitbar == 1
17     f = waitbar(0,'Fortschritt'); timearray = 0; up = 0;
18 end
19
20 % input temperature
21 param.icbc.Tin = @(t,y) (t<=param.mesh.not/4)*gamma_vec(1)+...
22     (param.mesh.not/4<t && t<=param.mesh.not/2)*gamma_vec
23     (2)+...
24     (param.mesh.not/2<t && t<=param.mesh.not*3/4)*
25     gamma_vec(3)+...
26     (t>param.mesh.not*3/4)*gamma_vec(4);
27
28 % mesh generation
29 [param] = mesh2d(param);
30 v2struct(param.geom);
31 v2struct(param.mesh);
32 v2struct(param.icbc);
33
34 % visualize material in domain
35 if param.display.matplot == 1
36     scatterbar3(center_coord(1,:)',center_coord(2,:)',...
37         elem_mat,x_length/max(nx,ny));
38 end
39
40 % initialize arrays for data saving
41 Tt = zeros(non,ceil(not/param.save.intervall));
42 s = 1;
43 if param.convection == 1
44     Ut = zeros(nx-1,ny,ceil(not/param.save.intervall));
45     Vt = zeros(nx,ny-1,ceil(not/param.save.intervall));
46 end
47
48 % initialize nodal temperature matrix
49 T_new = zeros(non,1);
50 T_old = T_init(:);
51 T_0 = zeros(not,1);
52
53 % initialize staggered grid velocity matrices
54 U_old = zeros(nx-1,ny);
55 V_old = zeros(nx,ny-1);
56 U_new = zeros(nx-1,ny);
57 V_new = zeros(nx,ny-1);
58
59 % add boundaries to the velocity matrices
60 Uwb = [zeros(1,ny); U_old(:, :) ; zeros(1,ny)]; % east and west
61     boundaries
62 Uwb = [-Uwb(:,1) Uwb -Uwb(:,end)]; % north and south
63     boundaries
64 Vwb = [zeros(nx,1) V_old(:, :) zeros(nx,1)]; % north and south
65     boundaries
66 Vwb = [-Vwb(1,:); Vwb ; -Vwb(end,:)]; % east and west
67     boundaries
68 Ue = avg(Uwb')';
69 Ve = avg(Vwb);
70
71 % initialize solid parts
72 elempcm = elem_mat(reshape(1:nel,nx,ny)) == 1;

```

```

67 T_ij = reshape(T_old(:),nx+1,ny+1); % staggered grid temperatures
68 Tl = param.pcm.Tm+param.pcm.dTm; % temperature of complete
    liquidification
69 %Tl = param.pcm.Tm-param.pcm.dTm; % temperature of partial
    liquidification
70 % disp('Convection starts above liquidus temp!');
71 % p_el = phase of element [0 = solid, 1 = liquid]
72 p_el = false(nx,ny);
73
74 % initialize heat flow and enthalpy arrays
75 Q_in = zeros(not,1);
76 Q_out = zeros(not,1);
77 H = zeros(not,1);
78 H_l = zeros(not,1);
79
80 %% FEM preprocessing
81 % calculate shape matrices
82 [gauss] = shape_mat(param);
83 % preprocess FEM data
84 [gauss] = FEM_preprocessor(T_old,gauss,param);
85
86 %% time stepping
87 idx = 1;
88 for t = 1:not
89     %%
90     % to update prescribed heat flux in each timestep
91     %{
92     if param.icbc.bc_type == 1
93         gauss.qin1 = @(a) param.icbc.qin(a,gauss.yl1); gauss.qin2 = @(a)
            param.icbc.qin(a,gauss.yl2);
94         gauss.qout1 = @(a) param.icbc.qout(a,gauss.yl1); gauss.qout2 = @(a)
            param.icbc.qout(a,gauss.yl2);
95     end
96     %}
97     %% FEM calculation
98     [C,K,R,Qin_e,Qout_e,H(t),H_l(t)] = ...
99         heat2Delem_new(t,T_old,Uwb,Vwb,p_el,gauss,param);
100
101     % heat flows and enthalpy
102     %%{
103     if t > 1
104         Q_in(t) = Q_in(t-1) + Qin_e; % input heat flow
105         Q_out(t) = Q_out(t-1) + Qout_e; % output heat flow
106     else
107         Q_in(t) = Qin_e; % input heat flow
108         Q_out(t) = Qout_e; % output heat flow
109     end
110     %}
111
112     %% solve equation for temperatures at t+1
113     T_new = solve_euler_back(T_old,C,K,R,param);
114
115     % refresh staggered grid temperatures
116     T_ij = reshape(T_new,nx+1,ny+1); % staggered grid temperatures
117     if param.convection == 1
118         p_el = min(min( T_ij(1:end-1,1:ny),T_ij(1:end-1,2:ny+1)),...
119                 min(T_ij(2:end,1:ny),T_ij(2:end,2:ny+1) ))>Tl...
120                 & elempcm;
121     end
122
123     %% solve velocities at t+1
124     if any(any(p_el)) == 1
125
126         %% operating temperature for boussinesq term
127         % mean temperature in liquid region
128         T_0(t) = mean(sum(T_new(IEN(:,reshape(p_el,[],1))==1)))/4);
129         % fixed temperature
130         %T_0(t) = 230;

```

```

131     param.pcm.T_0 = T_0(t);
132
133     %% solve navier stokes equations
134     [U_new,V_new] = solve_navierstokes(U_old,V_old,T_ij,p_el,param);
135
136     %% reset velocities in solid part
137     U_new = U_new.*(p_el(1:nx-1,:) & p_el(2:nx,:));
138     V_new = V_new.*(p_el(:,1:ny-1) & p_el(:,2:ny));
139
140     %% add boundary values to velocity matrices
141     % in domain phase boundary
142     U_new(:,1:end-1) = U_new(:,1:end-1)-U_new(:,2:end).*...
143         (p_el(1:end-1,2:end)==1 & p_el(1:end-1,2:end)~=p_el(1:end
144             -1,1:end-1));
145     U_new(:,2:end) = U_new(:,2:end)-U_new(:,1:end-1).*...
146         (p_el(1:end-1,1:end-1)==1 & p_el(1:end-1,1:end-1)~=p_el(1:end
147             -1,2:end));
148     V_new(1:end-1,:) = V_new(1:end-1,:)-V_new(2:end,:).*...
149         (p_el(2:end,1:end-1)==1 & p_el(2:end,1:end-1)~=p_el(1:end
150             -1,1:end-1));
151     V_new(2:end,:) = V_new(2:end,:)-V_new(1:end-1,:).*...
152         (p_el(1:end-1,1:end-1)==1 & p_el(1:end-1,1:end-1)~=p_el(2:end
153             ,1:end-1));
154
155     % domain boundaries
156     Uwb = [zeros(1,ny+2); [-U_new(:,1) U_new(:,2) -U_new(:,end)];...
157         zeros(1,ny+2)];
158     Vwb = [[0 -V_new(1,:) 0]; [zeros(nx,1) V_new(:,2) zeros(nx,1)];...
159         [0 -V_new(end,:) 0]];
160
161 else
162     U_new = U_old;
163     V_new = V_old;
164 end
165
166 %% waitbar update
167 if param.display.waitbar == 1
168     [f,timearray,up] = waitbar2D_simple(f,param,timearray,toc,t,up);
169 end
170 %% dump variables
171 if mod(t,param.save.intervall) == 0
172     T(:,s) = T_new;
173     if param.convection == 1
174         Ut(:,s) = U_new;
175         Vt(:,s) = V_new;
176     end
177     s = s+1;
178 end
179 if param.save.make_snapshot == 1
180     if mod(t,param.save.snapshot_int)==0
181         strFilename = sprintf('results/dump_%s_t%03d.mat',param.save.
182             name,t);
183         if param.convection == 1
184             save(strFilename,'C','K','R','t','T_new','T_old','U_new',
185                 ...
186                 'V_new','U_old','V_old','H','Q_in','Q_out','H_1','param')
187         ;
188         else
189             save(strFilename,'C','K','R','t','T_new','T_old',...
190                 'H','Q_in','Q_out','H_1','param');
191         end
192     end
193 end
194
195 %% initialize T,U,V for next timestep
196 T_old = T_new;
197 U_old = U_new;
198 V_old = V_new;

```

```

192
193 % save temperature and time vector
194     T_save(idx) = T_new(param.sensor.non);
195     T_save2(idx) = T_new(param.sensor.bi);
196     T_save=[T_save1 T_save2];
197     T_save=T_save1;
198     t_vec(idx) = t;
199     idx=idx+1;
200
201 end
202
203 %% postprocessing
204 % figure;
205 % plot(t_vec,T_save);
206 % delete waitbar
207 if param.display.waitbar == 1
208     delete(f);
209 end
210 % save data
211 sim_time = toc;
212 % strFilename = sprintf('results\dump_%s_t.mat',param.save.name,t);
213 %clear gauss.qin1; clear gauss.qin2;
214 %clear gauss.qout1; clear gauss.qout2;
215 % save('results/dump_results_me_geom_test_1h');
216 T_new(param.sensor.non)=0;
217 % plots after total time
218 if param.display.Tplot == 1
219     makeplot(T_new,param);
220 end
221 if param.display.Vplot == 1
222     makeplot_konv(U_new,V_new,param);
223 end
224
225 % show simulation time
226 strTimestamp = datestr(now(),30); % get timestamp
227 % fprintf('Simulation complete / timestamp %s\n',strTimestamp);
228 sim_time = toc;
229 % fprintf('Total simulation time [s]: %5.0f\n',toc);
230 end

```

Listing A.12: Code of run file for the parameter estimation proof run_param_proof_PCM

```

1 %% parameter estimation proof PCM
2 % Author: Carlotta Tubeuf
3 % Last modified: 28.02.2020
4 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
5 % trivial input case
6 % load OED results
7 load('results/triv_pcm.mat');
8 T_ein = gamma_0;
9 T = zeros(param.mesh.not,4);
10 idx_set = 1:(param.mesh.not/4);
11 for jj = 1:4
12     T(idx_set,jj) = 1;
13     idx_set = idx_set+(param.mesh.not/4);
14 end
15 T_ein_triv = T*T_ein'; % trivial input trajectory
16 Y_tats_triv=Y_triv; % "measured" Y
17 % rounding Y to integer values
18 Y_noise_triv=Y_tats_triv;
19 for i=1:length(Y_tats_triv)
20     Y_noise_triv(i)=round(Y_tats_triv(i));
21 end
22 % actual parameter values
23 gamma_real=[param.pcm.k_s;param.icbc.alpha_in];
24 % initial parameter values for the estimation
25 gamma_0=gamma_real*0.1;

```

```

26 % objective function
27 my_obj = @(gamma) eval_obj_proof_PCM(gamma,param,T_ein,Y_noise_triv);
28 my_opts = optimoptions('fmincon','UseParallel', true);
29 my_opts.Display = 'iter';
30 % lower and upper bounds
31 lb=gamma_real*0.01; ub=gamma_real*10;
32 % call optimization
33 [gamma_triv,fval,exitflag,output] = fmincon(my_obj, gamma_0, [], [], [],
    [], lb,ub,[],my_opts);
34 % calculate estimated temperature curve
35 param.pcm.k_s=gamma(1); param.icbc.alpha_in=gamma(2);
36 [~,Y_opt_triv] = PCMsolver(param,T_ein);
37 param.pcm.k_s=gamma_real(1); param.icbc.alpha_in=gamma_real(2);
38 %% det-optimized input case
39 load('results/det_PCM.mat');
40 T_ein = gamma;
41 T = zeros(param.mesh.not,4);
42 idx_set = 1:(param.mesh.not/4);
43 for jj = 1:4
44     T(idx_set,jj) = 1;
45     idx_set = idx_set+(param.mesh.not/4);
46 end
47 T_ein_det = T*T_ein';
48 Y_tats_det=Y_opt;
49 Y_noise_det=Y_tats_det;
50 for i=1:length(Y_tats_det)
51     Y_noise_det(i)=round(Y_tats_det(i));
52 end
53 gamma_real=[param.pcm.k_s;param.icbc.alpha_in];
54 gamma_0=gamma_real*0.1;
55 my_obj = @(gamma) eval_proof_PCM_objective(gamma,param,T_ein,Y_noise_det)
    ;
56 my_opts = optimoptions('fmincon','UseParallel', true);
57 my_opts.Display = 'iter';
58 lb=gamma_real*0.01; ub=gamma_real*10;
59 [gamma_det,fval,exitflag,output] = fmincon(my_obj, gamma_0, [], [], [],
    [], lb,ub,[],my_opts);
60 param.pcm.k_s=gamma_det(1); param.icbc.alpha_in=gamma_det(2);
61 [~,Y_opt_det] = PCMsolver(param,T_ein);
62 param.pcm.k_s=gamma_real(1); param.icbc.alpha_in=gamma_real(2);
63 %% trace-optimized input case
64 load('results/trace_PCM.mat');
65 T_ein = gamma;
66 T = zeros(param.mesh.not,4);
67 idx_set = 1:(param.mesh.not/4);
68 for jj = 1:4
69     T(idx_set,jj) = 1;
70     idx_set = idx_set+(param.mesh.not/4);
71 end
72 T_ein_trace = T*T_ein';
73 Y_tats_trace=Y_opt;
74 Y_noise_trace=Y_tats_trace;
75 for i=1:length(Y_tats_trace)
76     Y_noise_trace(i)=round(Y_tats_trace(i));
77 end
78 gamma_real=[param.pcm.k_s;param.icbc.alpha_in];
79 gamma_0=gamma_real*0.1;
80 my_obj = @(gamma) eval_proof_PCM_objective(gamma,param,T_ein,
    Y_noise_trace);
81 my_opts = optimoptions('fmincon','UseParallel', true);
82 my_opts.Display = 'iter';
83 lb=gamma_real*0.01; ub=gamma_real*10;
84 [gamma_trace,fval,exitflag,output] = fmincon(my_obj, gamma_0, [], [], [],
    [], lb,ub,[],my_opts);
85 param.pcm.k_s=gamma(1); param.icbc.alpha_in=gamma(2);
86 [~,Y_opt_trace] = PCMsolver(param,T_ein);
87 param.pcm.k_s=gamma_real(1); param.icbc.alpha_in=gamma_real(2);
88 %% mineig-optimized load case

```

```

89 load('results/mineig_pcm.mat');
90 T_ein = gamma;
91 T = zeros(param.mesh.not,4);
92 idx_set = 1:(param.mesh.not/4);
93 for jj = 1:4
94     T(idx_set,jj) = 1;
95     idx_set = idx_set+(param.mesh.not/4);
96 end
97 T_ein_gew_mineig = T*T_ein';
98 Y_tats_mineig=Y_opt;
99 Y_noise_mineig=Y_tats_mineig;
100 for i=1:length(Y_tats_mineig)
101     Y_noise_mineig(i)=round(Y_tats_mineig(i));
102 end
103 gamma_real=[param.pcm.k_s;param.icbc.alpha_in];
104 gamma_0=gamma_real*0.9;
105 my_obj = @(gamma) eval_proof_PCM_objective(gamma,param,T_ein,
106     Y_noise_mineig);
107 my_opts = optimoptions('fmincon','UseParallel',true);
108 my_opts.Display = 'iter';
109 lb=gamma_real*0.01; ub=gamma_real*10;
110 [gamma_mineig,fval,exitflag,output] = fmincon(my_obj, gamma_0, [], [],
111     [], [], lb,ub, [],my_opts);
112 param.pcm.k_s=gamma(1); param.icbc.alpha_in=gamma(2);
113 [~,Y_opt_mineig] = PCMsolver(param,T_ein);
114 param.pcm.k_s=gamma_real(1); param.icbc.alpha_in=gamma_real(2);

```

Listing A.13: Code of parameter estimation objective evaluation function `eval_obj_proof_PCM`

```

1 %% objective evaluation for parameter estimation PCM
2 % Author: Carlotta Tubeuf
3 % Last modified: 28.02.2020
4 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
5 function proof_obj = eval_obj_proof_PCM(gamma_vec,param,T_ein,Y_measured)
6 % param.pcm.k_l=gamma_vec(1);
7 param.pcm.k_s=gamma_vec(1);
8 % param.pcm.Tm=gamma_vec(3);
9 param.icbc.alpha_in=gamma_vec(2);
10 % param.pcm.beta=gamma_vec(1);
11 % param.pcm.mue=gamma_vec(2);
12
13 % call PCM solver
14 [~,Y] = PCMsolver(param,T_ein);
15 % calculate distance between measured and optimized temperature curve
16 proof_obj = norm(Y-Y_measured);
17 end

```

A.3 Upscaling of the Hybrid Storage

Listing A.14: Code of upscaling function `func_ruthscal`

```

1 %% RSS + Hybrid Storage Upscaling + Cost Estimation
2 % Author: Carlotta Tubeuf
3 % Last modified: 11.03.2020
4 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
5 function [RU]=func_ruthscal(p_RU)
6 % Include thermodynamic property library
7 addpath(genpath('\XSteam\'));
8 % Input variables

```

```

9 % Input variables RSS
10 LtD=3; % length / diameter relation [1]
11 Level1=0.9; % target filling level [1]
12 rho_St=7850; % density of vessel steel [kg/m^3]
13 % Input variables PCM
14 s_PCM=0.03; % thickness PCM module PCM [m]
15 s_RUPCM=0.003; % wall thickness RSS to PCM [m]
16 s_ALU=0.001; % thickness of aluminium fin [m]
17 x_ALU=.008; % mean distance between aluminium fins [m]
18 b_PCM=0.555; % width of one PCM module [m]
19 phi_modul=135; % vessel encase angle PCM [°]
20 phi_PCM=120; % filling angle PCM [°]
21 rho_PCM=2317; % density of PCM [kg/m^3]
22 rho_ALU=2800; % density of aluminium [kg/m^3]
23 Tm_PCM=192; % melting temperature PCM [°C]
24 cpL_PCM=1.726; % specific heat capacity liquid [kJ/kgK]
25 h_PCM=309.1; % phase change enthalpy [kJ/kg]
26 % Cost coefficients
27 c_RU=10; % assumed price of RSS vessel per kg [€/kg]
28 c_iso=120; % assumed price of insulation per m^2 [€/m^2]
29 c_other=2; % assumed price of supporting steel structure etc. [€/kg]
30 c_PCM=3.7; % assumed price of PCM per kg [€/kg]
31 c_ALU=2.15; % assumed price of aluminium per kg [€/kg]
32 %% Upscaling
33 % Initial values
34 Vol_Z=1; % starting value for the volume of the vessel cylinder [m
^3]
35 Vol_K=1; % starting value for the volume of the vessels' dished
bottoms [m^3]
36 index=1;
37 for Q_RU=0.1*(3.6*1E+6):0.1*(3.6*1E+6):40*(3.6*1E+6) % calculating for a
range of loading scenarios
38 t_RU=XSteam('Tsat_P',p_RU); % temperature inside RSS at p_RU [°C]
39 hV_RU=XSteam('hV_p',p_RU); % vapour phase specific enthalpy [kJ/kg]
40 hL_RU=XSteam('hL_p',p_RU); % liquid phase specific enthalpy [kJ/kg]
41 rhoV_RU=XSteam('rhoV_p',p_RU); % vapour phase density [kg/m^3]
42 rhoL_RU=XSteam('rhoL_p',p_RU); % liquid phase density [kg/m^3]
43 % starting values for iteration
44 a=0.1;
45 b=10000;
46 % iteration of liquid phase volume
47 f2=@(VolL_RU)VolL_RU*0.1/0.9*rhoV_RU*hV_RU+VolL_RU*rhoL_RU*hL_RU-Q_RU
;
48 while f2(b)>0.00001
49 if f2((a+b)/2)<0
50 a=(a+b)/2;
51 else
52 b=(a+b)/2;
53 end
54 end
55 VolL_RU=b; % liquid phase volume [m^3]
56 VolV_RU=VolL_RU/Level1*(1-Level1); % vapor phase volume [m^3]
57 Vol_RU=VolL_RU+VolV_RU; % volume of vapor-liquid-mixture inside
the RSS [m^3]
58 mV_RU=rhoV_RU*VolV_RU; % vapor phase mass [kg]
59 mL_RU=rhoL_RU*VolL_RU; % liquid phase mass [kg]
60 % iteration of RSS inner diameter
61 s_K=1*1E-3;
62 si_K=10*1E-3;
63 a=0.01;
64 b=1000;
65 f3=@(Di)Di^2*(Di*LtD)*pi/4+(0.1*Di^3+Di^2*3.5*si_K*0.785)*2-Vol_RU;
66 while f3(b)>0.00001
67 if f3((a+b)/2)<0
68 a=(a+b)/2;
69 else
70 b=(a+b)/2;
71 end

```

```

72 end
73 Di=b; % inner diameter of RSS vessel [m]
74 % iteration of wall thickness of the RSS vessel
75 s=1*1E-3;
76 si=10*1E-3;
77 while s<si
78     s=s+1*1E-3;
79     % allocation of allowable stress for respective wall thickness
80     if s<=16*1E-3
81         f=460*1E+6/2.4;
82     elseif s<=40*1E-3
83         f=445*1E+6/2.4;
84     elseif s<=60*1E-3
85         f=430*1E+6/2.4;
86     else
87         f=400*1E+6/2.4;
88     end
89     % minimum necessary wall thickness
90     smin=(p_RU*1E+5)*(Di+2*s)/((2*f-(p_RU*1E+5))*1+2*(p_RU*1E+5));
91     si=ceil(smin*1E+03)*1E-03; % rounding of wall thickness values
92 end
93 s=ceil(smin*1E+03)*1E-03; % wall thickness of the RSS vessel [m]
94 Da=Di+2*s; % outer diameter of RSS vessel [m]
95 Vol_Z=Di^2*Di*LtD*pi/4; % cylindrical volume of RSS vessel [m^3]
96 % iteration of wall thickness for torispherical heads
97 while s_K<si_K
98     s_K=s_K+1*1E-3;
99     % allocation of allowable stress for respective wall thickness
100    if s_K<=16*1E-3
101        f_K=460*1E+6/2.4;
102    elseif s_K<=40*1E-3
103        f_K=445*1E+6/2.4;
104    elseif s_K<=60*1E-3
105        f_K=430*1E+6/2.4;
106    else
107        f_K=400*1E+6/2.4;
108    end
109    smin_K=(p_RU*1E+5)*Da*1/2/f_K; % minimum wall thickness for
    % dished bottoms
110    si_K=ceil(smin_K*1E+03)*1E-03; % rounding of wall thickness
    % values
111 end
112 s_K=ceil(smin_K*1E+03)*1E-03; % wall thickness of torispherical
    % heads [m]
113 Vol_K=(0.1*(Da-s_K)^3+(Da-s_K)^2*3.5*s_K*0.785)*2; % volume of
    % torispherical heads [m^3]
114 A_K=(0.99*Da^2+3.5*s_K*Da*pi)*2; % outer surface of torispherical
    % heads [m^2]
115 Vol=Vol_Z+Vol_K; % total volume of RSS vessel [m
    % ^3]
116 A_Z=Da^2*LtD*pi; % shell surface of RSS [m^2]
117 A_RU=A_Z+A_K; % total surface area of RSS [m^2]
118 m_Z=(Da^2-Di^2)*pi*3*Da*rho_St/4; % mass of cylindrical vessel part
    % [kg]
119 m_K=((0.1*Da^3+Da^2*3.5*s_K*0.785)*2-Vol_K)*rho_St; % mass of
    % torispherical heads [kg]
120 m_RU=m_Z+m_K; % total steel mass [kg]
121 % PCM module calculation
122 N=floor(3*Da/b_PCM)*2; % number of modules per RSS [1]
123 Di_PCM=Da+2*s_RUPCM; % inner diameter PCM module [m]
124 Da_PCM=Da+2*(s_RUPCM+s_PCM); % outer diameter PCM module [m]
125 n_cell=floor(((pi*Da_PCM*phi_modul)/360)/x_ALU); % number of PCM
    % cells per module [1]
126 A_PCM=(Da_PCM+s_RUPCM)^2*LtD*pi; % shell surface of hybrid storage [m
    % ^2]
127 Vol_ALU=n_cell*(2*s_PCM*s_ALU+(x_ALU-s_ALU)*s_ALU)*b_PCM; % volume
    % aluminium fins per module [m^3]

```

```

128     Vol_modul=((pi/4)*(phi_modul/360)*(Da_PCM^2-Di_PCM^2)*b_PCM); %
           volume of 1 PCM module [m^3]
129     Vol_PCM=(Vol_modul-((phi_PCM/phi_modul)*Vol_ALU)); % volume PCM per
           module [m^3]
130     m_ALU=N*Vol_ALU*rho_ALU; % total mass of aluminium fins [kg]
131     m_PCM=N*Vol_PCM*rho_PCM; % total mass of PCM [kg]
132     Q_PCM=m_PCM*(h_PCM+cpL_PCM*(t_RU-Tm_PCM)); % total stored energy in
           liquid PCM [kJ]
133     % Cost calculation
134     Cost_RU=m_RU*c_RU; % material costs of storage vessel [€]
135     Cost_iso_RU=A_RU*c_iso; % isolation costs mere RSS [€]
136     Cost_other=(m_RU/3)*c_other; % supporting steel strucutre costs RSS
           [€]
137     Cost_iso=((A_PCM+A_K)*c_iso); % isolatoin costs hybrid storage [€]
138     Cost_ALU=m_ALU*c_ALU; % material costs aluminium fins [€]
139     Cost_PCM=m_PCM*c_PCM; % material costs PCM [€]
140     Cost_total=Cost_RU+Cost_PCM+Cost_ALU+Cost_iso+Cost_other; % total
           costs hybrid storage [€]
141
142     % saving variables for the range of loading enthalpy values
143     vektor_Q_RU(index,1)=Q_RU/(3.6*1E+6); % maximum capacity of the RSS [
           MWh]
144     vektor_Q_PCM(index,1)=Q_PCM/(3.6*1E+6); % maximum capacity of the PCM
           modules [MWh]
145     vektor_t_RU(index,1)=t_RU;
146     vektor_Vol_RU(index,1)=Vol_RU;
147     vektor_Di(index,1)=Di;
148     vektor_Da(index,1)=Da;
149     vektor_s(index,1)=s;
150     vektor_A_RU(index,1)=A_RU;
151     vektor_m_RU(index,1)=m_RU;
152     vektor_Cost_RU(index,1)=Cost_RU;
153     vektor_Cost_PCM(index,1)=Cost_PCM;
154     vektor_Cost_ALU(index,1)=Cost_ALU;
155     vektor_Cost_other(index,1)=Cost_other;
156     vektor_Cost_RSS(index,1)=Cost_RU+Cost_iso_RU+Cost_other;
157     vektor_Cost_iso_RU(index,1)=Cost_iso_RU;
158     vektor_Cost_iso(index,1)=Cost_iso;
159     vektor_Cost_total(index,1)=Cost_total;
160     index=index+1;
161 end
162 RU.Q_RU=vektor_Q_RU;
163 R.Q_PCM=vektor_Q_PCM;
164 RU.t_RU=vektor_t_RU;
165 RU.Vol_RU=vektor_Vol_RU;
166 RU.Di=vektor_Di;
167 RU.Da=vektor_Da;
168 RU.s=vektor_s;
169 RU.A_RU=vektor_A_RU;
170 RU.m_RU=vektor_m_RU;
171 RU.Cost_RU=vektor_Cost_RU;
172 RU.Cost_PCM=vektor_Cost_PCM;
173 RU.Cost_ALU=vektor_Cost_ALU;
174 RU.Cost_other=vektor_Cost_other;
175 RU.Cost_RSS=vektor_Cost_RSS;
176 RU.Cost_iso_RU=vektor_Cost_iso_RU;
177 RU.Cost_iso=vektor_Cost_iso;
178 RU.Cost_total=vektor_Cost_total;
179 end

```

Appendix B

Experimental Plan

In this appendix, the experimental plans for the experiments on the hybrid storage as well as the reference steam storage are presented. Note that the plan for the experiments with the optimized input trajectories for the hybrid storage is not finalized yet.

B.1 Experimental Plans

Versuch Nr	Versuchsdauer [min]	Startwerte Speicher			Beladen		Halten (p=konst.) Dauer [min]	Werte nach Beladen			Entladen		Halten (p=konst.) Dauer [min]	Werte nach Entladen			Beschreibung
		Füllgrad [%]	Temp. [°C]	Druck [bar]	Dauer [min]	Druck [bar]		Füllgrad [%]	Temp. [°C]	Druck [bar]	Dauer [min]	Druck [bar]		Füllgrad [%]	Temp. [°C]	Druck [bar]	
Be- und Entladen mit konstantem Druck																	
A.010	60	60	180	10	30	15	--	65	200	15	30	10	--	60	180	10	Aufwärmen
A.020	180	60	180	10	90	20	--	67	210	20	90	10	--	60	180	10	konstante Beladung bis quasistationär, wieder komplett entladen
A.030	180	60	180	10	90	23	--	70	220	23	90	7	--	57	165	7	konstante Beladung bis auf Maximaldruck, Entladen bis Minimaldruck
A.040	600	60	180	10	40	20	--	67	210	20	560	0	--	--	--	--	konstante Beladung bis quasistationär, Abkapseln, über Nacht beobachten
A.050	40	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	40	10	--	60	180	10	Entladen auf Startbedingungen
Rampentrajektorie: ansteigende Be- bzw. Entladung bis gewünschter Druck in vorgegebener Zeit erreicht ist																	
B.010	90	60	180	10	30	15	15	65	200	15	30	10	15	60	180	10	Aufwärmen
B.020	150	60	180	10	30	20	60	67	210	20	30	10	30	60	180	10	Beladung bis quasistationär, halten, wieder komplett entladen
B.030	120	60	180	10	30	23	30	70	220	23	30	10	30	60	180	10	Beladung bis auf Maximaldruck, Entladen

Figure B.1: Plan for the trivial experiments on the RSS

Versuch Nr	Versuchsdauer [min]	Startwerte Speicher			Beladen		Halten (p=konst.)	Werte nach Beladen			Entladen		Halten (p=konst.)	Werte nach Entladen			Beschreibung	
		Füllgrad [%]	Temp. [°C]	Druck [bar]	Dauer [min]	Druck [bar]	Dauer [min]	Füllgrad [%]	Temp. [°C]	Druck [bar]	Dauer [min]	Druck [bar]	Dauer [min]	Füllgrad [%]	Temp. [°C]	Druck [bar]		
Rampentrajektorie: ansteigende Be- bzw. Entladung bis gewünschter Druck in vorgegebener Zeit erreicht ist																		
C.010	180																	Stufenweises Aufheizen, wieder Entladen
C.011	30	60	180	10	15	13	15	63	190	13	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
C.012	30	62	190	13	15	16	15	65	200	16	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
C.013	30	65	200	16	15	19	15	67	210	19	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	
C.014	90	67	210	19	15	23	15	70	220	23	30	10	30	60	180	10		
C.020	360																	Abwechselndes Be- und Entladen
C.021	60	60	180	10	15	19	15	67	210	19	15	13	15	63	190	13		
C.022	60	63	190	13	15	19	15	67	210	19	15	13	15	63	190	13		
C.023	60	63	190	13	15	19	15	67	210	19	15	13	15	63	190	13		
C.024	60	63	190	13	15	23	15	68	220	23	15	13	15	63	190	13		
C.025	60	63	190	13	15	19	15	67	210	19	15	13	15	63	190	13		
C.026	60	63	190	13	15	16	15	65	200	16	15	10	15	60	180	10		
C.030	280																	Be- und Entladen auf Maximal- bzw. Minimaldruck
C.031	80	60	180	10	30	23	10	69	220	23	30	7	10	58	170	7		
C.032	80	57	165	7	30	23	10	69	220	23	30	7	10	58	170	7		
C.033	120	57	165	7	30	23	50	69	220	23	30	10	10	60	180	10		

Figure B.2: Plan for the detailed experiments on the RSS

Versuch Nr	Versuchsdauer [min]	Startwerte Speicher			Beladen		Werte nach Beladen			Halten (p=konst.)	Entladen		Werte nach Entladen			Halten (p=konst.)	Beschreibung
		Füllgrad [%]	Temp. [°C]	Druck [bar]	Dauer [min]	mit Druck [bar]	Füllgrad [%]	Temp. [°C]	Druck [bar]	Dauer [min]	Dauer [min]	mit Druck [bar]	Füllgrad [%]	Temp. [°C]	Druck [bar]	Dauer [min]	
Be- und Entladen mit konstantem Druck																	
D.010	60																
D.011	15	60	180	10	15	18,6	66	205	17,5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	optimierte Trajektorie: bestimmen von Verlust- Füllgrad- und Massenstromparametern
D.012	30	66	207	18	15	22,1	68,7	217,4	22,1	--	15	10,6	62	190	12,4	--	
D.013	15	62,8	193,5	13,6	--	--	--	--	--	--	15	10	60	180	10	--	
D.014	30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	30	10	60	180	10	--	Entladen auf Startbedingungen
D.020	60																
D.021	15	60	180	10	15	14,8	63,6	197	14,7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	optimierte Trajektorie: bestimmen von Verlust- und Füllgradparameter
D.022	30	63,6	197	14,7	15	23	69	218	22,5	--	15	10,6	62,1	190	12,6	--	
D.023	15	62,1	190	12,6	--	--	--	--	--	--	15	7,8	58,3	171,5	8	--	
D.024	30	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	30	10	60	180	10	--	Entladen auf Startbedingungen

Figure B.3: Plan for the optimized experiments on the RSS

Nr	Dauer [min]	Startwerte Speicher			Startwert Zellen Temp. [°C]	Beladen			Halten (p=konst.) Dauer [min]	RSS Werte nach Beladen			PCM nach Beladen Temp. [°C]	Entladen			Halten (p=konst.) Dauer [min]	RSS Werte nach Entladen			PCM nach Ent-laden Temp. [°C]	Beschreibung
		Füllgrad [%]	Temp. [°C]	Druck [bar]		Dauer [min]	Druck [bar]	Füllgrad [%]		Temp. [°C]	Druck [bar]	Dauer [min]		Druck [bar]	Dauer [min]	Füllgrad [%]		Temp. [°C]	Druck [bar]	Temp. [°C]		
Be- und Entladen mit konstantem Druck																						
E.010	60	60	180	10	180	30	20	--	68	212	20	196	30	10	--	60	180	10	190	Aufwärmen		
E.020	180	60	180	10	180	90	20	--	69	212	20	212	90	10	--	60	180	10	180	konstante Beladung bis quasistationär, wieder komplett entladen		
E.030	180	60	180	10	180	90	23	--	70	220	23	220	90	7	--	57	165	7	165	konstante Beladung bis auf Maximaldruck, Entladen		
E.040	600	60	180	10	180	40	20	--	68	212	20	212	560	0	--	--	--	--	--	konstante Beladung bis quasistationär, Abkapseln, beobachten		
E.050	40	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	40	10	--	60	180	10	180	Entladen auf Startbedingungen		
Rampentrajektorie: ansteigende Be- bzw. Entladung bis gewünschter Druck in vorgegebener Zeit erreicht ist																						
F.010	90	60	180	10	180	30	15	15	64	198	15	192	30	10	15	60	180	10	180	Aufwärmen		
F.020	135	60	180	10	180	30	20	60	68	212	20	212	30	10	15	60	180	10	190	konstante Beladung bis quasistationär, wieder komplett entladen		
F.030	90	60	180	10	180	30	23	30	70	220	23	209	30	10	30	60	180	10	190	konstante Beladung bis auf Maximaldruck, Entladen		

Figure B.4: Plan for the trivial experiments on the hybrid storage

Nr	Dauer [min]	Startwerte Speicher			Start-wert Zellen Temp. [°C]	Beladen		Halten (p= konst.) Dauer [min]	Werte nach Beladen			PCM nach Beladen Temp. [°C]	Entladen		Halten (p= konst.) Dauer [min]	Werte nach Entladen			PCM nach Ent-laden Temp. [°C]	Beschreibung	
		Füllgrad [%]	Temp. [°C]	Druck [bar]		Dauer [min]	bis Druck [bar]		Füllgrad [%]	Temp. [°C]	Druck [bar]		Dauer [min]	bis Druck [bar]		Dauer [min]	Füllgrad [%]	Temp. [°C]			Druck [bar]
Rampentrajektorie: ansteigende Be- bzw. Entladung bis gewünschter Druck in vorgegebener Zeit erreicht ist																					
G.010	180																				Stufenweises Aufheizen, wieder Entladen
G.011	30	60	180	10	180	15	13	15	63	192	13	192	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
G.012	30	63	192	13	192	15	16	15	65	202	16	193	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
G.013	30	65	202	16	193	15	19	15	67	210	19	197	--	--	--	--	--	--	--		
G.014	90	67	210	19	197	15	23	15	70	220	23	218	30	10	30	60	180	10	190		
G.020	360																				Abwechselndes Be- und Entladen
G.021	60	60	180	10	180	15	19	15	66.5	210	19	194	15	13	15	63	192	13	192		
G.022	60	63	192	13	192	15	19	15	67	210	19	197	15	13	15	63	192	13	192		
G.023	60	63	192	13	192	15	19	15	67.5	210	19	208	15	13	15	63	192	13	192		
G.024	60	63	192	13	192	15	23	15	70	220	23	217	15	13	15	63	192	13	192		
G.025	60	63	192	13	192	15	19	15	67.5	210	19	208	15	13	15	63	192	13	192		
G.026	60	63	192	13	192	15	16	15	65.5	202	16	201	15	10	15	60.5	180	10	190		
G.030	280																				Be- und Entladen auf Maximal- bzw. Minimaldruck
G.031	80	60	180	10	180	30	23	10	69.5	220	22	197	30	7	10	58.5	170	8	188		
G.032	80	58.5	170	8	188	30	23	10	69	219	22	197	30	7	10	58.5	170	8	188		
G.033	120	58.5	170	8	188	30	23	50	70	220	23	220	30	10	10	61	180	10	191		

Figure B.5: Plan for the detailed experiments on the hybrid storage

B.2 Experimental Matrix

	Tag 1		Tag 2		Tag 3		Tag 4		Tag 5	
	Nr.	Dauer [h]	Nr.	Dauer [h]	Nr.	Dauer [h]	Nr.	Dauer [h]	Nr.	Dauer [h]
Vormittag	A.010	01:00	A.050	00:40	A.010	01:00	A.010	01:00	A.010	01:00
	A.020	03:00	B.010	01:30	C.010	03:00	C.020	06:00	D.010	01:30
Nachmittag	A.030	03:00	B.020	02:30	C.030	04:40			C.010	03:00
			B.030	02:00					D.010	01:30
			B.030	02:00						
über Nacht	A.040*	10:00							A.040*	10:00
	Tag 6		Tag 7		Tag 8		Tag 9		Tag 10	
	Nr.	Dauer [h]	Nr.	Dauer [h]	Nr.	Dauer [h]	Nr.	Dauer [h]	Nr.	Dauer [h]
Vormittag	A.050	00:40	B.010	01:30	A.010	01:00	A.010	01:00	A.050	00:40
	A.010	01:00	B.020	02:30	C.010	03:00	A.020	03:00	B.010	01:30
Nachmittag	C.020	06:00	D.010	01:30	C.030	04:40	A.030	03:00	B.020	02:30
			D.010	01:30					B.030	02:00
									B.030	02:00
über Nacht							A.040*	10:00		

* übers Wochenende abkühlen lassen und beobachten

Figure B.6: Schedule for the experiments on the RSS

	Tag 1		Tag 2		Tag 3		Tag 4		Tag 5	
	Nr.	Dauer [h]	Nr.	Dauer [h]	Nr.	Dauer [h]	Nr.	Dauer [h]	Nr.	Dauer [h]
Vormittag	E.010	01:00	E.050	00:40	E.010	01:00	E.010	01:00	E.010	01:00
	E.020	03:00	F.010	01:30	G.010	03:00	G.020	06:00	H.010	01:30
Nachmittag	E.030	03:00	F.020	02:30	G.030	04:40			H.020	01:30
			F.030	02:00					H.010	01:30
			F.030	02:00					H.020	01:30
über Nacht	E.040*	10:00							E.040*	10:00
	Tag 6		Tag 7		Tag 8		Tag 9		Tag 10	
	Nr.	Dauer [h]	Nr.	Dauer [h]	Nr.	Dauer [h]	Nr.	Dauer [h]	Nr.	Dauer [h]
Vormittag	E.050	00:40	F.010	01:30	E.010	01:00	E.010	01:00	E.050	00:40
	E.010	01:00	F.020	02:30	G.010	03:00	E.020	03:00	F.020	01:30
Nachmittag	G.020	06:00	H.010	01:30	G.030	04:40	E.030	03:00	F.020	02:30
			H.020	01:30					F.030	02:00
									F.030	02:00
über Nacht							E.040*	10:00		

* übers Wochenende abkühlen lassen und beobachten

Figure B.7: Schedule for the experiments on the hybrid storage